

**The impact of Marketing Strategies on the profitability of
Convenience Stores in the United Kingdom**

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Abstract

Purpose – The research purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between marketing mix strategies and the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. Furthermore, it explores how marketing mix strategies drive convenience stores' profitability and how the improvement of convenience store's performance is contingent upon marketing mix strategies.

Design/methodology/approach – This study draws on 280 questionnaires from convenience store business owners or managers in the United Kingdom through online participants and rich secondary data from previous literature. This research uses a quantitative method to explore the marketing mix strategies in the convenience store industry and the data analysis was used (SPSS) the statistical package for social science. The analysis explores the demography and other relevant issues from respondents' regarding their marketing strategies and the profitability of convenience stores.

Findings – The findings revealed that marketing mix strategies (product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, process, and physical evidence) appear to positively impact the companies' profitability. Moreover, it shows that price and product differentiation is the most important aspect when business owners or managers apply marketing mix strategies. This indicates that convenience stores in the United Kingdom compete primarily based on price and product differentiation. In addition, the empirical findings present that in order for business owners or managers to increase their stores' profitability, they need to adopt at least 3 Ps of the marketing strategy, specifically product, price, and places.

Theoretical and Practical implications – This study contributes to prior studies on marketing and marketing mix strategies, particularly their dimensions and impact on profitability. It presents a new conceptual framework in this research area based on the United Kingdom convenience stores industry. This research supports the idea of applying marketing mix strategies that will generate positive business performance and increase profitability.

Originality/value – The author makes a significant contribution to the marketing mix literature by exploring contemporary issues regarding the relationships between the marketing mix and profitability of the United Kingdom convenience stores, thus moving beyond the marketing mix strategies and profitability relationships investigated in

extant studies. The author adds value to the research by providing insight into marketing mix strategies. The results theoretically and empirically draw out key factors for business owners' and managers' motivation in engaging with marketing mix strategies practices, therefore driving the company's profitability and business performance.

Keywords: Convenience stores, Marketing strategies, United Kingdom, Profitability, Product differentiation, Price, Promotion, Place, Process, People, Physical evidence.

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is my original work and it has never been submitted for a postgraduate, graduate, or undergraduate degree. I declare that I wrote it all on my own.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Chapter overview

This chapter's purpose is to reflect on the problem statement and outline the steps involved in carrying out the study. It also describes the contribution the proposed study would make to the industry. In Section 1.2 starts by providing an overview of the studies background context as well as the thesis's primary objectives. Section 1.2.1 discusses marketing mix strategy, followed by Section 1.3, which discusses the problem statement. The main objectives in Sections 1.4 and proposed research questions for this study are then explained in Sections 1.5. Following that, the rationale of the study explains in Section 1.6 and the methodology and hypothesis test explains in Section 1.7. Lastly, the thesis outline and overall structure of this dissertation discusses in section 1.8.

1.2 Study Background

This research attempt to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. A marketing strategy is a business approach used by a firm to achieve its objectives and reach the target markets (Morgan et al., 2019). For example Convenience Store Company use a strategy for converting prospective customers into paying customers for their products and services. Among other things, a marketing strategy includes information on target customers' demographics, important product demands, and the value of company's proposal, among other advanced considerations (Morgan et al., 2019). In addition, according to Fifield (2012), a marketing strategy is used by a Convenience Store Company to attempt to reach their target markets. A good marketing strategy should be centred on the appropriate product variety to maximise potential profits and ensure the company's long-term sustainability (Fifield 2012).

Nowadays, owners of convenience stores face many challenges, particularly in the highly competitive markets and during periods of economic instability. The challenges include increased of competitors, decreased consumer demand, decreased sales, which may decline their profitability and competitive advantage (Lee & Ha, 2012). Convenience stores competitors in the United Kingdom are consider high, in the

mainland UK, there are 46,262 convenience stores, and there are 5,765 convenience stores in London. However, according to Wells, (2019) show that the number of convenience stores that closed their doors increased by 590 stores in 2018 compared to 266 units in 2017. Additionally, the North West experienced the largest growth in independents in 2018 with (+1.0%) +395 units, whereas Greater London and Yorkshire & the Humber experienced the largest declines with (-1.4%) -429 units and (-0.5%) -377 units respectively (Wells, 2019). Convenience stores were the only industry, according to the data, that did not experience growth, with chain operators' competition growing more pronounced (Wells, 2019).

Therefore, in order to grow and sustain their business, convenience stores may need to use new marketing tools to draw in and keep customers, boost sales, optimise their offerings, and create a thorough understanding of customer needs. In addition to increasing profitability and outperform competitors' strategies and performance, convenience store owners should improve their competitive position (Desai, 2013).

Small business owners, such as those who operate independent convenience stores, have to create marketing plans that contribute to resource efficiency and profitability. Due to resource constraints, companies today face a challenge in developing relationships with customers through marketing (Fiore et al., 2013). According to Harrigan et al., (2011), marketing strategies for smaller enterprises differ from those for big organisations due to their restricted resources. Convenience store managers must do strategic market and competition analysis, as well as optimise their marketing strategy, in order to reach market value and profitability targets (Desai, 2013). Moreover, Ciemleja & Lace, (2011) stated that the capacity to respond to changes in market conditions is an internal aspect that determines corporate performance. Convenience store businesses cannot satisfy all of their existing customers; thus, they must constantly and continuously improve in order to create and maintain customer connections (Fiore et al., 2013). To retain customers, convenience store owners and managers should employ effective marketing strategies (Koutroumanis, 2011). Medium sized, independent convenience store owners should look for new ways to survive and profit in order to stay competitive.

It is critical to evaluate the marketing performance of a convenience store company in order to manage the business effectively and succeed in today's highly competitive markets. A marketing strategy of convenience stores should prioritise providing higher-quality services to customers while keeping costs as low as possible. However, determining the return on investment from marketing expenses on a business, such as promotion, advertising, staff costs, distribution, packaging, and customer service, is a very complex matter that retailers must consider before making decisions. (Katsikeas et al., 2019).

The marketing strategy begins with market research about consumers, prospect customers, business environment, and competitors. In addition, the marketing strategy continues through promotion, customer servicing, advertising, sales, packaging, and distribution (Morgan et al., 2019). For convenience stores' marketing strategy, a company has to analyse its marketing function into important elements along with an instrument in order to measure marketing strategy effectiveness (Katsikeas et al., 2016). Therefore, through the business analysis, the convenience stores company would understand how to create value for their customers. It will also lead to reducing marketing expenses and increasing shareholder value and profitability. The retailer of convenience stores will know which internal motives have an impact on the marketing value of the business. Commonly, many firms apply a marketing mix strategy to their business.

The company markets its goods and services by combining or mixing a variety of different types of marketing decisions that are variable in nature (Ali et al. 2017). As soon as market information and the surrounding environment have been gathered and identified, the next step is to determine which variable or instrument of strategy is most appropriate and necessary in order to meet customers' needs while also competing against competitors. There are four elements to the marketing mix, and they are as follows: product, price, location, and promotion (Chindasri et al., 2020). The convenience store company has a good chance of achieving its objectives, which include return on investment, market share, sales volume, and profit (Mohammadi et al. 2017). A profitable formula for marketing operations of convenience stores is that the majority of the marketing mix changes in response to changes in marketing conditions as well as changes in environmental conditions.

1.2.1 Marketing mix strategy

The marketing mix is a collection of controllable variables that a company can employ to influence the responses of potential customers (Ali et al. 2017). The convenience stores company can apply the marketing mix elements to influence the consumer's purchase decisions and increase profitability because the marketing mix is a controllable variable. Therefore, business owners or managers can make decisions on their budget expenditure to achieve company targets. They would choose and divide how much to spend on the total marketing budget between the variables in the marketing mix.

Marketing tools traditionally consist of 4 components: price, product, promotion and place (4Ps). However, according to Davcik and Sharma (2015), three new components have been added to marketing tools in order to boost the company's profitability: processes, people and physical evidence. The evolution of marketing strategy is happening because of the fierce competition among businesses in the retail industry or other sectors. Thus, the company need to choose the right strategy in order to sustain in business and achieve profitability otherwise it will be left behind in the competition. The evolution of the marketing mix from 4p to 7p demonstrates the addition of an important element from the fundamental marketing mix strategy. The objective of 7p is to create a more complete marketing mix so that the organisation may adopt a marketing strategy that includes all seven marketing strategy elements and still meet its goals. Many companies now recognise the importance of the 7Ps (product, pricing, location, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence) in business. The evolution of the marketing mix even goes further with different theorists.

Hood et al. (2016) stated that there has also been a significant economic and social transformation, which has altered consumers' perceptions of their own ability as well as their shopping habits. The convenience stores in the United Kingdom's retail atmosphere have changed significantly in recent years. Consumers nowadays have many choices to choose from, from local to imported products. The majority of consumers are very particular about the products they purchase, and their decisions are usually influenced by the product's quality and price. They will buy if they think the product has good value for the money. The capability and willingness to achieve these needs have also changed. Even though convenience stores in the United Kingdom

would provide for all consumer needs, however, it could be argued that convenience stores or grocery shops are unable to satisfy consumers' demands compared to bigger supermarkets, for example, Nisa Local Shop and Tesco Hypermarket. Although there are constant needs in the general sense, for example, basic needs like water, food, and household items, consumers' desires and needs have changed in these different behaviours. Based on the above observation, it is essential to apply specific strategies in order for convenience store companies to survive in a turbulent business environment (Harris et al., 2017).

1.3 Problem Statement

Marketing mix tactics are a collection of controllable marketing techniques which a company employ to fulfil the requirements of its target market (Nagle and Holden, 2012). The efforts taken by a corporation to assist in ensuring product demand are all included in the marketing mix strategy. Developing consumer insights and performance-enhancing initiatives must be the focus of aspirational businesses.

This research was motivated by gap of knowledge regarding the impact of the 7Ps of marketing strategy on the profitability of convenience stores. These 7Ps are product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, process, and physical evidence. Convenience stores face a variety of challenges that have an impact on the profitability of the industry. According to current data, over 99.9% of all enterprises in the UK are small and medium, employing 250 people or less. According to the latest official statistics, there are approximately 5.58 million businesses operating in the United Kingdom (Young, 2022). For small and medium-sized businesses to be sustainable and profitable, Parrott et al. (2010) claim that they must be able to identify the needs of the marketplace and the changes over time of the economy.

Additionally, about 20% of new firms fail in their first year, on average (Young, 2022). However, anyone may suffer from success, not just new business owners. According to the Insolvency Service's research, just one in three enterprises is able to continue for at least 10 years (Young, 2022). The typical business issue is that business owners of convenience stores face profitability difficulties as a result of marketing strategy

implementation. The business problem is that some independent convenience store owners do not have marketing plans that drive profitability (Young, 2022).

When it comes to business models, convenience stores are classified as small-range businesses that sell a selection of merchandises, for example magazines, toiletries, newspapers, groceries, tobacco, over-the-counter drugs (OTC drugs), confectionery, snack foods (such as chips and pretzels), soft drinks (such as soda) and household items (cleaning products) (Xin et al., 2021). Convenience stores in the United Kingdom are owned by local, Asian, or Middle Eastern people, and they entered these convenience store markets that developed fierce competition in the surrounding areas (Hood et al., 2016).

In today's world the convenience store business is classified as having a high level of competition and convenience store is no longer characterised by a low level of competitiveness industry. Businesses compete with one another over time to win consumers in a process known as competitive rivalry (Chang et al., 2019). Different things could lead to this rivalry. In some circumstances, the focus will be on achieving the lowest costs and prices possible in order to undercut rivals. In other instances, businesses go above and beyond this, using their entrepreneurial and innovative skills to create new goods and services, take advantage of specific strengths, aptitudes, or other advantages they may possess, and, in doing so, outperform rivals in terms of meeting customer needs. Along with price, range, quality, and convenience are all significant aspects of competition in the case of convenience stores. Competition in these conditions is likely to be marked by turbulence, uncertainty, and change. This rivalry process can be seen in things like how the market structure changes, how prices move over time, how non-price factors are changed, and how much new products are made (GLA Economics, 2005).

Another problem is nowadays, retailers have to compete for space with street vendors and large supermarkets, resulting in unprofitability in their business operations (Zhao et al., 2019). Retailers in the United Kingdom face competition from some large supermarkets including Tesco, Asda, Sainsbury's, and Mark and Spencer's outlets. Business owners of convenience stores find it difficult to compete with big companies

such as Tesco and Asda as they have the advantages of economies of scale. The advantages that sometimes result from expanding a business' size are called economies of scale (De Roest et al., 2018). Tesco, for instance, may benefit from economies of scale due to its large volume of purchases. It was able to obtain a lower price per unit than its rivals by making a large purchase all at once. Among them were getting better deals on buying, making distribution more efficient, and spreading fixed and mostly fixed costs over a larger number of sales. Therefore, convenience stores find it difficult to compete for prices with the big supermarket. Commonly, convenience stores offer slightly higher prices to consumers than big supermarkets because they cannot buy in bulk from suppliers to get cheaper costs (Lu et al., 2018).

When the economy is unstable, convenience store owners are significantly impacted and face numerous difficulties, including decreased disposable income, reduced customer demand and decreased sales that may jeopardise competitive advantage and their profitability (Lee & Ha, 2012). In addition, in many cases, convenience stores' capability of training and expertise for operating a business and starting an operation has never been tested and must be questioned because many entrepreneurs do not have proper expertise in this business. Therefore, convenience stores or corner shops must be as efficient and effective as they can in order to compete with many established companies. Businesses must take advantage of every opportunity that comes their way. (Cant et al., 2004).

London and other major cities in the United Kingdom were chosen because they are major business and financial centres from all over the country. The estimated population of Greater London in 2019 is 8,787,892 and three-quarters of the jobs in the City of London are in business services sectors, including financial and professional. London is the most diverse area within the UK and its population comes from many countries. (London Population, 2019).

According to the key statistics listed below, a convenience store in the United Kingdom is a massive business that has a great influence on the economy of country, and on its development and employment rates. The following are some key facts regarding convenience stores in the mainland of the UK as at December 2018: The total value of sales was £39.1 billion. Furthermore, convenience stores provide almost 365,000

jobs in the United Kingdom. In addition, there are 46,262 convenience shops located all over in the United Kingdom. Similarly, there are 5,765 convenience shops situated in London city of the United Kingdom. Additionally, independent retailers account for the operation of 72 percent of the nation's convenience stores (Ibisworld, 2018).

Moreover, according to (Dewar and Watson, 2018; Wiener et al., 2018) operating a convenience store is not an easy business and it is made even more difficult with multiple competitions and financial problems. There is a certain level of skill and personal commitment required to successfully address these challenges. As a result, more comprehensive research of the marketing strategies used by business owners in the United Kingdom is necessary. To be benefited from the sector, convenience store industries need to have a better marketing strategy. However, their marketing strategy and the influence of marketing strategy 7Ps on their profitability is not well studied and adequate information is not available, so that this study's goal is to determine how marketing mix strategies affect convenience store sectors' profitability. and will suggest the possible ways that will help the industries by being competitive and profitable. And due to the lack of a comprehensive model available therefore the proposed study will fill the gap study of how marketing strategy impacts the profitability of small convenience stores.

This study could potentially improve this ability by providing appropriate advice and training for convenience store retailers. This discovery may influence future strategic marketing decisions and, as a result, will impact the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

1.4. Research questions

This research aimed to investigate how strategies impacted the profitability of convenience stores in the UK. The explanation of how marketing strategy affects profitability contributes significantly to theory and management in this study. The results of this study offer an opportunity to enhance current business and marketing literature on convenience stores. As a result, it is anticipated that this study will provide fundamental scientific insights into:

1. What are the different marketing strategies at convenience stores that improve company profitability?
2. What are the challenges to implementing the marketing strategies at convenience stores?
3. What are the benefits of marketing strategy at convenience stores?
4. What is the relationship between marketing mix 7ps and profitability?
5. How does marketing strategy impact the profitability of convenience stores?

1.5 Aim and Objectives

Aim:

The main aim of this research is to investigate the relationship between marketing mix 7Ps strategies and convenience store profitability in the United Kingdom. Given the significance of the marketing mix 7Ps strategies and the evidence presented, it is therefore worthwhile to examine into the subject further to contribute new knowledge for existing research. This study makes an attempt:

1. To critically review the literature of marketing strategies and profitability for stores.
2. To examine existing practices of marketing strategies on profitability.
3. To examine challenges to implement the marketing strategies.
4. To examine the benefits of implementing the marketing strategies.
5. To analyse the relationship between constructs of marketing mix 7ps strategies that impact the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

This research's objective is to investigate the impact of marketing mix 7Ps strategies on the convenience store's profitability. It is intended that by attaining these goals, the research would contribute to existing knowledge about marketing strategy as well as provide practical insights to business owners and managers.

1.6 Rationale of the study

This study attempts to introduce additional research questions in an effort to acquire a deeper knowledge of the marketing strategies issue management. Moreover, this research makes important theoretical and managerial contributions through the finding of this study. The theoretical contribution provides an opportunity to improve current business and marketing literature.

Several studies have presented empirical evidence supporting the link between a company's profitability and its marketing strategy. Most of these research initiatives have focused on the marketing strategies' impacts on profit and business success (Mornay, 2009; Abedian et al. 2021). In addition, various studies by Bahador (2019), Karam et al. (2019), Mang'era et al. (2021), Ramadani, (2020) and Maerhaba et al. (2022) have claimed that the marketing strategy affects overall business performance. However, the findings of the studies mentioned above are not conclusive. In the United Kingdom context, Hassan (2012) studied the marketing strategies and tactics of supermarket whilst Sayyida (2021) studied the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on retail consumer behaviour and improving marketing strategies. However, neither study has made an effort to confirm the link between small businesses' profitability in the UK and their marketing strategies. This is the context in which the study was conducted.

Therefore, it is essential to conduct this research in order to fill the knowledge gap that has been identified, which will allow convenience stores to increase their profits and remain competitive in the market for the long term. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this is the first empirical study to explore the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

1.6.1 Contribution to Theoretical/Knowledge

The theoretical contributions of the current study to existing knowledge add new perspectives to the literature on marketing strategies. Furthermore, this study will provide additional understanding and theory extension through conceptualisation verification, empirical testing, theory testing, and generalisation measurement of research concept constructs from the perspective of entrepreneurs and managers.

This study examines the relationship between marketing strategies and profitability, thus adding significant value to the subject. The empirical findings presented here not only build on previous findings in marketing strategy-related research but also make a contribution to the field of company profitability research. It provides useful tools for understanding the role of marketing strategies in the retail industry. The findings could be used as a guide for marketers in their marketing strategy.

1.6.2 Contribution to Business Practice

For the industry contribution, this quantitative study may contribute to information on how convenience store business owners and managers can implement an effective business practise by exploring marketing mix strategies for profitability. The study's findings may aid business owners and managers in enhancing their business practises as well as in identifying and determining the factors that support innovative strategies to increase profits, sales growth, and market share. Proper implementation and efficiently executing marketing mix strategies for profitability is important from a business standpoint because it can assist convenience store business managers in accelerating growth, expanding their current market position, solidifying their brand position, and achieving marketing objectives. The responses obtained from the data collection instrument may enable business owners and managers to understand the needs of customers, analyse market conditions, and forecast marketing and brand strategies. Moreover, the result of this research will provide a comprehensive guideline for marketing strategies to gain profitability for convenience stores, which leads to success in the retail shop industry. The results of this study are significant because they show a clear understanding of the marketing mix strategy dimensions that lead to profits and give a general picture of the situation as a whole.

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge regarding the evolution of marketing strategies and their potential outcomes. The primary contribution of this research is to fill gaps in the existing literature. Therefore, the main research question was formulated based on the problem mentioned above.

The following list summarises the knowledge gaps in the field:

1. There is a scarcity of empirical study on how the company implements marketing strategies to increase convenience store profitability (Mornay, 2009, Abedian, et al. 2021).

2. There is little known about the relationship between convenience store marketing strategies, product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, advertisement, customer service, and profitability (Ramadani, 2020), Anjani et al. 2018, Komari et al. 2020, Jain 2013).
3. There is no systematic study in the marketing literature on the effect of:
Product differentiation and profitability; Promotion variation and profitability; Price variation and profitability; Place and profitability; People and profitability; Process and profitability; Physical Evidence and profitability (Mornay, 2009 and Abedian, et al. 2021).
4. There is a lack of studies explanatory models and theory-building in the area of marketing strategies, product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, advertisement, customer service, and profitability (Bahador, 2019, Karam et al. (2019), Mang'era et al. (2021), Ramadani, (2020) and Maerhaba, et al. (2022).
5. The convenience store in the United Kingdom has gone through rapid growth and change since the 1990s. The growth and change were particularly due to the competition among chain convenience stores. Despite the fact that convenience store retailers have experienced strong competition, the development of this industry seldom attracts the attention of academia in the UK, and the existing studies in the United Kingdom are obsolete and lack a theoretical explanation. As a result, this research would provide a comprehensive examination of the convenience store industry in the United Kingdom within the framework of the marketing mix (7p).

1.7 Methodology Overview

In this study, the deductive method was employed. Due to the fact that the research problem is based on previously published literature that is being applied to a specific situation, this method is particularly useful in this study. Moreover, an exploratory method was chosen for this investigation in order to understand and measure the

problem. In terms of data collection, the distribution of the questionnaire to the manager and owners of the convenience stores will help this study to gain information regarding the research. Primary data will be collected from questionnaire and personal observation. The questionnaire will be administered online using the website www.smartsurvey.co.uk and distributed to owners or managers of convenience stores in the United Kingdom by email. Secondary data is which has been found from the previous research literature.

A questionnaire would be given to 280 business managers and owners of convenience stores in four parts of the London area, such as the East, West, North, South, and outside London, to gain better results from the study. The research would be statistically analysed by using SPSS to examine the proposed conceptual model. This study used quantitative research to learn more about the reactions of managers and entrepreneurs to marketing strategies. A questionnaire with seven-point Likert scales ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (7) strongly agree was applied to obtain satisfactory properties related to the essential distribution of respondents (Bagozzi, 1994). Four major principles from the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee guidelines would be considered to ensure that this research meets the ethical practise of business research standards and has no ethical issues. Prior to the main investigation, a small sample study (10 surveys) of this pilot study was collected to prove the reliability of the methodology and collect data.

The descriptive statistics for the entire sample were computed using the SPSS statistical package for social science (SPSS) software. The analysis starts with demographic data analysis to understand and study respondents' responses to the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. Next is a reliability test to measure the reliability of the data. The analysis continues with data preparation, which includes editing and data coding, missing data analysis, and data screening. Following that, the Levene's and normality tests are performed. The paths between the constructs would be tested using correlation and regression analysis to assess the hypotheses study. Next is the measurement of validity. The result of the hypothesis test would be the final part.

1.8 Thesis Outline

The objectives of research were clarified and the scope of this study was outlined based on the existing limitations. There are five main chapters in this study.

Chapter 1: Provided a brief introduction to the project concept as well as an explanation of the current challenges addressed in this research.

Chapter 2: Discussed comprehensive background into the marketing strategies in different businesses and their impacts on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom were investigated.

Chapter 3: Described in detail the quantitative method that was used to test the proposed hypotheses and their causal relationships, as well as the scale validation.

Chapter 4: Discussed the findings and data analysis.

Chapter 5: Discussed the results and contributions.

Chapter 6: Discussed the conclusion, findings and limitations of the study, as well as the conclusions and recommendations for future research.

1.9 Summary

Chapter 1 established the context of the research by providing a background for the study as well as an understanding of the research problem area. This section explains why this research topic is important and necessary for understanding the study's main points. The background section of a research thesis justifies the need for the study and summarises what the study hopes to achieve. This chapter summarises the main developments in this research topic and identifies the main gaps that need to be addressed. This chapter also explains marketing strategies and how convenience store owners and managers can use them to improve their business performance and profitability. Then describes the problem statement, which provides an overview of the current issue discussed in the paper, as well as its background and its impacts on the convenience store industry. It also describes the goals for conducting this research. The problem statement reveals the gap that exists between the current situation and the desire to achieve the goal of this research, which aids in the discovery of a solution. Following that, this chapter go into detail about the five proposed research questions and five main objectives. The methodology is then explained which employs a

deductive and exploratory approach. This study employs a quantitative approach to investigate marketing mix strategies in the convenience store industry, as well as data analysis (SPSS). In the last part, this section discusses the thesis outline and overall structure of this dissertation.

The following chapter examined the literature regarding the relationship between 7Ps marketing mix strategies and the profitability of convenience stores.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Chapter overview

The purpose of this chapter is to conduct a review of relevant literature in relation to the relationship between 7Ps marketing mix strategies and the profitability of convenience stores in general. In this chapter theoretical literature review, empirical review and conceptual framework are included.

This chapter begins by describing the marketing strategy and marketing mix strategy in Sections 2.2 and 2.3, respectively. Section 2.4 then investigates the relationships between the 7Ps marketing mix strategy and profitability, which is the primary focus of this study. Then, in Section 2.5, the conceptual framework and research hypotheses are explained. The relationship between retail strategies and profitability is described in Section 2.6. Next, strategic planning in the retail industry is explained in Section 2.6.1. After that, the retail strategy based on the product-mission matrix is described in Section 2.6.2. It is followed by the retail strategy based on Porter's five forces model, which is explained in Section 2.6.3. Lastly, Section 2.6.4 describes the limitations of retail strategic planning models.

2.2 Strategy of Marketing

Marketing strategy is one of the most important parts of the business. Marketing strategy is the method of promoting the idea of a company's products and services, which includes meeting consumers' needs and demands in order to satisfy them (Ferrell et al., 2021). In addition, marketing strategy is concerned with matching external opportunities with corporate resources while maintaining acceptable profit and risk levels. This study aims to investigate the marketing strategies' effectiveness on convenience stores' performance that lead to profitability.

Traditionally marketing strategy is viewed as a firm's using its existing resources to respond to the environment. According to Knee and Walters (1985), strategy is the nature of a company's connection with its surroundings and specifies the types of business that the firm will engage in. Knee and Walters (1985) also stated that any company's overall strategy is made up of decisions on five elements: (1) product mix,

(2) customer mix, (3) competitive emphasis, (4) geographic limits of the market to be served and (5) objectives (performance criteria).

2.3 Marketing Mix Strategy

Marketing mix Strategy is a collection of business strategies that company use in their business operation to achieve their company objectives (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010). Advertising, delivery, and corporate image building are just a few of the new elements that other researchers have introduced to the marketing mix. Accordingly, Lovelock (2011) implemented seven elements of the marketing mix into advanced strategies. These elements are as follows: place, product, price, promotion, process, physical evidence and people. While developing a marketing mix strategy, decisions are made by considering the product, the location, the promotion and the price. This is the most significant parts because they necessarily require the optimum usage of all company resources throughout in order to boost profit and sales revenues (Garavand et al., 2010). Marketing managers are in charge of figuring out who their target market is and then coming up with a plan to sell their goods to consumers while also building good relationships with customers. The marketing mix outlines the key functions in which business owners should be involved. The managerial decision factors in a variety of marketing mix concepts act as guidelines and purpose for marketing-focused business plans (Pourdehghan 2015).

In addition, Borden invented in 1965, the marketing mix consisted of 12 elements: pricing, analysis and fact-finding, servicing, product, physical handling, planning display, packaging, promotions; distribution channels and branding, personal selling and advertising McCarthy (1964). Borden's (1965) developed further concept, specifying the marketing mix as a combined application of all the variables at a marketing owner's disposal that work together to reach its target market's needs. To satisfy the target market, he restructured Borden's 12 components into four components, known as the 4Ps, under the direction of a marketing manager. These four elements are: product, price, promotion, and place. Similarly to Lazer and Kelly (1973), recommended 3 aspects of marketing: the goods and mix services, the mix distribution, and the mix communication. To summarise Frey (1961), marketing variables can be divided into two categories: the proposing (i.e. the product and packaging, the brand, the price, and the service); and the methods and tools used to

deliver that offering (publicity, sales, promotion, advertising, personal, distribution channels and selling.

McCarthy (1964) was the first to offer the Marketing Mix (often known as the 4Ps; pricing, product, promotion, and place), a set of four elements that firms must manage in order to fulfil the wants and requirements of their target consumers. Vignalis and Davis (1994) proposed that the existing marketing mix be supplemented by one S (service). Magrath (1986) recommended introducing three more components: "process management, physical facilities, and personnel," and Goldsmith (1999) suggested contributing another 4 Ps (process, physical, evidence, participants, and personalization). Kotler (1986) suggested the addition of two more components (political power and public opinion). Since the 1960s, numerous variations on the 4Ps conception have been recommended. Judd (1987) suggested adding another one P for people. Many of academic and business attention has been implement the development and use of the marketing mix concept (Goi, 2009).

There have been a number of proposals, the most important and generally accepted of which is the 7Ps approach developed by Booms and Bitner (1981). (Rafiq & Ahmed, 1995). Even though services are formed and consumed at the same time, the quality, attitude, service efficiency provider, professionalism, and the existence of certain other consumers will have an influence on the amount of satisfaction with services (Booms & Bitner, 1981). According to Booms and Bitner (1981), individuals such as the service provider and other customers have an impact on the total service experience. In 1981, Booms and Bitner (1981) expanded the 4Ps to become the 7Ps by including three additional factors: people, process, and physical evidence. Those three new factors serve as a basis for the service marketing strategy that is currently in use.

The extended marketing mix (7P's) is a marketing strategy that combines seven elements. The aim is to develop as a potential solution to this research's objectives and achieve the goals of a marketing strategy. 7Ps are used in this study to evaluate higher education options. All components of the marketing mix must be integrated, interconnected, and interdependent with one another (Armstrong & Kotler, 2012). For the concept of the convenience store, the 7 P elements of items include: price (product

price), place (convenience store or grocery shop), promotion (weekly or monthly limited offer, use of the website and social media), people (owner, managers, sales assistant, suppliers), physical evidence (products, store layout, shelf, fridge, coffee machine, etc. in convenience store), and process (buying/ordering from suppliers or cash and carry wholesalers and selling directly to customers). The following section will focus on the argument of the benefits of retail marketing mix strategy

2.3.1 The benefits of a retail marketing mix strategy

Market research and development are important aspects of a company's marketing strategy because they help the organisation develop a marketing mix that will enable the organisation to attain their goals (Varadarajan & Clark, 1994). When a company uses an innovative or creative strategic plan, it differentiates itself from the competition and makes it difficult for them to copy (Barney, 1991; Porter, 1996). In marketing, creativity is defined as "the degree to which the actions taken to market a product differ significantly from marketing techniques in the market sector in which the product was originally introduced" (Andrews & Smith, 1996). Hamel (1998, p. 8) argued that "Strategy innovation is the only way for newcomers to succeed in enormous resource disadvantages and the only way for incumbents to renew their lease on success."

Those businesses that are the most creative and innovative have had a benefit opportunity that allows others to envision how a significant new value can also be used to generate a new challenging area or reorganise available space. The implementation of an innovative or creative strategy positions the firm in a unique way that is difficult for competitors to imitate and, as a result, may provide a competitive advantage to the firm (Barney, 1991). These elements of the marketing mix may provide unique customer value or provide buyers with a compelling reason to make a purchasing decision. Innovative marketing strategies that are based on consumer production systems, different price strategies, product offerings, or extending clever ways of reaching consumers and responding to their particular interests and preferences are examples of innovative marketing strategies.

Moreover, according to West et al. (2015), one of the benefits of marketing strategy creativity is to create a competitive advantage. A competitive advantage is a component that means being able to enhance business performance in a given market

segment or industry. The downside of developing a strong marketing strategy is that it is incredibly expensive, despite the fact that it attracts new customers (Money Matters, 2019). Competitive advantage can be gained through three strategies: cost leadership, differentiation, and concentration (Cost-focus, and Differentiation-focus). In order to gain a competitive advantage, an organisation needs to outline the advantages that they need to their target market in a way that other competitors are unable to do. Since convenience stores face fierce competition, a company's competitive advantages will allow it to achieve higher margins than its competitors and generate value for the company and its shareholders.

According to Christensen (2010), competitive advantage is defined as any benefit that a company provides that encourages its consumers (or end-users) to choose its goods or services over those of its competitors and that creates significant barriers to exact replica by current or future main rivals. This is supported by Porter (1985), that the company's ability to utilise core competencies in responding to external situational benefits while preventing existential threats and internal weaknesses is the source of its competitive advantage. It is one of a company's internal strengths to employ this marketing mix strategy. In the broadest sense, "competitive advantage" means that a company knows how to use its valuable resources to make high-quality products and services. The retail industry needs a theory closer to real retail market situations and able to model the influence of retail competition on the industry and on the environment within which they compete. The following section will focus on the discussion of marketing mix.

2.3.2 The importance of Marketing Mix in the retail industry

The environment in which a convenience store company must evolve in the twenty-first century is not the same as it was decades ago. Indeed, maintaining a convenience store firm's visibility and keeping its customers was easier in the past than it is today. This phenomenon, which may be caused by the growing number of new convenience store businesses, has been impacted by globalisation (Tien et al. 2019). That is one of the main reasons why marketing strategies are so essential for the expansion of a convenience store company's profitability, because without them, and thus without recognition, firms will struggle to grow in a competitive market. From that point forward, convenience store companies had to deal with internal competition within their country

from that point forward, which was especially true in the convenience store industry. In theory, in this specific context, where competition is becoming more fierce and intense, companies must struggle and innovate in order to have the greatest influence and notoriety and thus gain market share over their competitors. Because of the increased availability of products, convenience store companies must alter their approach to the market. Any major blunders in a company's strategy can lead to failure. Even if well-implemented, companies must constantly compete for ingenuity, particularly when it comes to marketing mix strategy implementation, in order to secure positions. This marketing mix strategy is especially important in convenience stores in order to compete with many enterprises and large companies such as Tesco, Asda, Morrison's, and others in order to survive and gain profitability.

Chouliaras et al. (2015) also investigate the relationship between operating expenses, total revenue, and net income, as well as the changeability as a result of the crisis. Even though these variables are different, the results of this research show that marketing is the most important factor in determining how profitable a business is. In this paper's findings, it is revealed that companies have failed to adapt their marketing strategies in order to respond to the wide range of changes in consumer behaviour that have resulted from the economic crisis. In addition, the implementation of a marketing mix strategy is critical for achieving long-term sustainability and profitability for businesses. Therefore, convenience store companies need to change their marketing mix strategies to adapt the business situation.

As stated by Thomson (2008), a marketing mix strategy is focused on the precise details of a company's strategy for gaining a competitive edge and achieving competitiveness. The pursuit of competitive advantage can take a variety of forms, but they all revolve around producing better with what they perceive to be the best option, which is a compelling combination of quality, features, pricing, and services. A good product at a low price with additional appealing characteristics is worth paying a little more for.

This research's purpose is to study the influence of every strategy marketing mix (7P) component on convenience stores' profitability in the United Kingdom, specifically. Consequently, it would be clear which components of the marketing mix have an

important impact on profit margins in the future. In spite of the fact that all 7 the marketing mix (7P components) are equally important and interdependent on one another, each of the components has a distinct effect on competitive advantage. How much the other element of the marketing mix contributes to overall profitability is the question under investigation.

Because there are so many operators in this business, competition for convenience store services in the United Kingdom is fierce. They must compete aggressively to obtain and retain customers. To achieve profitability, companies must provide the best marketing mix strategy. The preceding description and literature review demonstrate a strong connection between company's profitability and marketing mix strategies. How it happens in the retail business are some of the topics explored in this study.

The following topic will discuss more about constructs of marketing strategy which are product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, process and physical evidence.

2.4 The relationships between the marketing mix variables and profitability

This section examined the relationship between the marketing mix strategies 7Ps (Product differentiation, Promotion variation, Price variation, Place, People, Process, Physical Evidence) and Profitability.

2.4.1 Product differentiation → Profitability

2.4.1.1 Product

The first component of the marketing mix strategy 7Ps is product. A product is defined as a physical product or service that is offered in the business market to fulfil consumer demand (Thabit and Raewf, 2018). Dang (2015) states that the product is the primary focus and the most essential component of marketing. The product is what could be provided to the convenience store's business, to get exposure, to be the purchase of used or used goods, and can fulfil the needs or wants of the customer. It includes half of the material goods, such as furniture, clothing, and grocery items, and intangible products, such as goods and services (Singh, 2016). In point of fact, it was discovered that the majority of instances involve the literature being influenced by a limited

"product" opinion or understanding. Consequently, in obtaining a deeper understanding of the character of the product, refer to Figure 1, which demonstrates a more broad view.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Strazdas, 2011. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 1: Product wider perception (Strazdas ,2011)

As a result, the definition of a product is broad, as it not only refers to tangible goods and services but also to ideas, information, corporations or organisations' property rights, locations, people, and experiences. Nevertheless, in an attempt to more broadly raise consumers' awareness of the product, Thrush (2011) suggests evaluating the following 3 perspectives: Firstly, the customer-satisfaction approach; secondly, the importance of materiality; and thirdly, the perspective outcome and process.

Therefore, the actual advantages, which are the primary reasons a customer purchases a goods and services, are those that illustrate the fundamental advantages that convenience stores offer to the customer. The primary product: This refers to the basic minimal criteria that the product would satisfy in order for the user to get any noticeable benefits. (Thrush, 2011). The respective product characteristics, which the user anticipates gaining from using the product, are included in the product that the user expects to receive; this fulfils the expectations of the consumer (Thrush, 2011). When a product not only meets but also exceeds the expectations of the average user, it is considered supplemented and can be improved upon by adding new properties or enhancing those that already exist (Thrush, 2011). It is dependent on a wide range of

aspects, such as the marketing approach that was chosen, the characteristics of similar products offered by competitors, the practicability of the product from a technical standpoint, the quantity of recourses, and so on. The product may include characteristics that surprise the buyer in some way, and its potential might exceed both the simplest and the greatest expectations of a modern user (Thrush, 2011).

According to Uznien (2011), the products are also classified as general consumption (milk, bread, papers, apparel, everyday usages, etc.). They buy items for their own use, and despite this, the items that they purchase are still categorised as essential, beneficial, unique, and unsellable. Secondly, a valuable product: a product that the buyer contrasts with others, taking into account fit, value, design, and price. Thirdly, a product that the client considers to be necessary and important; something they consistently and almost immediately buy without thinking to compare it to other items of a similar nature. Last but not least, an exclusive product is a consumer commodity that is renowned for its unique qualities or distinguished by its trademark and is bought by a large number of individuals (Uznien 2011).

In the meantime, the range of products is comprised of all of the different types of goods, different classes, brand names, and unit measurements that the convenience stores offer to the customer (Thrush, 2011). The range is the group of products or the entirety of the company's offerings that are made available to customers. These products are comparable to one another not only in terms of their features but also because they are categorised by certain features and are centred on the requirements of the end users (Thrush, 2011). There are other methods to describe the range, including by the depth. (also called the deep variety), (also called the width), alignment, and saturation (Thrush, 2011).

To summarise, the concept of a product in convenience stores is extremely all-encompassing as it includes not only tangible goods and services but also individuals and locations, land ownership, commercial enterprises or charitable groups, resources, and suggestions. When evaluating perception via the lens of user needs, the three main benefits of the given product, the creation and addition process, and the product's capability are the five levels of the product that are taken into account. Additionally, the items are divided into categories based on the consumable things, which are still divided into minimal, unmarketable, exclusive and valuable categories.

2.4.1.2 Product differentiation

This thesis would apply product differentiation as the first element in the marketing mix. Product differentiation is a strategic effort to build different products in such a way that the differences provide a competitive advantage. Furthermore, product differentiation is the process of modifying a product to make it more appealing to the target market. This includes distinguishing it from competitors' products as well as the firm's product mix (Van Alstyne et al. 2016). The changes are typically minor; they can range from a simple change in packaging to a shift in advertising theme. In terms of convenience store marketing strategy, product differentiation is required to provide customers with more options for similar products from different brands.

According to Davcik et al. (2015), the goal of a product differentiation strategy is to develop a situation that will be perceived by prospective consumers as being unique. When any product is seen as unique in comparison to those offered by competitors in the target market, the company will have more leeway when working to develop its marketing plan. If you have a successful product differentiation strategy, you will be able to shift the product's focus from competing primarily on price to competing on factors other than price, for example, product features, distribution channels, or advertising variable differences.

In addition, Nam (2001) defines the concept of product differentiation by stating that it is a strategy that encourages and enables consumers to choose one product or brand over another in a competitive marketplace. It does this by determining the qualities that set one product apart from others that are in a similar category and then using those distinctions to influence the choice that customers make. Each company has a different way of differentiating its products based on its sales goal.

There are three distinct ways to differentiate one product from another: vertically, horizontally, and through a combination of the two (Nam 2001). When two products are very similar but are priced differently from one another, this is an example of vertical integration. On the other hand, if the price increases of both goods were the same, one would be regarded as "the best" due to the obvious quality that people associate with it; for example, a premium chocolate from Godiva as opposed to a

chocolate from Cadbury. The quality of a product or its price point have no bearing on whether or not horizontal differentiation takes place. The consumer chooses a product or brand according to his or her own preferences, e.g., Pepsi or Coca-Cola, for instance. Because it involves factors of all of these vertical and horizontal differentiations, mixed differentiation is a complicated form of differentiation. For instance, a customer may decide to purchase a new automobile from the same class of automobiles by taking into account not only the price ranges offered by the various brands (a form of vertical differentiation) but also the hues of the interior (a form of horizontal differentiation) (Ferreira and Thisse 1996).

According to Wang (2021), who studies performance evaluation of retail enterprises, product differentiation appears to boost competitiveness and profitability. He discovered that as product differentiation increases, so does intra-industry trade share. Product differentiation is important not only in trade and economic terms, but it also plays an important role in convenience stores' and industrial sales performance and profitability (Wang, 2021). It is perhaps natural that many companies, both past and present, have emphasised the critical role that product differentiation plays in improving the effectiveness of products and services.

Nowadays, as a result of the increased level of competition in the market, a significant number of companies are focusing their efforts on trying to distinguish their offerings as a tactic to optimise company profitability. Businesses have created product differentiation methods to increase revenue growth by continuing to attract new customers and retain existing ones. According to the results of the research (King'oo, 2015) who studied the effect of differentiation strategy on market share, both product differentiation and physical differentiation contribute significantly to stimulating yearly basis company profitability at superstores.

Moreover, according to Waterson (1990), who studied product differentiation and profitability, product differentiation significantly enhances a company's profitability. Businesses are typically interested in selling differentiated products at a premium because customers are willing to pay more for longer product life, improved aesthetics, and better support. Consumers were willing to pay a higher price for products that came in attractive boxes or that offered amazing events (Waterson 1990).

Product differentiation is essential to a company's profitability because it enables retailers to make a comparison of their own products with those of their competition in the industry and to highlight the distinctive qualities that set their products apart from those of their rivals. When vendors are able to convincingly demonstrate why their wares are distinctive from those of other vendors, they achieve a significant competitive advantage. Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed based on the preceding discussion:

H1: The product differentiation will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.2 Promotion variation→Profitability

When developing a promotion strategy, promotion is considered one of the seven components that comprise the 7P marketing mix (Kotler 2015). These components include things like direct marketing, advertisements, promoting sales and media exposure, to name a few examples. The most basic aim of sales promotions is an increase in revenue (Kotler 2015). Many times, sales promotions will restrict a company's ability to make a profit, but they will allow the company to bring in more revenue in the short term due to an increase in the volume of sales. Convenience stores need more consumers to shop for more products at a lower cost in order to increase their revenue.

Consumer awareness of a company's products can be raised through promotional variation, which ultimately results in higher sales and strengthens customer retention (Elgarhy and Mohamed 2022). As a result, the promotion component of the marketing mix is a tool that facilitates the release of knowledge, motivates buying, and plays a role in the process of deciding which sales to make. Endorsement is perhaps the most essential tool for consumer sales promotion that also involves deals and coupons, and also vouchers, samples, discounts, incentives, prizes, contests, and demos, and that is what encourages shoppers to purchase (Elgarhy and Mohamed 2022).

According to Kotler (2015), sponsorship is an event that educates and manages to convince potential consumers about the benefits of a good or service. Sponsorship or endorsement is a marketing mix component that involves behaviour and choices taken

for groups of individuals who are educated and motivated to make a purchase (Kotler 2015). To fully comprehend what promotion is, however, business owners or managers of convenience stores must take into account the complicated systems supplied in past studies, such as ads, product promotion, direct marketing, and media affairs (Kotler 2015).

Advertising is perhaps the most popular method of marketing, and it remains generally the subject of practical socioeconomic study. It starts with the marketing photo as well as a concentration on straightforward, captivating, or interesting and yet realistic information from groups to the viewer (Iorait 2016). Advertising is defined as "any form of information and the promotion of a set of ideas that helps to inform customers about new products and helps to reduce barriers between customers and organisations" (Iorait 2016).

Advertisement The word "banner" comes from the French word "reclams," which comes from the Latin term "reclama," which means "screaming." The word "banner" can be used to refer to either of the following: Firstly, that is the exposure of product details (books, sanatoriums, excursions, etc.). Secondly, this is an advertisement, signage, showcase, or text that is telecasted on broadcast, TV, or another form of media (Usman 2019). The actions and choices that are attributed to sales promotion are those that provide shortened time initiatives to boost the buying, utilise, and also enable the purchasing. These sales promotion actions and decisions could be aimed directly at the end user or through an intermediary. The purpose of this promotional tool is to convince a customer or purchaser to make additional purchases more quickly. Inducements can take a variety of forms, including vouchers, prize money, freebies, discounted rates, marketing materials, and other types of rewards (Usman 2019).

According to Usman (2019), in spite of the efforts that have been made to encourage innovation, they can be broken down into the following categories: The cooperation of competitions between buyers and sellers, including the presentation of rewards for the winners, such as merchandise display, Offering free tasters, Vouchers that guarantee a fee reduction when merchandise is purchased, additional items for additional purchases from the same company and wholesaler discounts.

Furthermore, in-store sales incentives can be divided into the following categories: image-based (score boards in the store or screens are used not only as a promotion show for products but also for draws, games, the location, and also layouts of products, box lotteries, and the like.) Games and cash prizes; vouchers, which aim to attract purchasers through positive feelings; product presentations and demonstrations, which are a new trend of products inside the retail shop and allow customers to not only explore but also review the goods; these are some examples of in-store marketing strategies (Mulhern et al., 1990). Consumers are interested in promotions such as discounts and rebates, which are the marketing platforms that have the widest acceptance overall. In the meantime, strategic marketing measures that take place outside of the store include the distribution of coupons (in letterboxes, magazines, newspapers and on the streets), as well as loyalty programmes (purchasers' activities, consumer certificates, purchasers' clubs, expeditions, and so on) (Mulhern et al., 1990).

A personal conversation between two parties that ends with one of them making an offer to the other to buy a product or service is an example of a private sale. This type of sponsorship is the most costly because it involves interaction with a single individual rather than a large group of people. However, it typically has a decisive impact on the choice that the potential purchaser makes. The buyer and the seller negotiate the terms of a private sale directly with one another. According to Olson et al. (2001), the following are the most important personal sales targets: To notify prospective purchasers about the resource; develop and sustain customer relationships; to pique buyers' interest in persuading the buyer to purchase the suggested merchandise and facilities; the requirement to reveal the unseen; assist consumers in problem resolution; make the sale; and increase profit.

The four types of sales that comprise missionary sales (opinion leaders, sponsors) are retail sales (consumers at the end of the distribution chain), business-to-business transactions (operations and production), and professional marketing. Relations with the public: The communication that takes place between a company and the managerial staff of a society to have an effect on behaviour is known as public relations. Unpleasant rumours, gossip, and incidents can harm a company's corporate

reputation image; however, public relations (PR) can help ensure adequate communication with customers and classroom points of contact. According to Olson et al. (2001), the company must accomplish the following primary goals in order to successfully complete the sales process: establishing and maintaining collaboration and understanding with the public in order to build stronger credibility and acceptance of the organisation. increase public interest while taking into account public interests and needs; increase public interest in the organization; achieve public understanding of and approval for the organization's activities Organizations that have expressed interest in the delivery and modification of services, the role and importance of public opinion, negotiations and methods of conflict resolution, concord, creation, and cohesion (Olson et al., 2001).

In addition, conventions, expos, and fairs. A fair is an event that takes place on a daily basis in certain locations (Olson et al., 2001). At this event, respondents from various corporate aspects of the firm offer prospective customers their goods or services. An exhibition is a type of event that has the purpose of acquainting business professionals and the general public with their recent accomplishments and innovative ideas (Olson et al., 2001).

Furthermore, "word of mouth" advertising is when knowledge regarding the business is passed through the consumers, and so forth, without the need for newspapers or any other communication channels that are accessible from the outside (Ferrell et al., 2021). Moreover, event marketing is when a product, service, or company is presented in an impressive manner at a particular event or corporate promotion with the intention of generating sales. Also, indirect demonstration is the "unintentional" promotion of a company's products or services by means such as watching movies, going to the theatre, or broadcasting on television (Ferrell et al., 2021).

Besides, direct marketing encourages two-way communication between the consumer and the company offering the product (Ferrell et al., 2021). Direct marketing has many features, some of which are direct communication, interactive elements, conventional direct marketing, and media exposure. Therefore, a scenario, the customer's response to the purchasing happened shortly (as though they were actually purchasing), whereas in another scenario, the user must first register, the product must be tested,

questions must be inquired, and effective communication must be finished before the user can acquire goods or services (Ferrell et al., 2021). The authors differentiate between three main types of sales promotion retailing done directly to consumers: postal address, catalogues and brochures, as well as online business marketing (Ferrell et al., 2021).

Understanding the marketing plan, that is created by choosing a range of various methods of supporting, is therefore an essential additional part of a consideration of the elements of the promotion in convenience stores (Ferrell et al., 2021). In addition, the quick-skimming strategy presents a higher price and higher operational cost, and the company's goal is to sell each item to achieve higher profitability. Furthermore, the slow-skimming approach provides low support expenses and high pricing. It works well when the target market knows a lot about the product and doesn't care about how much it costs (Ferrell et al., 2021). Moreover, the rapid approach has the lowest resource costs and the highest operational costs, but it works best when customers are uninformed about the product, price sensitivity exists, and there is a lot of competition in a relatively large market. Besides, a slow approach has a low initial cost as well as a low ongoing support cost. When the company is large and has a dominant share of the available market, this method is used to target users who are interested in the product but do not want to pay a high price for it (Ferrell et al., 2021).

According to Adefulu's (2015) study, who studied promotional strategy impacts on organisational market share and profitability, promotional variation strategy increased market share and profitability. Furthermore, promotional strategies as measured by advertising, publicity, and sales promotion had varying percentage effects on market share and profitability. In addition, the use of appropriate packaging is an essential component of various promotional methods. Packaging is often referred to as the "least expensive form of advertising," and its importance at the point of sale cannot be overstated because it is the manufacturer's final opportunity to persuade the customer to purchase the product in question (Ziliani and Ieva, 2015). When trying to entice new customers to try a product, the packaging is of the utmost importance. Customers have a good visual identifier in the form of the package. According to Ziliani and Ieva (2015), customers have come to expect that the goods and services they purchase will be packaged and presented in a manner that is convenient for them. This expectation is

essential for the success of the convenience store business. Before-sale marketing that features appealing packaging is a helpful sales tool. Having said that, once a product has been purchased, the packaging transforms into an element of the service. The consumer is looking for packaging that is simple to take off and move around. An advertisement is the promotion of a product, service, company, or idea by a specific sponsor in exchange for financial compensation (Sallam and Algamash, 2016). Thus, convenience store owners use advertising as a key component of their overall marketing strategy.

Moreover, as suggested by Loda (2014), The advantages of a product can be communicated to a prospective buyer by a convenience store company through the medium of advertising. Advertisements may be published in newspapers or magazines, broadcast on radio or television, displayed on billboards or online, or distributed using any number of other communication channels. Advertising, on the other hand, is usually a paid service, while publicity is usually given for free (Loda 2014).

Promoting means making sure that the product is right for the different types of customers that are part of the marketing mix. For effective communication with the consumer about the product or service, it is important to make sure the consumer base knows about the parts of the marketing mix. Personal selling, selling to a large number of people, and sales promotions are all important parts of marketing.

In recent years, a significant amount of money has been spent on sales promotion by a number of businesses, and we are curious as to whether or not businesses that implement such a strategy see a positive return on their investment. It was curious as to whether or not the rise in sales promotion variation expenses was accompanied by a rise in organisations' overall sales and profitability. According to the findings of Aghara et al. (2018), company used variety of sales promotion as the approach became so effective at building and maintaining retain its customers, which led in profitability (Aghara et al., 2018). In other words, the strategy was implemented because it increased sales and income. The expenses of marketing variation and volume of sales were also shown to be strongly positively correlated, as well as between the expenses of sales promotion and profit (Aghara et al., 2018). As a result,

it was suggested that businesses employ promotional strategies as a method for increasing profits, sales and revenues. However, it was stipulated that such organisations must maximise the marketing promotion programme in order to achieve the desired results.

Furthermore, Aghara et al. (2018) carried out research on four distinct product categories to define the short-term and long-term impacts of sales promotions on profitability. According to the findings of their study, sales promotions do not typically have an effect that is felt in the volume of sales and profitability spanning a considerable amount of time. Therefore as result, the study's findings suggest that over time, sales promotions have little impact on the way sales are structured.

However, the long term profitability of sales promotions is heavily dependent on cost parameters and the size of the response. In addition, since brand image eventually enhances consumer loyalty, it have made brand loyalty the standard for long term benefit, a key measurement of future profitability (Aghara et al., 2018). Aghara et al. (2018) discovered that the rapidly decreasing impact of sales promotions can also be contributed to brand selection, total amount purchased, and categorization incidence. This was discovered in their research. The investigation of extraneous factors allows for the consideration of this facet as well, which is one of the goals of our study.

Finally, Anthonia (2019), who studied how promotions affect an organization's profitability, asserts that analysis of data from the business's performance accounts shows that elements like sales revenue, as well as cost of promotions, have a slight impact on profit, whereas hypothesis testing revealed that sales promotions have a positive effect on profitability. Every result mainly focused on the necessity for a business to properly coordinate its sales promotion plan through an advertisements and promotion about their brand and products. As per the study, promotion is an important tool for companies looking to increase their profits. Anthonia (2019) suggested that organisations increasingly incorporate effective promotion into their strategy to increase profitability and competitive advantage.

In summary, promotion increases both the awareness and the loyalty of customers to brands. As a result, promotion is one of the marketing mix component that makes it

useful, contributes to the dissemination of information, inspires purchases, and has a positive impact on sales and profitability for Convenience Stores Company. Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed based on the preceding discussion:

H2: The Promotion variation will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.3 Price variation→Profitability

2.4.3.1 Price

Price is one of the most important components of an effective marketing strategy and is also viewed by a large number of studies as one of the important elements of a successful market (Greenleaf 1995). Thus, price affects both profitability and sales expansion, on the other hand, price is not just one of the most crucial competitive aspects, impacting the firm's revenue and profitability predictions, but it is among the marketing mix's most flexible components, able to do so immediately in response to market environment (Grewal and Marmorstein 1994). In other words, in a competitive environment, pricing is one of the most important factors. As a result of this, price is the single component of the marketing strategy that directly affects profit, price is also the element that has the biggest impact on how satisfied and loyal customers are. There are many various valuations of conceptualization and interpretation in connection to pricing in the research journals. This is due to the fact that one component of the marketing mix is pricing. (Grewal and Marmorstein 1994).

According to Kohli and Suri (2011), the price reflects a rational assessment of the service or product; for instance, a good product for a reasonable price. "The price is defined as the amount of money to pay for a product or service, or the value of the exchange that allows customers to receive a product or service for a specific amount of money," (Kotler and Armstrong 2010). Therefore, the direct cost of the time period is the total amount that the consumer needs spend on the service or product in order to complete the transaction. Another way to think of the price is as a monetary statement of value that the customer agrees to pay. The price of the product is determined by the numerous parts of change that are involved in the transaction since the price is the total that the customer should pay, which would require transactions.

(Kotler and Armstrong 2010). The only aspect of the marketing strategy that is connected to income and all of the other aspects is the price. As a consequence of this, Given that it helps them understand the worth of the goods, pricing is one of the aspects that affect how customers make purchasing decisions. Price can also be understood to mean something that is real or valuable, which confers value and enables companies to identify their goods or services for the purpose of marketability regulation (Tanaka 2001). This enables company to differentiate their products offer from those of their opponents. According to Yuliantine et al. (2018), the product cost, advertising and promotion cost, distribution costs, or variations in price due to market conditions are all important factors of pricing in marketing strategy.

Price and sales are indeed closely correlated because retail prices are determined by the volume of production that is marketed (Mulhern et al., 1991). This suggests that fewer units will be sold as the price increases. As a consequence of this, determining the price of a product can be challenging, and as a result, the following strategies can be utilised: Cost-plus-is pricing is backed up by a basic percentage of profits that is applied to the potential costs of producing the goods, such as an assessment of variable and fixed costs. Next, value basis some are based on the consumer's assessment of the product's quality (rather than cost). In this scenario, the perception of the product held by the purchaser is affected by all attributes of the design, including the price, as well as variables such as image quality and reputation. The price of similar products offered by other businesses determines competition (Mulhern et al., 1991).

In addition, prices charged by the company are compared with those charged by its competitors, which enables the company to directly monitor the price responses of their competitors to changes in the market (Greenleaf 1995). Because if companies choose not to, consumers might select other companies depending on the alternatives that are offered (Greenleaf 1995). When entering a market, it is customary to agree upon a common selling price for the product. To maintain their market position, the majority of businesses must reduce their expenditures or refrain from raising their prices (Greenleaf 1995).Advertising-based discounts help to lower prices, which helps to increase the number of customers and maximize profits. Moreover, a non-profitable guide since it is built on the concept that the sale occurs at a lower price than the cost of manufacturing in order to persuade consumers' attention hence that they can

purchase additional products (Greenleaf 1995). In addition, from a psychological point of view, a price that appears to be lower than it actually is, such as \$1.99 instead of \$2.00, can influence customer behaviour (Greenleaf 1995).

In conclusion, the pricing of the goods is another factor in influencing the customer since it helps the consumer evaluate the cost of the products being purchased. (Grewal and Marmorstein 1994). As a result, the following should be reflected in the cost in terms of monetary value so that customers can receive value from the product: The only aspect of marketing that has any bearing on revenue is price; the rest of the aspects are all connected to expenses in some way. Since its level is established by the quantity that is sold, there must be an inverse connection between the parties: when prices increase, sales decrease. The next topic discusses price variation.

2.4.3.2 Price variation

The firm's pricing position could indeed vary from consistent pricing (sustained, every day prices with fewer pricing promotions) to high price promotions, which is represented by the price variation policy (frequent price discounts) (Peng and Kaza 2019). Price variation and price promotion are a set of promotional and pricing decisions intended to engage a pricing direction with customers and have an impact on both ongoing sales response and companies' profit (Peng and Kaza 2019). A successful pricing strategy is necessary for the operation of a convenience store. A convenience store business can determine the appropriate price to set for a product to preserve and rise a stable profitability while also preserving its position as a competitive market player using this method. A convenience store company has access to a variety of different pricing strategies, and the one it decides to implement is contingent on the results of a number of different considerations.

According to Nagle and Müller (2017), who studied the strategy and tactics of pricing, a business can maximise its profitability by determining an appropriate price for each of its products. The cost of the good or service is among the most important aspects to take into account when creating marketing strategy. When it comes to the business of convenience stores, the price of a product is one of the first things that a customer notices about that product, and it is among the factors that influence their choice regarding whether or not to purchase that product. A pricing policy that is favourable

to customers will lead to an increase in returning customers and, eventually, profitability (Nagle and Müller, 2017).

According to Savan (2018), who studied analysis of companies' strategic pricing for small-medium businesses, companies employ the variation of prices to accurately price their goods and services in accordance with the demand that exists in the market at the present time. The finding showed that it is useful in determining the optimal price for the product, which can vary depending on the positioning that an organisation targets to increase sales and profitability (Savan 2018). Convenience store owners and managers need consider a variety of factors when determining the price. This aspects include the core business objectives, target consumers, and strategic and financial brand and product marketing objectives (Savan 2018). Even before determining their pricing strategy, convenience store managers ought to take into consideration a variety of other factors. Some examples are direct costs (which would be extra costs incurred in the manufacturing of your goods or services) and indirect costs (costs not directly associated with producing the products or services). Other examples include the activity of competitors, the position of the market, and the dynamics of (for example, depreciation, insurance, and general operating expenses).

In addition, the pricing strategy is an important element of the overall marketing strategies. It's possibly the most attainable lever for managing profitability, and it does not require significant investments or resources to be implemented (Kohli and Suri, 2011). According to Kohli and Suri (2011), who studied guidelines for pricing to enhance profitability, even relatively minor adjustments to price could have a sizeable effect on companies' profitability. As a consequence of this, failing to engage in careful price planning results in a lost opportunity. When it comes to making acquisition choices, customers place varying degrees of importance on price, depending on their individual preferences, motivations, and propensity to spend money. Setting prices is a mathematical and behavioural economics-based creative exercise, and companies should do so with an eye toward maximising profits (Kohli and Suri, 2011).

In addition, according to Benoit et al. (2020), who studied intuitive pricing by independent store managers, the following types of sales promotions include free offers and discounted prices, gift certificates and samples, to different types of

rewards. Moreover, these are all utilised by convenience store businesses as a means of boosting profits by incentivizing consumers to make an initial purchase (Benoit et al., 2020). One sub-category of sales promotions is known as a group promotion. One example of a convenience store organisation promotion would be offering a price reduction for a set period of time on the purchase of two distinct but complementary products (like toothpaste and soap, for instance).

According to the findings of an additional study that was carried out by De Toni et al. (2017), who studied price strategy and its effect on company profit, high price and value-based price strategies have a significant influence on businesses' profitability that were studied, while low pricing has a disadvantageous effect on profitability. According to these results, product prices has an impact on an organization's profitability (De Toni et al., 2017).

Moreover, according to Jindal et al. (2020), who studied marketing-mix response across retail formats, one of the most crucial business decisions is determining prices because doing so could have a significant effect on the profitability of a company, return on investment, and level of business competitiveness. The mission of creating and specifying costs is thus complicated and difficult since the management teams responsible for this process should comprehend how to create purchase intentions and what their consumers know about the charges, how to determine the essential and appropriate fees to satisfy this requirement; in addition to keeping in mind the budgeting of the company's objectives and their market position in the industry (Jindal et al., 2020). Because of this, coming up with and setting prices is hard and complicated (Jindal et al., 2020). In addition, according to De Toni et al. (2017), businesses that do not organise their prices risk losing control over those prices, which can have a negative impact on both their cost efficiency and profitability. Consumers were willing to buy at the price offered, which is defined not only by the perceived product value but also by the different price levels of the main competitors' offers.

As a consequence of this, purchasers may feel compelled to acquire additional knowledge, thereby enhancing their position in the negotiation process and thereby increasing their ability to obtain cost reductions and discounts. According to Nagle and Müller (2017), who studied the strategy and tactics of pricing, the primary difference

between conventional pricing and strategic pricing is that the latter is determined by either reactively or pro-actively responding to changes in market conditions. This is done with the intention of achieving the most profitable pricing possible through the generation of additional value for the company's clientele (Nagle and Müller, 2017). Conventional pricing, on the other hand, is determined solely by internal considerations (Nagle and Müller, 2017). There isn't just one way to define prices, which makes perfect sense. Because it will be much easier for the convenience store company to set prices after making these decisions, the convenience store company needs to decide on the product's strategy and proposed goals before setting the price of the product.

According to Goić et al. (2021), who studied drivers of customer satisfaction in the grocery business, price shifts has a significant effect on the of businesses' profitability besides pricing strategies are highly variable depending on the industry as well as the specific conditions of the market. However, most researchers agree that pricing strategies can be broken down into one of three primary buckets: pricing that is created on the value that the customer places on the product, pricing that is created on competition and cost-based pricing (Goić et al., 2021).

Moreover, according to Bolton and Shankar (2018), who studied emerging retailer pricing trends and practices, a pricing practise known "Perceived value-based pricing" is one in which price decisions are made by convenience store managers based on the perceived benefits of the item being provided to consumers, in addition to the way all such benefits are also viewed and measured by consumers. As a consequence, "value-based pricing" comes from a collection of basic ideas and business approaches that a convenience store chain may employ to boost profit (Bolton and Shankar, 2018).

In addition, according to the findings of Cleary et al. (2018), who studied store profitability and public policies, view value-based pricing, as well as retail pricing practises that describe applying knowledge regarding the pricing and costs of competitors, inseparably linked to business success of both the product and the service, as well as increasing sales and profitability. These journalists confirmed about using "value-based pricing" is an important pricing strategy for maximising profits and creating a competitive edge for businesses (Cleary et al., 2018). Furthermore, this was

proved in a study that was carried out by Hameli (2018), who carried out a literature review of the retailing sector and business retailing. The companies in this study used the perceived variation pricing strategy more frequently than the other companies. These authors found that the companies that utilised this strategy had contribution margins that ranged from 11 to 30 % profitability, whereas the companies that did not utilise this strategy had contribution margins that ranged from 0 to 10 % profitability.

As a result of this, the approach of a variation pricing strategy is considered to be superior to other approaches when measured against the results obtained by other businesses to increase profitability Nagle and Müller (2017); Savan (2018); Kohli and Suri (2011); Benoit et al. (2020); De Toni et al. (2017); Jindal et al. (2020); Nagle and Müller (2017); Goić et al. (2021); Bolton and Shankar (2018); Cleary et al. (2018); Hameli (2018). Therefore, based on the above discussion we propose the following research hypothesis:

H4: The Price variation will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.4 Place→Profitability

Place, which is another name for distribution, is another very important aspect of marketing. The process and means whereby the commodities or goods are provided to consumers are referred to as distribution (HR and Aithal, 2020). Place or also known as distribution is a component of the marketing mix strategy that relates to the locations and methods that businesses employ to provide their products widely available for the consumers they are trying to attract as customers. Research indicates that customers of convenience stores place a moderate to high value on the convenience of the store's location (Hanaysha et al., 2021). Outside of the main parts of cities, consumers will normally find convenience stores. Convenience stores are typically located in residential areas that are convenient to access. This is because convenience stores are all about making things easier for their customers (Hanaysha et al., 2021).

According to Bahador (2019), "distribution companies' products in the dissemination of measures to ensure their identification and implementation." "Distribution" is the process of assisting customers and users in locating and keeping products that they have purchased from certain manufacturers or providers when they are required

(Bahador 2019). The "distribution" component of the marketing mix refers to the decisions and activities involved in getting products from the manufacturer to the end user (Bahador 2019).

As a consequence of this, distribution can develop into a complicated system that performs admirably in a particular setting in time. These shows that all parties involved, including manufacturers, traders, individual trade, and consumer interests, collaborate in the same setting and at the same time. Hanaysha (2020) stated that the function of marketing distribution can be split into two parts: Firstly, distribution is viewed as a marketing channel, with the goal of not only making the service more accessible but also making it more easily accessible to a wider audience. Secondly, physical distribution, which is influenced by environmental factors, operational feasibility, shipping, and other factors based on the nature of the service, can also be influenced by other factors (Hanaysha 2020).

The term "distribution channel" refers to an essential component of the service that typically includes the supplier, intermediaries (also known as agents), and the end user of the service, all working together (in most cases). Therefore, in order for convenience store businesses to exercise control and management over these procedures, managers must create a market strategy that is suitable and consistent with the business mission. Moreover, according to Hanaysha (2020), in order to establish a distribution chain, one must first analyse consumer requirements as follows: Firstly, identify the distribution chain's goals as well as potential barriers to achieving those goals. Secondly, identify which potential distribution chain options are the most important. Lastly, think about all of your options.

An analysis of published research in the relevant field revealed that there are a number of different approaches that businesses can take when offering their services and goods to consumers. Their primary distribution channels are often classified as "direct marketing channels" or "indirect marketing channels" (Huang and Liu 2017). As a result, these companies provide the consumer with a good or service that comes straight from the manufacturer. When it comes to the direct distribution of goods, there are three different types of people who represent the interests of a production company. These people are called dealers, brokers (brokers), and commissioners. In

the meantime, in this regard, brokers are included in the indirect distribution channel; any number of products can sell their goods to wholesalers and retailers, and as products reach consumers, they are sold in retail convenience stores. It is possible that product prices will go up as a result of the fact that a portion of the business's earnings will be distributed to every agent (Huang and Liu 2017).

The placement of a product or service in a marketing plan is among the most crucial elements of marketing strategy (Mason 2019). This "place" strategies of a business outlines how it will offer its products and services in an effort to grow its market share and the number of consumers. For instance, convenience stores are the final link in the distribution chain because they deal directly with their customers and supply them (Mason 2019). Technological advancements in information and communication have resulted in a shift in the manner in which the service industry interacts with its clients. Customers choose various service delivery channels in a manner compatible with their needs, such as the availability of personal assistance, the distance to travel, the working hours, the parking facility, and the physical location of the business. After being manufactured and given a price, products have to be distributed to the market before they can be sold. Every convenience store company needs to make decisions about their distribution to successfully bring their products and services to the consumers they are trying to reach (Hunelegn 2019).

The distribution strategy of a company is typically comprised of two primary elements: the distribution channels and physical distribution (Hameli 2018). According to Hameli (2018), who studied the business retailing types, distribution channels can be thought of as the paths that goods and services take on their journey from the point of production to the end user. The process that all convenience store companies use to disseminate the products and services that they sell to customers. Wholesalers and retailers are individuals and companies who distribute mainly to resellers or other distributors (Hameli 2018). Wholesalers and convenience store retailers can sell to the end consumer. The "physical distribution" of goods and services, which refers to the actual transportation of these items from their place of origin to the final customer, is a crucial component of any distribution strategy (Hameli 2018). The term "physical distribution" can refer to a wide variety of different activities (Hameli 2018). Some examples of these authorities and responsibilities include customer service, logistics

and inventory control, handling of materials, order processing, and warehouse management. It is necessary for convenience store companies to determine where they will purchase their goods and how they will get them to their end users. If products were made available at the right quantity, right place, and in the right time, the customer would be satisfied (Hirsch et al., 2021).

Another name for the location is the "distribution of a product," which is also used. It refers to the procedure and approach used to provide consumers with goods and/or services (Hirsch et al., 2021). This aspect of the marketing mix involves making choices and taking actions that are connected to the distribution of products from the manufacturer to the end user (Le-Hoang et al. 2020).

According to Degeratu and Gruca (2015), the function of marketing distribution can be broken down into two distinct parts. The initial delivery is viewed as a marketing channel, and its primary objective is to make the service not only more available to users but also more easily available to users who want to interact with it. The second consideration is the manner in which the service is actually rendered in everyday life. Depending on the type of service being provided, this can be affected by things like the local environment, the degree to which a particular technology is feasible, and transportation options (Degeratu and Gruca, 2015).

Distribution channels are essential to the success of convenience store businesses because they guarantee the prompt delivery of goods or services to customers which lead to profitability (Hirsch et al., 2021). Moreover, according to Hirsch et al. (2021), who studied profitability and profit persistence in EU food retail, if a company does not select the most reliable companies for this purpose, it runs the risk of upsetting its customers and delivering subpar service. In addition, according to Mason (2019), who studied logistics business on online grocery and profitability, in some contexts, a location could also be named a delivery or intermediate channel. The method through which ownership of produced services or goods is moved from the manufacturer to the final customer (Mason 2019). In addition to offering a wide range of things for purchase, convenience stores also offer the services required to deliver those products. The vast majority of retail businesses purchase their inventory from distributors or other vendors in the same format that it will be presented to the end

customer in. Convenience store retailers are in the business of increasing the value of a good or service by making it possible for customers to buy it at a location that is convenient for them, which leads to increased sales and profitability (Mason 2019). Furthermore, according to Le-Hoang et al., (2020), the part of the marketing strategy entails taking action and making decisions on the flow of products from the manufacturer to final customer.

According to Huang and Liu (2017), who studied the distribution strategies of convenience store chains in China from Japan 7–11, the majority of retail establishments have as their primary objective to maximise profits for the benefit of their owners or other stakeholders, while also adhering to the principles of corporate social responsibility. They also need to understand that profits are the best component of cash flow and financing for a company, and that this is something they should take into consideration. It is necessary to both lower the costs of distribution and increase the profit of the company in order to achieve high levels of both profit and service. As a result, the company must take into consideration the various aspects of the purchase, including the distribution of vehicles, the design of delivery information, etc. (Huang and Liu, 2017). According to Huang and Liu (2017), if the company expands its business marketing strategies to include place and distribution activities, it will be able to generate additional revenue and profitability as a result.

In addition, a number of the research recommendations suggest that the company's profitability may be affected by its location or distribution channel. According to the findings of the study that was conducted by Hunelegn (2019), the correlation and regression analysis showed that there is a significant relationship between product and place strategies and the profitability of a company. In addition, the researcher recommends that businesses cut their costs in order to provide customers with better prices and increase the number of customers they serve prior to actually incorporating pricing and promotion strategies. In addition, Fraser and Hite (1990), who studied the impact of international marketing strategies on performance in diverse global markets, stated that even though each major component of the marketing mix, such as place and distribution, seems to impact quality in one or more regions, the nature of the association and the degree to which it is present vary considerably across global regions. There is a strong correlation between large corporations' levels of profitability

and the degree to which they incorporate place and distribution into their marketing mix (Fraser and Hite, 1990).

Furthermore, according to Londhe (2014), who studied marketing mix for next generation marketing, demonstrated that there is a positive relationship between elements of the marketing mix and profitability. These elements include location and distribution channels. Moreover, Londhe (2014) stated that one strategy for increasing sales is to enhance the general quality that is reflected in the marketing mix. The marketing mix is one of the marketing strategies that can be utilised to accomplish goals. The four most important aspects of any marketing strategy are the product, the promotion, the location, and the price. Using these four pillars of the marketing mix, the convenience store company was required to be evaluated in relation to its rivals operating in the same geographic region. Multiple linear regressions demonstrate that one of the ways to contribute to the improvement of the convenience store company in order to gain sales and profit is to improve the marketing mix. This is one of the reasons why these regressions were carried out (Londhe 2014).

According to Degeratu and Gruca (2015), who studied The Effect of Marketing Mix Strategy on the Market Share and Profitability of Corporate Ventures, (product, promotion, place, and price) separately, the concept that the combined effect of marketing mix elements leads to superior performance and profitability is inherent in the concept of the marketing mix. Product, promotion, place, and price are the four components that make up the marketing mix. In this study, they recognise these marketing mix element variations for corporate ventures that are found in the PIMS Start-Up database by employing the technique of factor analysis. Degeratu and Gruca (2015) determine the combinations that best reflect the aggressiveness, breadth, and quality-focused orientation of the venture's marketing mix strategy. Through the use of regression, they were able to demonstrate that the corporate ventures' marketing mix had a significant impact on their market share as well as their return on sales and profitability. Moreover, those who pursue an aggressive strategy have both a larger market share and higher margins than their competitors (Degeratu and Gruca, 2015). Higher market share performance can be achieved through the use of either a broad coverage strategy or a focused niche strategy. However, this comes at the cost of

lower margins. It is plain to see that this element of the marketing mix contributes positively to the profitability of the business.

In conclusion, distribution is a part of the marketing mix that consists of decisions and actions pertaining to the movement of products from the producer to the end user. In most cases, the term "distribution channel" usually comprises a service that is characterised by the presence of the service provider in addition to intermediaries (agents) and the end user of the service. Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed based on the preceding discussion:

H4: The Place will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.5 People→Profitability

Judd and Vaught (1987) suggested adding a new component to the market mix, which they referred to as the "people" component. He suggested that it be finalised, implemented, and organised as a distinctive element of the market mix due to the fact that it is the staff who reflect the convenience store's company to the customers. If employees are not motivated by face-to-face interaction with customers, then it is possible that all marketing efforts will be in vain (Su-Mei, 2011). Moreover, service is a performance that cannot be detached from people, so the quality of a service company can only be as dependent on the quality of its employees (Dabija et al. 2014). The manner in which services are provided by individuals is an essential component of differentiation and a significant source of competitive advantage as well as a company's profitability (Chandra, 2016). The research findings of Chandra (2016), who studied Perceptions on Marketing Mix Strategies Practiced by Employees of Organized Retailers, demonstrated that employees have a significant impact on business performance and profitability.

The 7Ps, which are the extended marketing mix used in service management, include people as an essential component (Azeem and Sharma, 2015). According to Azeem and Sharma (2015), who studied the elements of the retail marketing mix and a study of different retail formats in India, the finding showed that employees play an important role in increasing sales and profitability for the company. Moreover, the employee is

typically the first point of contact for customers in the majority of service industries, including but not limited to department stores, hospitality, banking, and healthcare. During the course of this research, the researchers investigated various aspects of the marketing mix, one of which was the people or employees working in convenience stores. The perspective of the customer regarding the efficiency of the people providing the service is essential when conducting an analysis of the level of service provided (Azeem and Sharma, 2015). As a consequence of this, the provider of the service is obligated to focus their attention on the performance quality of their service employees by providing them with encouragement, vision, responses, expertise training and development, and other similar activities. Competencies like proactivity, assurance, and compassion and understanding will be absolutely necessary for optimal performance (Azeem and Sharma, 2015). It encompasses things like demeanour and conduct as well as expertise, self-assurance, courtesy, and a willingness to assist customers. Customer relationship management (CRM) needs to be given priority by service personnel in the form of personal attention, interpersonal care, readiness to assist, politeness, and caring behaviour (Azeem and Sharma, 2015).

According to Hill and Alexander (2017), who studied the handbook of customer satisfaction and loyalty measurement, the importance of providing excellent service to customers is frequently disregarded in the industry of convenience stores. Companies might have the misconception that they can gain a competitive advantage primarily by lowering their prices and that consumers are price-conscious to the point where they will only buy the item that is the least expensive option (Hill and Alexander, 2017). According to the findings of the study, the following aspects play a significant part in the decision-making process of customers and have the potential to give the convenience store business an advantage in the marketplace and increase profitability in their business (Hill and Alexander, 2017). To clarify, this refers to the offering of a replacement service to customers, such as changing business hours to better accommodate individual customers' needs and the punctual keeping of commitments and agreements.

Furthermore, according to Lam and Mayer (2014), who studied a model of voice in a customer service context, the finding showed that employees who provide exceptional

customer service have a substantial impact on sales and profitability. Moreover, the researchers suggested that the following factors are important whenever a customer receives a personalised service: First, know the names of the customers. Secondly, attending to the customer's needs and demonstrating concern for their satisfaction by being present at the business. Thirdly, ensure that the target market's customers can easily obtain the products. State-provided amenities and services are crucial considerations in this context. Fourthly, customer feedback is a crucial aspect of providing excellent service. Therefore, managers now have an advantage over their rivals. Fifthly, managers hire employees who genuinely care about the customers they serve. Finally, instruct employees on how to offer superior customer service (Lam and Mayer 2014).

To be successful in building customer loyalty, one must first comprehend the factors that bring customers into the store. On the other hand, Mitchell et al. (1998) conducted a number of studies on store image and found no correlation between store attributes and customer loyalty. According to Garton (1995) and Bloemer et al. (1998), the level of influence that a consumer's experience with the quality and service of a store has on whether or not they become a loyal repeat customer is relatively low.

Employees who are directly or indirectly involved in interactions with customers and vendors during the delivery, management, and organisation of convenience stores are considered to be part of the "people" component of the marketing mix strategy (Ali et al., 2017). Employees can come in many forms, including owners, managers, workers, and shareholders, as examples (Ali et al., 2017). Because employees in convenience stores communicate with customers, it is necessary for them to provide effective service quality in terms of attitude, competency, and professionalism. These three factors are equally important for ensuring that customers have a positive experience, are satisfied, and remain loyal. Convenience stores are great places to shop, so having friendly and helpful employees is just as important to the overall customer experience as having a wide variety of products to choose from (Ali et al., 2017).

According to the findings of a number of studies, the component of the marketing mix strategy that deals with people has a substantial bearing on the amount of profit that the company makes. According to Ali et al. (2017) who studied the impact of marketing

mix strategies on the performance of tourist hotels in the eastern province of Sri Lanka, variables in the marketing mix that have a positive effect on the marketing productivity and effectiveness of tourist hotels in the eastern province include product, price, location, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence. Based on the finding, it was shown that price and the people who interact with their offering are the two aspects of the marketing mix that have the most significant impact on marketing performance (Ali et al., 2017). People are an indispensable part of any product, service, or experience offered by a company. Particularly in the industry of convenience stores, production and consumption of a service typically occur simultaneously, and various facets of the consumer experience are altered to cater to the specific requirements of the individuals who are using the service. In addition, people have a tendency to do business with those that they like, and since this is the case, it is imperative that all employees possess excellent attitudes, skills, and appearances. People, or employees, play an important role in service provision. Convenience store retailers rely on them to carry out and maintain sales promotions, and they also play an important role in the relationship between retailers and their customers (Ali et al., 2017).

In addition, Pooser et al. (2018) carried out research on the subject of customer satisfaction within the United States auto insurance industry and linked the customer satisfaction rating of each insurer to profitability metrics. The findings lend credence to the hypothesis that increased levels of service satisfaction are associated with decreased expenses and increased profits. One possible explanation for this phenomenon is that contented consumers are more willing to continue their relationship with an insurance provider and to recommend the provider to their friends and family, thereby reducing the costs associated with the acquisition of new clients by the provider.

According to Judd and V.C. (1987), who examined the traditional advertising views of employees and developed a differentiation strategy for the purpose of gaining a competitive advantage and increasing profitability, employees should be recognised as a distinct component of the marketing mix, referred to as "people power," and should also be considered an integral part of the marketing strategy. By redefining the roles of its employees in terms of how they interact with customers and managing

those employees accordingly, an organisation can increase its profitability and achieve a competitive edge. In addition, Handayani et al. (2020) conducted research on the implementation of marketing mix in the success of businesses. The findings of this research revealed that the growth of fiber-based corporate development has improved in terms of the number of businesses, profitability, total production, and market share. Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed based on the preceding discussion:

H5: The People will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.6 Process→Profitability

The process is the methodical sequence that generates the perceived value that was guaranteed to the customers (Hanaysha et al., 2021). Based on Hanaysha et al.'s (2021) research study, process elements in the marketing mix significantly impact customer purchase decisions, which leads to profitability for companies. In the case of businesses that have a high level of customer interaction, such as convenience stores, the customers may play an important role in the business, which can turn the interaction into an experience for the business and purchase decision (Anjani et al., 2018). A poorly designed process has the potential to irritate customers by causing frustration due to poor service delivery quality (Anjani et al., 2018). In contrast, a very well-designed process ensures accessibility with speed, quality product, and convenience to consumers and can sometimes align requirements with service supply during peak hours as well (Anjani et al., 2018).

Moreover, the process element determines the method and order of services in convenience stores; it ensures that the value proposition promised to customers is created (Salloum and Ajaka). A poorly designed process can lead to slow, useless, and low-quality service delivery, resulting in customers' frustration (Kushwaha and Agrawal 2015). Customers can give different reactions in this situation. They can accept buying substitute products or go to other shops. According to Kushwaha and Agrawal (2015), who studied an Indian customer's surrounding 7Ps of service marketing, a study reveals that factors such as speed, product quality, and ease of service availability significantly affect customer satisfaction, which leads to increased

sales and profitability for a company. However, in some cases, failure to deliver quickly can cause consumers to abandon convenience stores (Kushwaha and Agrawal 2015).

The manner in which goods or services are delivered, in addition to the behaviour of the individuals who perform the delivery, are critical elements in determining the level of satisfaction a customer experiences. The interest of customers in a product or service can be increased by providing them with services that are prompt, accurate, and free of mistakes (Bahador 2019). Within the context of the marketing mix, "process" refers to all of the actual business settings and procedures that are followed in order to provide services (Bahador 2019). The method is an essential part of the marketing mix, and it plays a significant role in ensuring that customers are happy and content. According to Bahador (2019), who studied the effect of marketing mix on organizations' performance, process includes all of the actual procedures, mechanisms, and activities that are carried out in order to provide the services. The research findings showed that the process variables have a positive impact on sales and business performance as well as increase profitability (Bahador 2019). All of the activities that take place at work can be categorised as processes, which is an important element in the marketing mix strategy for convenience stores to increase profitability.

Furthermore, according to the findings of Chantayarkul et al. (2020), who explored the marketing strategy for enhancing the competitiveness of local traditional stores in Thailand, there is a significant influence of product and service quality on customer purchasing decisions at those stores. The investigation also established that providing a high level of services is critical for businesses to do in order to remain competitive and generate a profit (Chantayarkul et al. 2020).

The arrangement or process of the convenience store's space is also an important component of the marketing mix (Babu and Naveen 2018). According to Babu and Naveen (2018), who studied perceptions about 7ps of organised retail stores and unorganised retail stores, the research findings showed that a well-designed and created with a high emphasis on operational excellence by providing a large number of product lines and a substantial scale of activities significantly impacts on sales and profitability. This place will create an attractive environment for customers to buy (Babu

and Naveen 2018). In addition, according to Sankham and Putsom (2021), who studied the relationship between marketing mix perception and consumer choice in Muak Lek Municipality, convenience stores deal with a significantly large number of product lines and breadths, and they have a setup to manage. Convenience stores place a higher value on achieving operational excellence (Sankham and Putsom 2021). Although each of these process and service activities is an essential part of the overall marketing mix strategy, it would be expensive to deliver high-quality services to the target market with excellence (Sankham and Putsom 2021). For instance, the proprietor of a convenience store company is obligated to make advance payments to vendors for the purchase of goods and supplies, as well as salaries for employees and all other bills, such as those for electricity, upkeep, marketing and promotion, lease, and taxation, among other things. After deducting all costs from gross sales, a convenience store company will see an increase in their profitability (Sankham and Putsom 2021). As a consequence of this, increases in profitability occur in response to decreases in costs. The ability of a business to turn a profit is essential to its ability to maintain and expand its operations over time.

Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed based on the preceding discussion:

H6: The process will positively impact profitability.

2.4.7 Physical Evidence-Profitability

Customers' perceptions of a company's service quality and their intentions regarding how they will behave are impacted by physical evidence, which provides a tangible indication of that quality (Elgarhy and Mohamed 2022). Because it is an intangible performance, customers are unable to evaluate the quality of the service. However, they are going to rely heavily on the service environment (also known as the service scape) as a key alternative for quality (Elgarhy and Mohamed 2022). In this context, "physical evidence" refers both to the interior design and the exterior appearance of the physical surroundings, as well as the experience of the customer at service delivery sites (Mudassir et al. 2022). As a consequence of this, service companies have a responsibility to manage physical evidence because it has the potential to have a reflective influence on the impressions that customers form (Mudassir et al. 2022) and because it communicates the image of the company that provides the service package. This includes the outward appearance of the building, the surrounding

landscape, the interior furnishings, the technology-based infrastructure, the equipment, the uniforms of the staff, the communication materials, and whatever other viewable prompts (Ramadani 2020). Alterations in technology and organisational structure are suggested for the retail service sector as a means of realising both of its marketing objectives (Ramadani 2020).

According to research conducted by Hill and Alexander (2017), who studied customer satisfaction and loyalty measurement, there is a positive impact on high-value perceptions on the physical evidence of business services stores on sales and profitability. The physical evidence of business services, including customer satisfaction, wide assortment, and convenience, is offered by the convenience stores (Hill and Alexander 2017). In addition, according to Khairannur (2021), who studied marketing strategy for PT. Aurora Wisata Internusa Medan during the COVID-19 Pandemic, the research findings showed that physical evidence of the shop has a positive relationship with customer purchase decisions, which leads to profitability for the company. Moreover, the majority of customers typically visit two or more retail establishments on a consistent basis. This is partly due to the fact that they shop at a variety of locations, such as on the commute home from work or during other activities outside the home (Khairannur 2021). In a similar vein, one might go to a different store depending on the quantity of goods needed (for instance, one might make a purchase once a month or just restock when it's absolutely necessary), or one might go to a different store depending on the type of goods needed (e.g., vegetables, meat, frozen foods, discounts, etc.) (Khairannur 2021). In terms of convenience store situations, some customers might well be searching for specific products that meet their highest standards, or different members of the same household might have different preferences regarding which convenience stores to patronise.

To be successful in generating repeat business from existing customers, it is necessary to first comprehend the factors that bring customers into the store. Despite this, Mitchell (1998) conducted several studies on store image and found no correlation between both store attributes and customer loyalty.

The "physical evidence" component of the marketing mix refers to the customer's experience with the surrounding physical environment, such as the design and

organisation of a store (Bahador 2019). According to Bahador (2019), who studied the effect of the marketing mix on organizations' performance, the finding showed that the "physical evidence" component of the marketing mix has a positive impact on a company's profitability and sales. Moreover, customers are unable to evaluate the quality of the service because it is an intangible effectiveness. However, they are going to rely heavily on the service environment (also known as the service scape) as a key alternative for quality (Bahador 2019). All of the tangibly present items that customers can see and touch constitute the elements of the physical evidence in the case of a convenience store.

In addition, according to O'Sullivan and Ngugi (2022), who studied marketing mix, the style and exterior of the immediate environment, as well as the expertise of customers at service delivery sites, are all connected to physical evidence in some way. Consequently, convenience stores are obligated to manage physical evidence because it has the potential to have a reflective influence on customers' perceptions and it communicates an external image of the service package, both of which can lead to the development of a desire to make a purchase and an increase in profitability. Based on O'Sullivan and Ngugi's research findings, (2022) physical evidence has a positive relationship with business performance and profitability.

One more researcher's hypothesis proposes that customers' perceptions of a company's service quality and their intentions to make a purchase are impacted by physical evidence in the form of tangible evidence of that firm's service quality (Qomariah and Kurnia 2022). According to Qomariah and Kurnia 2022, who studied the Impact of Marketing Mix (7P) on Impulse Buying at Supermarket MD 3, Jember, based on research findings, demonstrated that the physical evidence of the store's image has a significant impact on store sales and profitability. For example, the appearance of the building, the grounds, the interior and exterior furnishings, the infrastructure, the equipment, and the uniforms of the employees, the communication materials, and any other visible prompts are all examples of physical evidence (Qomariah and Kurnia 2022). All of these concrete pieces of evidence serve as observable confirmation of a convenience store's company's appearance, and they contribute to the establishment of the shop's reputation, business performance, as well as profitability.

It is widely acknowledged that the reputation of the store is a significant contributor to the amount of repeat business it receives. According to Hartman and Spiro (2005), who studied store image in customer-based store equity and conceptualization, research findings presented that the physical evidence of the appearance of a store has a positive impact on a company's profitability and sales, as well as its location, the products and services it offers, as well as the friendliness and expertise of its staff, are all factors that contribute to the store's reputation. This image can be determined through the functional qualities of the environment as well as the psychological characteristics of the store's customers (Hartman and Spiro 2005). In other words, when we talk about a store's image, we're referring to the reputation that a particular store has developed over the course of time in the minds of its customers. (Hartman and Spiro, 2005).

A positive image for a brand can help that brand garner more attention, pique the interest of prospective customers, and form contacts (Elgarhy and Mohamed 2022). It can also help improve customer satisfaction and influence customers to spread satisfied customers. According to Elgarhy and Mohamed (2022), who investigated the influences of services marketing mix (7ps) on loyalty, intentions, and profitability in the Egyptian Travel Agencies, the research showed that the elements of physical evidence have a significant impact on sales and profitability.

In addition, the quality and variety of the brands that are carried, the speed with which products can be obtained, the prices, the atmosphere of the stores themselves, and the level of service that is provided to customers can all contribute to the establishment's overall reputation (Jain et al. 2022). According to Jain et al. (2022), who studied Analyzing and Exploring the Effectiveness of Each Element of the 7Ps of Marketing Mix, these aspects of a store's image have an impact on customer behaviour and the extent to which they retain a brand's loyalty, both of which are directly related to the retention of customers' trust, which, in addition to maintaining a positive image for one's convenience store, is an essential component for businesses that wish to continue to be profitable.

Moreover, according to the findings of Erlina and Hermawan (2021), who investigated the marketing mix at a coffee shop in Bandung and its influence on customer loyalty, the most significant factor that affects customer loyalty and company profitability is physical evidence. This study highlights the significance of the various components of the marketing mix in the process of engaging consumers in the coffee shop sector. When it comes to the convenience store industry, one of the most important factors for long-term growth and profitability is having a large number of loyal customers. Based on the above literature, the hypotheses for this study are presented as follows:

H7: The Physical evidence will positively impact the profitability.

2.4.8 Profitability

The ability to turn a profit is a measure of both effectiveness and, eventually, success or failure. It is the ratio that is used to determine how much of a profit a convenience store chain can expect to make in comparison to its total revenue. Profitability can be described as the ability of a company to create a profitability ratio that measures its resource management compared to an alternative investment. This definition of profitability focuses on a company's ability to compete with other investments (Melissa Horton, 2019). According to Laffy and Walters (2016), who study managing retail productivity and profitability ratios, in general, measures the efficiency with which large retailers generate business activity into profits. Specifically, these ratios focus on the ratio of gross profit to total revenue. The ability of a business to turn revenue into profits can be measured by looking at a company's profit margins. Return on assets is a performance metric that evaluates a company based on its ability to turn its assets into net income. For a company to be considered profitable, its total income must be greater than its total expenses. The expenditures of the various resources that are utilised in the running of a business are referred to as its expenses. The company that owns convenience stores determines its profits by conducting an analysis of what is left over after operating expenses have been subtracted from total revenue (Laffy and Walters, 2016).

According to Anthonia (2019), the term "profit" refers to the sum of money that is left over after all expenses have been subtracted from revenue sales. As a consequence

of this, an increase in costs poses a threat to profits, in particular when the relatively modest price increase is not easily passed on to the customer and cost-cutting strategies are not aggressively pursued as a way to reduce total costs, which will improve profitability. This is because an increase in costs makes it more difficult to pass on the marginal increase in cost to the consumer (Anthonia 2019). In general, profits are the results of a variety of business activities and decisions, such as marketing, pricing, location, labour, and so on (Black et al. 2017). Ineffective marketing strategies may be to blame for the lack of supply of goods and services, in addition to production shortages. Scarcity can be turned into the availability of products and services by employing marketing strategies that are both innovative and effective. Therefore, it is evident that the marketing mix has an effect on the profitability of the organisation (Black et al. 2017). For instance, Cleary et al. (2018) state that a marketing mix strategy is profitable for organisations when it is properly implemented and that these profits can be used to expand the organisation. They continue by suggesting that a well-executed marketing strategy would be profitable for the organisation; therefore, it is worthwhile to argue that marketing can influence the profitability of organisations. For example, the term "market penetration" refers to efforts made by an organisation to expand sales of existing products within existing markets, with the ultimate goal of raising the business's overall level of profitable activity. Of course, there are some situations in which a more aggressive marketing mix is required (Cleary et al. 2018).

To summarise, profit is critical in business. Companies must become profitable in order to survive in a competitive industry and grow their businesses. Based on the above literature, the conceptual framework and research hypotheses for this study are presented as following topic.

2.5 Conceptual framework and research hypotheses

The main goal of this research is to see if marketing strategies affected the profitability of convenience stores. Figure 2 describes the conceptual framework that was developed. The relationships between various components were illustrated and summarised by developing this conceptual framework. It also aided in the formulation of hypotheses.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework

Source: The Researcher

As shown in Table 2.1, seven hypotheses were developed based on the research questions and literature reviews, which will serve as the structure for the research tools (questionnaires) used to determine the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom market. This research thus will provide a complete study of the convenience store industry in the United Kingdom, under the framework of marketing mix 7p. This chapter has also briefly examined one models (Ohanian, 1990), which were influential for building a framework for this research as shown in Figure 1.

	Research questions:
RQ4	What is the relationship between marketing mix 7ps and profitability?
RQ5	How does marketing strategy impact the profitability of convenience stores?
	Research hypotheses:
H1	The product differentiation will positively impact the profitability.
H2	The Promotion variation will positively impact the profitability.
H3	The Price variation will positively impact the profitability.
H4	The Place will positively impact the profitability.
H5	The People will positively impact the profitability.
H6	The Process will positively impact the profitability.
H7	The Physical evidence will positively impact the profitability.

Table 2.1: The research hypotheses
Source: The Researcher

The following topic discussed the convenience store in more detail.

2.6 The convenience store concept

There are several types of convenience stores or corner shops, including franchisee outlets, speciality stores, and supermarkets. The convenience store concept in the United Kingdom is committed to keeping up with shopper demand and their dynamic necessities (Anon, 2010). A convenience store is defined as a retail store with a gross floor area of 3,500 square feet or less that sells a variety of goods and products for daily convenience and the shopping needs of consumers (Anon, 2010).

Though the supermarket provided one-stop shopping, consumers found that it was inconvenient to shop for emergency needs. The needs for emergency purchase, together with the increase in numbers of double income families, facilitated the

expansion of convenience stores in the United States from the 1970s (Su, 1990). A convenience store, according to Kotler (2000), is a "relatively small store located near a residential area, open long hours and seven days a week, and carrying a limited line of high turn-over convenience products at slightly higher prices" (compared with the prices at the supermarket). Many people have added pastries, coffee, and takeout sandwiches to their menus.

According to W. Lamb, F. Hair, and McDaniel (2008), a convenience store can be describe as a small shop that carries just a limited selection of quality convenience items. They are typically found along with major streets, in densely populated urban areas, at gas or petrol points, or in close proximity to transportation stations or other train stations. In certain countries, these convenience stores often have extended store hours, and some are even open 24 hours a day. Gas station stores may also sell windshield washer fluid, motor oil, maps, and radiator fluid. Health and toiletries are frequently supplied in these shops, which also offer money transfer services as well as alcoholic beverages in some cases. Moreover, according to P.Miller et al. (2009), a convenience store is a small operation or shop selling items such as dairy products, candy, sodas, newspapers, magazines, and scratch cards, as well as a variety of groceries and ready meals.

The definition of convenience store varies slightly across countries, as shown in table 2.2 below.

The British Association of Convenience Stores or Corner shop (ACS UK)	The American Convenience Store Association (ACSA)	The Manufacture Convenience Store Research, Japan (MCR)
"From 300 square meters to 12,000 square feet (1,100 m2)"	Below 300 square meters	Below 300 square meters
As a result of various competition acts and the availability of large business space, several of the bigger top stores, including Sainsbury's Local, Little Waitrose, and	5-15 parking space	Foods sales accounting for over 50% of total sales

Tesco Express, have established store formats based on convenience store and corner shop scales.		
“Large-format shops larger than 12,000 square feet (1,100 m2) were permitted to open on Sunday under the Sunday” Trading Act of 1994, which was recently revised to seven days a week and.24 hours a day.	Extended hour operation, compared with stores in the nearby area	Opening hour over 16 hours per day, 340 days per year
Self-service	Self-service	Selling over 2,000 items, mainly service and convenience products
Small stores that sell perishable goods for example bread milk, fresh meat, butter, vegetables, food, drinks, and household items.	Mainly selling deli, foods and groceries	Equipped with POS or EOS systems
Small Corner shops, owned by local companies that were often started by people who had starting a trading business.	Being complement of supermarket	

Table 2.2 Definitions of the convenience store in different countries
Source: (ACS UK, 2022)

To summarise, a convenience store is a store with a small shop of less than 300 square metres. They sell foodstuffs, household items, under counter medicines, and other goods and services at slightly higher prices, but with a limited selection (Mang’era and Munga, 2021). A convenience store typically stocks 2,000–3,000 different product lines. When compared to other retail formats, for example, a supermarket in the United Kingdom typically stocks 6,500–8,500 lines. The purpose of the convenience store is to serve customers who are not price-sensitive or who make emergency purchases.

In addition, in the United Kingdom, convenience stores are valued according to the following three benefits: First, convenient shopping locations. In the United Kingdom, convenience stores are normally located in residential areas, in prosperous business areas, near traffic centres such as railway stations, and near schools. Consumers can reach a convenience store in around 5–10 minutes by walk. Second, they provide convenient shopping hours for customers. A convenience store is normally open for 14 hours per day for the whole year. Third, the compact store size and clear space allocation enable customers to find the convenience goods quickly. It provides convenient products. They sell small-sized items that are easy to carry for consumers. Moreover, since in-store space is very limited, the product assortments generally reflect the basic needs of customers in order to satisfy consumers' needs for convenience goods (Rybackzewska and Sparks, 2020).

Besides convenience, the convenience store also provides modern shopping environment because it has the following characteristics (Hsu, 1997): Emphasis on customer-relationships: to provide services to retain customer loyalty. Comfortable store ambience: to provide comfortable shopping environment. Efficient store operation: In an attempt to lower employment costs, convenience stores implemented self-service, and retail outlet operations were implemented in order to maximise profits. Moreover, the support of know-how from the headquarters also improves store-operation efficiency.

2.6.1 Reasons for selecting the convenience store industry

In this research, the convenience store is chosen to test Marketing Mix 7Ps theory because it plays an important role in the modernisation of the general merchandise retail industry in the United Kingdom. Moreover, it is worthy of attention because of this industry's tremendous growth in the 2020. According to an IBIS World (2022), the convenience store industry in the United Kingdom is estimated to grow at a multiple yearly ratio of 2.9 percentage above the 5 years through 2021-22, reaching £44.3 billion. Changing trends, such as the growing popularity of top-up shopping, have been key to revenue growth.

According to Lumina Intelligence (2021) report, convenience stores have the highest visit frequency among grocery channels, with two visits per week, compared with

supermarkets with 1.8 visits and online grocery with 1.5 visits and due to convenience stores catering to the little and often purchasing pattern. The effects of the COVID-19 (coronavirus) pandemic are expected to linger, particularly in the first half of the period as local shopping habits become ingrained, while subdued incomes are likely to lead to more home cooking. However, competition from supermarkets is expected to intensify as they continue to expand their online businesses.

In addition, based on ACS (2018), the survey found that customers' main reason for shopping in the stores of the United Kingdom was the proximity to home. Most customers at that time were aged between 20 and 40. It also showed consumers' major reasons for shopping in convenience stores were proximity/convenience, providing official receipts and stocking complete product assortment.

Therefore, convenience/proximity is always the main reason for consumers' patronage of convenience stores. This explains why convenience store retailers are eager in expanding their stores island-wide. During the 2020s, the number of convenience stores grew rapidly; the store expansion was mainly through different franchise mechanisms - either franchise or voluntary chain systems. According to ACS (2018), network expansion through franchise and voluntary chain systems is the focus of the convenience store industry. These chain stores grew at the expense of individual stores.

The following topic discussed about the second objective of this research, which is to examine existing practises of marketing strategies on profitability. It also seeks to determine what the various marketing strategies at convenience stores are that improve company profitability. Thus, the next chapter explains in detail the relationship between retail strategies and profitability in the convenience store sector.

2.7 The relationship between retail strategies and profitability in retail sectors (inclusive of convenience stores)

The following section will explaining retail strategies and review these previous works and point out their limitations. This section will also examine the various marketing strategies employed by convenience stores to increase their profitability. Even though the number of convenience stores is increasing, surviving in a highly competitive

industry is difficult. According to Hood et al. (2016), convenience stores in the United Kingdom are owned by locals, Asians, and Middle Easterners, who entered these markets, which created fierce competition in the surrounding areas. In this industry, most convenience store companies compete with one to another. Thus, many convenience stores companies employ various strategies including Strategic Planning that suitable for the business in order to survive and increase profitability in the highly competitive retail industry (Fox and Sethuraman, 2010). The next chapter will explains in detail about Strategic Planning in retail industry.

2.7.1 Strategic Planning in retail industry

According to Bryson, (2011)The term "strategic planning" refers to a tool that can be thought of as a "guide" to the realisation of an organization's long-term goals. It outlines the processes and programmes that an organisation plans to implement in order to transition the company from the state it is in now to the outcome that is anticipated for the company in the foreseeable future. It places an emphasis on the most efficient and successful approaches to achieving organisational success. It is possible for companies in the retail industry, and specifically convenience store companies, to implement retail strategic planning in order to run the most profitable businesses possible. This process of strategic planning consists of steps such as conducting a situational analysis, establishing objectives, and determining target markets. Refer to Figure 2.1, which demonstrates a view of these discussions follow to the general strategic planning process. Organizations use strategic planning to create a plan with goals and targets to realise their strong vision. (Donkor et al., 2018).

Figure 2.1: General strategic planning procedure (Donkor et al., 2018).

Moreover, according to Weston (2020), strategic planning is the deliberate, systematic process of determining a direction and action plan for achieving a desired future vision. A retailer of convenience stores could apply strategic planning concepts to establish a future desired state and clear direction and objectives in the form of a documented list of goals, objectives, actions, and outcomes to achieve this vision. It begins with an audit of the strategic assessment of the environment. When planning strategically, a number of methods can be employed to identify current and emerging trends. The information gathered has frequently been organised using a SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) (Benzaghta et al., 2021). This involves conducting an environmental scan to determine the convenience store company's strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats.

Human capital, culture, resources, assets, and distinctive characteristics should be evaluated as part of the internal environment of an organisation. The evaluation of the external environment should include competitors, location, suppliers, target customers, technological trends, and the competitive marketplace for convenience stores. The manager of convenience stores can make decisions regarding market segmentation and company positioning based on an analysis of the external and internal environment. Best practises in Strategic Planning involve establishing the course.

Most convenience store business owners have a mission and vision statement (Tien et al., 2019). The mission statement describes what the business does, who it serves, and how it serves them. A strong mission should inspire the team to work toward a common objective. Often, these convenience stores have a mission statement along the lines of "to provide customers with high-quality, affordable products and excellent service (Tien et al., 2019)." Strategy is an intricate process. Each step of the plan must be consistent with the others, and as decisions are made regarding areas of concentration or approaches to be taken, the mission and vision will become more distinct. As clarity emerges on how to best add value to the customer, more resilient strategies will be identified and the ultimate vision will become more clear.

The last step is strategic choices and implementation. According to Weston (2020), Strategic plans frequently fail due to a lack of a well-defined implementation plan or a

failure to follow through on the proposed plan. To begin, implementation entails establishing alignment by ensuring that everyone on the convenience store team understands and is committed to the direction. To gain support for the strategic plan, convenience store owners and managers must clearly explain the clear plans, the reasoning for the direction, and exactly how the planned actions will achieve the desired objectives in a way that is clear enough to communicate all of the nuances and subtleties (Weston 2020). Convenience store owners and managers need to get their teams excited about the future. Therefore, even with all the daily tasks, goals and priorities can still be achieved.

When developing strategic options, many studies in general adopt two major approaches for strategic planning:

1. The product-mission matrix developed by Ansoff (Kristenson, 1983; Omura, 1986; Knee and Walters, 1985; Walters, 1989; McGoldrick, 1990)
2. Retail strategy based on Porter's five forces model (Knee and Walters, 1985; Walters, 1989; McGoldrick, 1990; Davies and Brooks, 1989).

The following section will focus on the discussion of retail strategy based on the product-mission matrix.

2.7.2 Retail strategy based on the product-mission matrix

Ansoff's strategic planning includes the decision plan in strategic formulation and the product-mission matrix. The earlier is a standard strategic planning procedure: decision on strategic objective, internal and external analysis, and the decision of strategic directions. The latter has four options for a company's strategies, based on the product and market a company chooses. Kristenson (1983) develops a model of retail strategic planning based on Ansoff's strategic planning framework. He contends that any strategic planning should consider the following three factors first: consumers' demand, a retailer's resources and environmental factors. Following the analysis of the above three aspects, he develops an 'assortment-segment-matrix' and 'the capability grid applied to retail'.

The matrix provides retailers of Convenience Stores Company with basic strategic choices based on market segments and product assortments. The retail capability grid is a tool for Convenience Stores retailers to determine their organisational functions needed to achieve these strategic choices. By using the 10 matrix and the grid, Convenience Stores retailers can set a strategic direction and make clear the resources necessary to develop along that direction. Furthermore, Omura (1986) combined Ansoff's product-mission matrix with other three concepts - the corporate portfolio planning techniques, the retail life cycle, and the merchandise-market scope - and develops a model of retail strategy development.

The model suggests that the strategic planning start from the environmental and internal assessment and the decision of strategic objectives. The model then suggests four common corporate strategies: To manage for immediate cash, to manage for earnings, to invest for future growth and to disinvest. The product-and-market mix based on Ansoff's model is developed subsequently to provide detailed directions for implementing these strategies in convenience store business to increase profitability.

Furthermore, Knee and Walters (1985) used Ansoff's product-mission matrix to create four strategic options for retailers. The first is productivity and consolidation, which means increased efficiency from existing resources to asset utilisation, volume, and higher margins. The second step is diversification, which involves expanding into new product categories and trading environments. Take into account multifaceted and global activities such as customer service or service products. The third option is to expand into related trading or environmental product categories, or both. Finally, repositioning, which involves meeting the changing needs of current customers and related customer segments. Thus, to increase profitability, a convenience store retailer could consider repositioning and expansion.

The following section will focus on the discussion of Retail strategy based on Porter's five forces model strategy.

2.7.3 Retail strategy based on Porter's five forces model

Porter's five forces have two components, which are the framework of industrial analysis and the generic strategy framework. The previous provides a framework to

analyse the external factors of a company. The latter provides a company with three strategic directions—cost leadership, differentiation, and focus (Lauer, 2019). Michael Porter introduced the theory of generic strategies as a great achievement in the discipline in his famous book *Competitive Strategy* (1980). He identified three basic strategy types by using two components: competitive advantage, with the possibility of lower costs or differentiation; and competitive scope, which can be narrow or broad. Differentiation, cost/price leadership, and niche focus:

Price/Cost Leadership: This strategy includes companies that compete on price and focus on the entire market, attempting to gain a large market share in order to realise maximum cost savings from economies of scale. In the highly competitive business environment of today's companies, many companies in the convenience store industry are looking for the best way to gain a competitive advantage. Pulaj et al. (2015) suggest that Porter's generic strategies are currently relevant and technically proficient to support and guide as a direction for a company in trying to define the significant strategy to accomplish its objectives and achieve maximum success (Pulaj et al.2015). Companies that possess these capabilities are in a position to gain a competitive advantage by delivering products that are identical to those of the competition at prices that are lower than the industry standard in order to achieve higher levels of profitability, or by delivering products that are comparable to the industry standard in order to achieve comparable levels of profitability (Brenes et al.2014). According to Brenes et al. (2014), the strategy of cost leadership requires quality along with price aggressiveness. Nevertheless, it is attempted by businesses in an effort to have a competitive advantage by implementing an effective lower cost in comparison with the competition. A company can take advantage of a situation like this by either lowering its costs and gaining market share and business from competitors, or by maintaining its costs at the level they are currently at in the market and making a slightly higher profit on each unit that it sells. In this way, the assembling requirements can in some way or another support the application of one of the techniques that are referenced (Asiedu,2015).

Differentiation: Dombrowski et al. (2018) stated that differentiation took place when a product appears to be unique and of high quality and standard. Differentiation includes distinguishing the company's service or product, creating something that is perceived to be unique in the competitive marketplace. For example, rivalry of

convenience stores will, in general, create between various item classes, which play out a similar capacity with regards to complex needs. This strategic positioning is founded on competitive advantages other than lower prices, such as improved functionality, higher quality, or superior services. By providing unique products and services, the convenience store company would gain a competitive advantage and increase profitability. Nonetheless, the entire market is being targeted, not just a specific segment. It entails providing advantages of products and services that are distinct from competitors while charging a comparable or, in some cases, higher price. Differentiation techniques are widely used in market economies and are overarching methods for gaining competitive advantages (Karyani & Rossieta, 2018). Differentiation could be based on a variety of fundamentals or aspects, such as product features, brand, design, customer service, and product image. If competitors work in a small or similar market segment, it is reasonable to use focused differentiation (Brenes et al.2014).

Focus (Niche): A niche strategy focuses on a specific and well-defined market segment or target market, usually by offering a specialised product or service or a special price. According to Porter, a company must select one of these generic strategy types in its entirety and not mix them. Convenience store companies, for example, that lack positioning by not clearly representing one of those types, "stuck in the middle," will most probably fail.

According to Gilbert and Strebel (1987), success does not necessarily imply focusing solely on a cost-or price-leadership strategy or a differentiation strategy; instead, those certain strategies can be viewed as stages in the market evolution process. There are two development paths that can lead to a successful superior market position. These innovative companies continuously improve the value of the new product at an early stage of the product life cycle until a commonly accepted standard is established. This level marks a watershed moment in the strategic orientation. Prices are now the main cause of competition. As a result, businesses must shift their strategic focus to cost reduction, which is primarily accomplished through process improvements.

In addition, researchers Davies and Brooks (1989) use Porter's retailers' positioning strategy. The research starts by using Porter's five-force model to analyse the

influential factors in Britain's food retail industry. The discussion then focuses on price and image of various sectors of British retail industry, e.g., the food retail industry and the DIY retailing. The research concludes that differentiation is the key factor for British retailers seeking success in the future.

Furthermore, Helms, Haynes and Cappel (1992) also utilise Porter's framework of five forces and generic strategy when examining the US retailers' strategic choices. They discuss the difference of influential factors between the manufacturing industry and the retailing industry based on Porter's five forces. The study then surveys 40 retailers and concludes that most of sampled retailers pursue combination strategy of low-cost and differentiation.

Most convenience store strategies appear to fall within Porter's cost leadership category. However, it is not surprising that cost leaders and differentiators can be successful simultaneously and increase their profitability. For instance, convenience stores such as Sainsbury's maintain a high level of service quality by offering customers high-quality goods at reasonable prices (Cronshaw et al. 1994). It has varying prices to accommodate various types of customers. It was able to establish a high level of customer trust by providing low-cost, fundamental products to customers with low income. The following section will focus on the discussion of limitations of these retail marketing strategic planning models.

2.7.4 Limitations of retail strategic planning models

Despite their popularity, Ansoff's product-mission matrix and Porter's five forces framework have their drawbacks. Ansoff's product-mission matrix is fairly simple and highly generalised (Davies and Brooks, 1989), as are the later adaptations of this matrix (Mudambi, 1994). It is difficult to label a convenience stores retailer as choosing only one specific strategy. The convenience stores retail industry is highly dynamic and this framework may not model the market situations and a retailer's strategic choices correctly because a retailer may pursue multiple strategies and its strategic decisions are highly interrelated. One example of this problem is seen in Knee and Walters' strategic choices mentioned earlier. Knee and Walter (1989) mention that a

retailer will develop these four strategies one at a time, in line with the increasing investment risk. However, in reality, a convenience stores retailer may utilise several strategies at the same time or may prefer a higher risk strategy to a lower risk one.

For example, a convenience stores retailer may pursue growth of stores because it wants to build scale economies and improve productivity. A retailer may also diversify through a strategic alliance to reduce the risk of introducing new services; thus the risk of diversification may not be larger than repositioning and growth. Porter's five-forces of industrial analysis and the generic strategy framework are another widely used set of retail strategic planning tools. Though the five-forces is adopted in strategic analysis of the retail industry, Walters (1989) points out some determinants of Porter's five-forces framework are not applicable for this industry.

For example, contrary to the prediction of Porter's framework, the bargaining power of customers does not threaten convenience stores retailers' retailer-brand product development, based on the fact that the power of retailer-brand products in the UK grocery retail industry dominates consumers' purchases. McGee (1987) also criticises the five forces as unsatisfactory in explaining retail competition. Due to the following two reasons, this framework cannot explain retailers' strategic directions in the real world: Firstly, the simplification of retailers' strategies based on Porter's generic strategy. Secondly, the positioning of a retailer's strategy at a certain corner of the generic strategy matrix. For instance, the study of Helms, Haynes and Cappel (1992) mentioned earlier shows that the majority of retailers they sampled (12 out of 20) use a combination strategy, i.e., combination of the low-cost and the differentiation strategy, instead of using a single strategy.

Previous studies of retail strategy based on Ansoff's framework and Porter's five forces contend that a convenience stores retailer's strategies are confined within the retailer's environment. This view dictates the passive role of a convenience stores retailer towards its environment and ignores the ability of the retailer to change its environment. These discussions also do not mention what resources a convenience stores company will need when planning strategies, nor do they describe patterns of resource deployment (McGee, 1987). Though McGee's discussions of strategy include the deployment of distinctive assets in the formulation of strategy and creation

of a retail business portfolio, his framework does not explain the relationship between competition and a retailer's adoption of certain resources and strategies. This framework also does not explain the change of retailers' strategic moves over time.

Another drawback of these studies is that discussions are confined to a certain point in time and do not model the dynamics of retail competition or changes in strategy over time. Moreover, Miller, Reardon, and Mocorkie (1999) stated that more research needs to be done on possible multiple causal loops, nonlinearities, and dynamical changes in the composition because competition is by definition a one-way idea.

Some studies of retail competition try to describe the change in retail development over time (Guy, 1994; Swinyard, 1997; Millier, Reardon and Mocorkie, 1999; Clarke, 2000). For example, Swinyard (1997) discusses US retail trends in the 1990s, and Clarke (2000) describes the competitive dynamics in the UK convenience store retail industry. However, these discussions are not based on theoretical frameworks and often use anecdotal evidence. Thus, the problem is how to describe convenience stores retail competition using a theoretical framework and at the same time put retail strategic planning into long-term perspective. One way to show strategic movement over time is to apply the retail life cycle in the process of their strategic planning (Knee and Walters, 1989; Omura, 1986).

2.8 Summary

This chapter provided a review of literature that already exists about relationship between the marketing strategies and profitability of conveniences store, the introduction of literature review, Marketing Strategy, Benefits of Marketing Strategy, Profitability, theories regarding retail organizational change, Conceptual framework and research hypotheses. In section 2.3 explains the benefits of marketing strategies including marketing mix which is Product differentiation, Promotion variation, Price variation, Place, People, Process and Physical evidence. All of the aspects were examined in this chapter in order to comprehend their significance in marketing and how the constructs are interconnected. It was possible to construct concepts by combining various ideas and outcomes from previous research. Based on the literature reviews, there are several research gap found as follow:

- There is a lack of empirical research into the company implements its marketing strategies and maximise their profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.
- Little is known about the relationship between the marketing strategies, product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, advertisement, customer service, and profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.
- Marketing literature has no systematic study on the effect of: (Product differentiation and profitability), (Promotion variation and profitability), (Price variation and profitability), (Place and profitability), (People and profitability), (Process and profitability) and (Physical Evidence and profitability).
- There is a lack of explanatory models and theory-building studies in the area marketing mix 7p and profitability.
- Despite the fact that convenience store retailer's experienced strong competition, the development of this industry seldom attracts attention of English academia and the existing studies in the United Kingdom are obsolete and lack a theoretical explanation.

This research thus provides a complete study of the convenience store industry in the United Kingdom under the framework of marketing mix 7p. This chapter has also briefly examined one model (Ohanian, 1990), which was influential in building a framework for this research as shown in Figure 1. Afterwards, as shown in Table 2.1, seven hypotheses were developed, which serve as the structure for the research tools (questionnaires) used to determine the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom market. The next chapter goes into detail about the methods that were used to collect the primary data collection.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1. Chapter Overview

The purpose of this chapter is to explain the procedures, methods, and techniques employed by the researcher during the course of the study. In this chapter, the authors explain the method used to test the hypotheses and answer the research questions posed in Chapter 1. This methodology chapter also presents the precise measures that have been taken to address the research questions and objectives. For this reason, the method section logically follows from the problem statement, much as research questions follow from the literature review. This section also discusses and provides justification for the study's sample size, measurement instruments, analysis methods, and data collection.

The chapter begins with the methodological review of research in Section 3.2. In Section 3.3, the objectives are outlined. In section 3.4, the research question is explained. Section 3.5 examines research design details in greater depth. Section 3.6 addresses the collection of data, and the chapter's summary is in Section 3.7.

3.2 The methodological review of research

This chapter's objective is to provide an explanation of the theory and methods employed to address the research question and achieve the research objective. The research's methodology was carefully and meticulously developed based on its goals. Systematic methods that are based on this study are part of the research methodology. The research clarifies the sequential choices and judgements taken using "Research Onion" framework (Saunders, et al., 2012). The "research onion," as depicted in figure 3 below, provides a framework that may be used to more effectively ensure that everything is accomplished in a logical manner.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders et al. 2012. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 3: Research Onion. Source: Saunders, et al., 2012.

First, the researcher determines whether the research's underlying philosophy adheres to interpretivism, objectivism, positivism, realism, constructivism or pragmatism. The researcher then gathered the necessary information for the research. This research involves a deductive method design, philosophy, process, sample size for data collection, and the design of research questions. This methodology section explains the goal of the research on the topic, as well as the steps and clarity of the whole research process.

In the subsequent study, the rationale behind the use of quantitative is also explained. In addition, the researcher discusses how quantitative techniques were used to choose participants. The processing and acquisition of data is vital to the study and can be categorised as either primary or secondary data (Remenyi, 2002). The study included both primary and secondary data collection methods to obtain data, which has been used for analysis. The quantitative (questionnaire survey) methods described in this research were used in this study, which was justified by the main goals and research questions.

3.3 Objectives

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between marketing mix strategies and the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. Defining the

research objective is critical to responding effectively to the research questions (Saunders, et al., 2012).

Main Objective:

1. To critically review the literature of marketing strategies and profitability for stores.
2. To examine existing practices of marketing strategies on profitability.
3. To examine challenges to implement the marketing strategies.
4. To examine the benefits of implementing the marketing strategies.
5. To analyse the relationship between constructs of marketing mix 7ps strategies that impact the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

3.4 Research Question

According to Thabane et al. (2008), the efficiency of any study approach is based, first and foremost, on how well a researcher can convert a research problem into a research question. The goal of research questions is to identify, investigate, and interpret the phenomenon under study (Ploeg, 1999). This research attempts to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store with two objectives:

- 1) It explores in detail impact of marketing strategies on profitability.
- 2) It evaluates and develops a conceptual framework relating to the relationships between marketing strategies, their dimensions, and their consequences.

Based on marketing literature about the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store there have been few systematic studies on the topic. This study aims to explain the significance, the importance and the dimension of the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store from the managerial point of view. The following five research questions were formulated in order to achieve the two objectives stated above:

Main Questions:

1. What are the different marketing strategies at convenience stores that improve company profitability?

2. What are the challenges to implementing the marketing strategies at convenience stores?
3. What are the benefits of marketing strategy at convenience stores?
4. What is the relationship between marketing mix 7ps and profitability?
5. How does marketing strategy impact the profitability of convenience stores?

3.5 Research Design

This study was intended to investigate on the marketing mix 7ps strategies that impact the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. Therefore, to accomplish this research investigation, an appropriate research design was used. The choice of research approach is an important decision in the research design process because it defines how relevant information for a study will be gathered; yet, the research design process comprises several interrelated considerations. There are several frameworks for study designs, which can be categorised into three types: exploratory, descriptive, and causal (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018).

Therefore, descriptive research approaches were chosen, as they facilitate quantitative data processing. The researcher examined the connection between marketing mix strategies and convenience store profitability using a cross-sectional field survey.

In the cross-sectional field survey, both independent and dependent variables were evaluated simultaneously with a single questionnaire (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). Furthermore, the study was described as having an associational design because it aimed to determine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The sample was drawn from the target population using a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling. After collecting and analysing the data using mean, frequency, correlation, specifically Pearson's correlation, and regression analysis, the effect of independent factors on the dependent variable was determined (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018).

The author utilised descriptive research for brief analysis within a research design that consists of a single-method quantitative design that involves survey data collection.

This would help gather information through an online survey sent only to owners and managers of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

The author also adopted similar methodology based on similar study of this thesis by Hunelegn (2019). Hunelegn (2019) investigated the effect of marketing mix strategy on profitability in the case of teff milling industry sub-sectors in Addis Abeba, employing a cross-sectional descriptive survey design and a questionnaire with close-ended 5-point Likert scale questions that rate scales ranging from 1–strongly disagree to 5–strongly agree, and the SPSS programme was used to analyse the data for descriptive, Pearson correlations, and multiple regression analysis. The findings reveal that there was a high level of product and location strategy implementation. However, price and promotional methods were implemented on a smaller scale. The correlation and regression analyses showed that there is a strong link between a Teff milling company's profitability and its place and product strategies (Hunelegn, 2019).

Furthermore, with the aim of understanding the causes of these preferences and updating the current theoretical background, this research used a quantitative research method to examine the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom. The researcher also used a quantitative methodology and had the option of developing quantitative research questions (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018).

The objective of this study is to examine the variables that may or may not have caused certain outcomes by making use of the information that was acquired through the application of quantitative research methodologies (Saunders et al., 2012). For instance, one of the aims of the investigation that is contained within the thesis is to investigate which of the marketing mix variables are connected to the profitable performance of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

3.5.1 Research Philosophy

A research philosophy is a theory that guides the conduct of research based on assumptions regarding reality and the nature of understanding (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Positivism and interpretivism are the two major research philosophies. These philosophies describe two fundamentally different ways in which we as humanity attempt to comprehend the world around us: Positivism holds that reality is independent of us and that researchers may thus observe reality objectively. Reality is viewed as very subjective in interpretivism since it is moulded by our views (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Positivism emerged in the natural sciences and relies on scientific hypothesis testing and logical or mathematical proof derived from statistical analysis (Collis and Hussey, 2014). As a result, positivists tend to use large sample sizes and to generate exact, objective, and quantitative data (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

The positivist research philosophy underpins this research investigation. Moreover, the quantitative technique was used in this study's research methodology. The quantitative technique was used to conduct the research since it provides particular options for the researcher to acquire data in order to perform the research (Ho & Temperley 2013). The positivist concept aided the research in gathering data through questionnaires targeted primarily at convenience store owners and managers. Positivism aided the researcher in determining which aspects of marketing strategy influence the profitability of convenience stores.

The present study aims to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between marketing mix 7ps and profitability, as well as how marketing strategy impacts convenience store profitability. Furthermore, the topic covers the perspectives of convenience store owners and managers on their marketing methods. According to Bryman and Bell (2011), human behaviour is important in this strategy since it allows for the collection of knowledge.

3.5.2 Research Approach

Research findings can be concluded in two ways: an inductive approach and a deductive approach. In the inductive approach, researchers collect data and formulate their own theories. In the deductive approach, researchers draw conclusions based on existing theories. Deductive theory is a method to explain the association between research and theory. Then it is carried out with reference to the previous researcher's hypothesis and philosophies (Bryman and Bell, 2018).

The researcher used deductive reasoning to conduct the study and developed a theory based on how the profitability of convenience stores is affected by the marketing mix strategy. Researchers obtained a study to better understand the impact of the marketing mix strategy on the profitability of convenience stores (Dawes & Nenycz 2013).

This strategy is very helpful for the analysis of this particular issue as this research problem is founded on a literature review and is being applied to a specific circumstance. As shown in Figure 3.1, the process of deduction serves as the model for how this research was conducted. A deductive approach methodology was used in order to validate the hypotheses that were presented and to find the answers to the research questions.

Figure 3.1: The Deduction Study Process
Source: Bryman and Bell (2018).

Descriptive research is used when the information is available for conducting the research, whereas explorative research is used when information is less available (Sekaran and Bouge, 2009). These two approaches are used by the condition and situation. In this study, convenience stores provide an abundance of information regarding the marketing strategy of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

A careful analysis of the data from the quantitative method, which included a questionnaire, was done to determine the influence of the marketing mix 7Ps strategies. Since research is primarily concerned with developing particular standards or theories, the majority of professional studies fall under the category of derivative research. The deductions approach is the best strategy to use when conducting research on how marketing strategy affects profitability (2016 Chowdhury).

The deductive approach focuses more on verifying the theories that have already been formed (Cresswell, 2009). According to Saunders et al. (2012), there are six list to measures a deductive analytical thesis:

1. The presenting of an idea, hypothesis, or combination of hypotheses in order to develop a theory.
2. Examine current literature on the concept/hypothesis of developing a testable proposition.
3. Examine the assumptions and reasoning of the theory that developed them, then compare this assertion to the current hypothesis to see if it gives any progress.
4. Gathering adequate primary data to calculate and assess the concepts/variables using the appropriate tools.
5. If the study's findings contradict the idea/hypothesis, the assumption is erroneous, and the method must be discarded or revised.
6. If the data confirms the assertion, the hypothesis may be accepted as correct.

The deductive approach is the most appropriate for evaluating and refining such a hypothesis in light of recent developments in the United Kingdom convenience store industry, provided that the quantitative method methodology employed in this research is focused on already confirmed hypotheses. Moreover, as researcher used conceptual framework and research questions, therefore a deductive approach is more suitable for this study and two types of approach was used, descriptive and explorative research. Understanding the underlying causes of a marketing phenomenon is the goal of exploratory research, which aims to shed light on the research question (Malhotra et al., 2013). This study used an exploratory approach to better understand and measure the problem at hand.

3.5.3 Research Strategy

The method used to answer the research question and accomplish the objectives of the study is largely what determines a research project's effectiveness and success. Without a consistent framework, the accuracy of the collected data and the integrity of the analysis as a whole would fail. According to Saunders et al. (2012), a research strategy is a plan of action for achieving a goal. In addition, according to Malhotra et al., (2013), quantitative and qualitative methodologies are the two primary options available to researchers when selecting a research approach. In quantitative research, data is analysed through the application of statistics, whereas in qualitative research, a limited number of participants is used to gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomena being researched.

Moreover, the results of the literature review have revealed that the objective of this study is to investigate the influence that various marketing strategies have on the amount of money that convenience stores make. In addition to this, it investigates the connections that exist between marketing strategies, product differentiation, promotional variation, pricing variation, advertising variation, and customer service variation. The purpose of the study is to investigate and try to get an overall picture of the phenomenon that is being looked into. Therefore, this study used quantitative research as its foundation in order to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store. The quantitative research were applied with the aim of further discover managerial and entrepreneurs' responses to the marketing strategies.

Moreover, quantitative research has the advantage of allowing the researcher to gather and examine data, which is a significant benefit. An extensive investigation was conducted into the relationship that exists between a variable that is independent and one that is dependent. This is beneficial because it allows the researcher to approach the findings of the research in a more objective manner. Experiments can be designed to put hypotheses to the test through the use of quantitative research because of its capacity to measure data through the application of statistics. On the other hand, one of the drawbacks of conducting research through quantitative methods is that the context of the experiment or study is not taken into consideration. Quantitative research, in contrast to qualitative research, does not examine phenomena in the natural context in which they occur, nor does it discuss the significance of phenomena to various individuals (Bryman and Bell, 2018).

The study method is usually determined by four primary factors, including the research topic, the cost or budget needed for the analysis, the amount of time needed for the research, and the researcher's level of skill (Remenyi, 2002). The researcher used quantitative information obtained from business owners and managers of convenience stores specifically in city area of the United Kingdom. This approach is appropriate because the purposes of the research are to understand the impact of marketing mix strategies on the profitability of the convenience store industry in the United Kingdom. It is quite successful in gathering opinions from a large number of people and is also

very cost-effective to employ the quantitative survey method in deductive analysis (Saunders, et al., 2012).

3.5.4 Exploratory Fieldwork

In order to construct a questionnaire for the primary survey, it was necessary during this phase to conduct exploratory fieldwork. It is possible to develop items that are more reliable using multiple-item measures as opposed to single-item measures if one follows the approaches outlined by Churchill (1979) and DeVellis (2003) for the development of numerous measures for marketing constructs. Single-item measures are normally used. The quantitative theory proposed by Churchill completed the first phase (1979). The appropriate structures for creating measurement scales for constructs of marketing are illustrated in figure 3.2.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Churchill, 1979. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 3.2: Steps in measuring scale development. (Source: Churchill, 1979)

3.5.5 Domain of constructs

The objective of the research is to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability and dimensions of convenience stores. Therefore, the domain of constructs was applied step by step by creating and editing a list of sample items relevant to the concepts as per Churchill's (1979). Churchill (1979) asserts that the step following domain specification is the generation of sample items. Utilising all accessible sources (published research, journals, and insight). Following data collection, the measure must be refined through calculations of internal consistency (e.g., coefficient alpha). This step allows us to determine if the specified dimensions are discernible. After that, additional data will be collected, and reliability and validity will be evaluated. As the last step of Churchill's paradigm, the development of norms would give managers a way to measure how they respond to marketing strategies.

The research was guided by a set of definitions referred to as the domain of constructs. Finding the range of constructs to measure is the first step in creating precise measurement scales (Churchill, 1979). It's critical to build models that take into account all of the variables that could affect the study. Defining what will be measured is made possible by this step. This step is important as it allows for the definition of what will be measured: Marketing mix strategy, product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, people, place, process, physical evidence and profitability.

3.5.6 Items pool for a questionnaire

From the domain of constructs development we pool of items to measure each construct and its intended purpose of evaluation is exhibited in the **Table 3.1**. We use all the items for designing the questionnaire form.

Table 3.1: Initial pool of items

Marketing Mix Strategy	Reference
The Marketing Mix Strategy is necessary to increase sale.	Mas, N. and Nanik, S., 2017. Yuliantine, Indasah and Siyoto, 2018.
"Customers derive satisfaction as a result of the application of strategies to the marketing mix".	

<p>“Your organization achieved improved sales as a result of the application of strategies to the marketing mix”.</p>	
<p>“The application of strategies to placement gives room for product accessibility”.</p>	
<p>“The application of strategies to promotional activities gives room for product awareness”.</p>	
<p>Product Differentiation</p>	
<p>“Your organization products has good brand name, image and varieties of products in meeting customers’ satisfaction”.</p>	<p>Larimo et al., 2018.</p>
<p>“The brand name influences organizational sales”.</p>	
<p>“Your products meet customer’s requirements”.</p>	
<p>“Customers complain about the quality of your products”.</p>	
<p>Your product has good packaging and attractive.</p>	
<p>Promotion Variation</p>	
<p>“People know your products based on your promotional strategy”.</p>	<p>Larimo et al., 2018.</p>
<p>“Your organization applies advertising as one of the promotional strategy”.</p>	
<p>“Your organizational applies sales promotion as one of the promotional strategy”.</p>	
<p>“Your organizational applies personal selling as one of the promotional strategy”.</p>	
<p>“Your promotional strategy influences the rate of purchase positively”.</p>	
<p>Price Variation</p>	

“The pricing decisions allow for discounts”.	Dadzie et al., 2017.
“Prices of the products are appropriate”.	
“The pricing strategy gives room for large customer base”.	
“Applying strategies to the prices leads to increase in sales, thereby contributing to the achievement of objectives”.	
“The pricing decision allows for credit terms”.	
Place	
Your products get to the target customers.	Dadzie et al., 2017.
It is easy and convenience to reach the store.	
Transportation system is effective.	
People	
Your organization have well-trained staff.	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019.
Most of your staff have work experience in convenience store.	
Your employees practice great customer service.	
Your organization have great team leader.	
Your employees knowledgeable about all product in store.	
Process	
Your organization educate and support customers on an ongoing basis.	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019.
Are your customers being serviced excellently?	
Are your customers get all product information they need?	

The store offers speed deliver of service.	
The store opens and close at convenient time.	
Physical Evidence	
Your store are well organized.	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019.
Your store are clean and tidy environment.	
Your store are impressive with nice design and decoration.	
Profitability	
Sales is the base for measuring performance.	Bishnoi, T.R. and Devi, S., 2017
Profit margins is the base for measuring performance.	
Do you agree that marketing strategy improve your sales?	
Organization should allocate budget for marketing to improve sales.	

Source: The Researcher

3.5.7 Assessment of content adequacy

The content adequacy assessment came next. The preliminary scale items were created using the above-mentioned item-generation process. Questions on the instrument were used to gather data on each of the theoretical model's constituent parts or constructs. All of the items were rated using a Likert scale with seven different points. The responses varied from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

To attain greater accuracy it was essential to consider clarity, ease of completing, wording style, total time for responding, questionnaire design, and to validate if the study instrument measures all the constructs. We used the informal wording, easy to understand, clear and suitable with the subject of the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store.

According to DeVellis (2003), content validity refers to the extent to which a particular set of items accurately reflects a specific domain of information. In this investigation we examine the conceptual definitions of every construct based on our judgments and assessed it from the representation each item of the construct. In order to achieve greater level of validity, pilot study were conducted and feedback from the respondents were received as well as from our supervisor. Based on the pilot study result, the measurement tools were designed.

3.5.8 Time Horizon

Considering that the current study research is a thesis that partially satisfies the requirements for a DBA degree, the author had to make sure that the strategy chosen would be sufficient to solve the research topic and accomplish the associated goals within the proper timeframe. According to Saunders et al., there are two different kinds of horizons: longitudinal and cross-sectional. The only practical choice for the study is cross-sectional because longitudinal takes months to years to complete. The longitudinal horizon has not been used for this investigation because there are no time shifts that need to be observed.

This thesis used a cross-sectional method in order to investigate the impact of marketing strategy on convenience stores' profitability during the research process. This distinction is made by comparing the primary data gathered in the current research with those specified in the literature review.

3.5.9 Sample Size

The word "sample size" in research refers to the number of people chosen to represent a population (Bergin, 2018). A population is also defined as "the universe of units from which the sample is to be selected" by Bryman and Bell (2007, p. 182). The sample size refers to the overall number of participants in a study, and this figure is frequently divided into subgroups according to demographic factors like age, gender, and geography to ensure that the final sample accurately reflects the entire community (Bergin, 2018). One of the most crucial aspects of statistical analysis is choosing the proper sample size. In addition, before the questionnaires were distributed, some targets were set according to the following criteria:

1. The sample size should be at least 100.
2. Convenience stores or small grocery shop and the size of shop should be around 50 - 300 square meters.
3. The participant must be owner or manager level of convenience stores/small grocery shop.

The worksheet in Google Forms was used to create the online surveys, which were then distributed via email to managers and company owners of convenience shops in the United Kingdom. As an outcome, 290 copies of email questionnaires were gathered, with a total of 280 valid copies. Comprehensive findings will be covered in the following chapter; additionally, all other objectives were also met.

This study was careful and deliberate in selecting the appropriate sample size and specimen to conduct the research effectively (Hornibrook et al., 2015). All survey participants were volunteers with no benefits transfer due to limited resources. Online and email sampling were used in this research in order to achieve the above targets. Ibisworld (2018) data indicates that there were 46,262 convenience shops in the United Kingdom as of 2018. Based on the sample size calculator from Raosoft website, it shows that the recommended sample size is 269 with a confidence level of 90% and a margin of error of 5% (Raosoft, 2018). There are more complicated formulas, but generally, a correlation or regression analysis needs at least 100 individuals. Due to time constraints and participant availability, the present study employed a sample size of 280 respondents.

In terms of sampling methods, sampling methods are classified into two groups: First is random selection, where probability sampling enables the creation of reliable statistical inferences about the overall population. Second, non-probability sampling involves a non-random approach that relies on practicality or other factors, making it simple to collect data (Ho & Temperley 2013). This study used non-probability convenience sampling methods (Liu et al., 2014). The non-probability sampling method was used as it is an appropriate method to select the survey participants who answered the closed-ended questions. According to Malhotra et al. (2010), the non-probability method is a method which involves selecting people at non-random. It was

important to identify the suitability of the people who participated in this study to achieve the research's objectives.

3.5.10 Techniques of data analysis

Following the completion of the data collection phase, SPSS was used to perform preliminary descriptive statistics to provide a summary of the data. The descriptive statistics method was used to this research's advantage (De Pelsmacker et al., 2008). Following data capture, coding, and editing, various tests (missing data measurement, normality assessment, and Levene's test) are performed. To assess the study of hypotheses, the paths between the constructs were tested by correlation analysis and regression analysis with conceptual framework and theories. The findings were shown in tables and figures. Following that step is measurement of validity and hypotheses testing.

The method of conducting a survey by means of a questionnaire would be employed in gathering all the necessary quantitative data in order to examine the impact that marketing strategy has on the convenience store's profitability. It released details and assessments that could be used to make precise assumptions about the relationship between marketing strategies and profitability. These predictions could be made using the information that was provided. In the process of quantitative data analysis, three analyses would be carried out: the descriptive data, the factor as well as the inferential data analysis of regression. The findings of the research would be statistically analysed using SPSS to simplify examination of the suggested conceptual framework. It is carried out on a sample size of the target respondents in order to acquire precise data from people participating in the structured questionnaire (Malhotra et al. 2010). The following is an outline of the steps involved in the quantitative phase of the research:

1. Preparation of data: data editing and coding.
2. Using SPSS software to process the data and generate descriptive statistics.
3. Using SPSS to perform validity and reliability tests to ensure that all constructs in questionnaires accurately measure the research variables being investigated in this study without bias.
4. Performing multiple linear regression analyses with SPSS.

5. Applying the normality test in SPSS to make certain that the interpretation of the regression result is consistent with the hypothesis and the results of statistical tests.

3.5.11 Analysis and data interpretation

The quantitative data collection results were analysed, and responses that were specifically relevant to the research questions were also identified. Additionally, the constant comparative method was used to analyse the quantitative data. Access and ethical concerns pertaining to this research will be covered in the subsequent section of this article. In this section, the access and ethical issues that were taken into consideration are summarised.

3.5.12 Access issues and ethical considerations

The ethical question is extremely important with regard to marketing research in general. Due to the fact that primary research is being conducted as part of this investigation, it is absolutely necessary for the researcher to take into consideration the ethical concerns of each respondent. Research ethics is defined by Cooper and Schindler (2008) as "the goal of research ethics is to ensure that no one is harmed or suffers adverse consequences as a result of the research." Getting this done is as simple as ensuring that each participant gives their informed consent. During the quantitative phase, the questionnaire will be completely anonymous and will not contain any identifying features. However, applicants are required to submit personal data, including their names as well as the names of their companies. Before they give their consent, the participants will be informed about the confidentiality of their responses. The major principles outlined in the guidelines provided via the UWS's ethics committee was being taken into consideration in order to guarantee that this research adheres to the ethical knowledge of business research standard and does not raise any ethical concerns.

All of the respondents who take part in this research will be chosen in an unbiased manner, and no one will be excluded from the process due to differences in age, gender, ethnicity, culture, disability, language, or religion. After the experiment, each participant will be told that any and all data obtained will be given the same consideration for the intent of the research. It is also going to be provided that all respondents will have the same opportunity to gain benefit from their inclusion in the

study by providing them with a copy of the publication once the research has been completed.

Before continuing with the research process, informed consent from participants is obtained during the data collection phase to make sure that they are willing and ready to take part in the investigation being conducted. A written briefing of the study will be provided to respondents in this study before they are asked for their consent. This will allow the participants to understand both the purpose of the study as well as the procedure that will be followed during the study. Participants will be given the author's contact information in the event that they decide to withdraw from the study. The following section discussed about data collection.

3.6 Data collection

The research's important component of data collecting was classified under two categories: primary data and secondary data (Remenyi, 2002). This research acquired and interpreted numerical data for statistical research analysis using both primary and secondary data collection methods. The questionnaire provided primary data, while secondary data was obtained from existing research literature. To complete all material research, it is required to select information from important sources. Moreover, the researchers thoroughly analyses the data in order to distinguish between significant and needless information of data collected. This research employed quantitative methodology to collect the relevant data (Betancourt 2015).

3.6.1 Primary Data

The primary data for this study was obtained through survey methods questionnaire. Firstly, a questionnaire is cost-effective when the number of respondents is large. Secondly, it can help facilitate disclosure of sensitive issues, such as entrepreneurial success. Lastly, it enables participants to have a high degree of flexibility in completing questionnaires at their own time and pace.

The questionnaire was administered online using the website www.smartsurvey.co.uk and was distributed to owners or managers of convenience stores in the United Kingdom by email. A structured questionnaire with closed questions was created for this study. The questionnaires were disseminated throughout email and to managers

and business owners of convenience stores in four parts of the London area, such as east, west, north, and south London, and major cities in the United Kingdom. Finally, 290 copies of email questionnaires were collected and 280 copies were valid. There were 280 total copies of valid questionnaires. That all the other objectives were met as well; more specific outcomes would be addressed in a following chapter.

With a sample size of 280 participants, online surveys were deemed appropriate for quantitative research. To obtain precise information from individuals who participate in the survey, the questionnaire survey was used for a sample of the target population (Malhotra et al. 2010). Malhotra et al. (2010) stated that these process is practical as the collected data is continuous and has a low variability, and the analysis of the data can be properly understood with a moderate amount of effort.

The choice of a web-based questionnaire is to avoid high travel costs in collecting data. Closed-ended questions were chosen for questionnaires because this method can only be used to support quantitative research. The distribution of the questionnaire to the manager of a convenience store would help this study gain information regarding the topic.

The objective of this investigation is to know to what extent the relationship between marketing strategies and product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, advertising, and customer service lead to the profitability of convenience stores. A questionnaire was created using the most recent literature to obtain the answers for this study. It is important that the questionnaire instruction and scales of measurement are written clearly and simple to comprehend, and that the respondent answers the questionnaire correctly (Malhotra et al. 2010). The quantitative instruments consisted of nine parts: marketing mix strategies, product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, people, place, physical evidence, process, and profitability.

The study's empirical research component was a self-administered questionnaire. Several questioning techniques were used in the questionnaire. Categorical scales and dichotomous questions provided ease of understanding and flexibility. In order to guarantee the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, a preliminary test was conducted with five of the respondents who were selected to be a part of the sample.

Every single one of our construct measures was based on information gathered from past research and implemented. Throughout the study, numerous types of measuring scales were utilised. For the purpose of the demographic survey, respondents were compelled to provide details about themselves, including their ages, genders, and levels of education (Nayeem, 2012). The questionnaire used a seven-point Likert scale, ranging from “(1) strongly disagree to (7) strongly agree”, to offer qualities relevant to the data set of satisfactory answers (Boone, 2012). Because of that, the same scale was used to measure each of the instruments.

3.6.2 Secondary Data

Documents and record-keeping approaches was being employed to acquire secondary data. Furthermore, to make the study more consistent, extra information was acquired from numerous other findings of current written documents, also including online NGO sites, related articles, academic journals, journal database, academic eBooks, and official government publications (Andreti et al., 2013). These techniques allow the author to extract the relevant information from secondary sources or previous studies. To avoid collecting irrelevant information in collecting secondary data, reliable sources and up-to-date information would be considered.

3.6.3 Pilot Study

A pilot study, often known as a "feasibility" study, is a small-scale preliminary study conducted before such a large-scale type of research in order to evaluate the suitability of a full-scale project (Julia, 2022). The pilot study is an important part of the research process. These could help discover design issues and analyse the practicality, practicability, materials, timeframe, and cost of a particular project before doing primary research (Lowe, 2019). It involves choosing a small sample size and conducting the study on them. If the processes created by the researcher have any weaknesses, it may be able to save time and money by identifying issues and improving them. After the first group of questionnaire items had been developed, the purification stage was then carried out.

The pilot survey, which was conducted among managers and entrepreneurs of convenience stores in the United Kingdom, was designed to test the questionnaire for any gaps that may have been overlooked. Before the main study, A pilot research with

a small sample size of 10 surveys was conducted to assess the method's reliability and gather information for the main survey (Lackey and Wingate, 1997).

Furthermore, the researchers chose to create an online questionnaire through a pilot survey in order to take into consideration the present condition of COVID-19 and maintain social distance, as well as to resolve any potential difficulties during the survey. The pilot survey was distributed via text, WhatsApp, and email to friends who own or work in convenience stores in the United Kingdom. The questionnaire was created using Google Forms for fast delivery and feedback. Besides that, the questionnaire contains 42 questions about the relationships between the constructs of marketing mix 7ps strategies that impact convenience store profitability. The response was positive, however there were some issues of the instruments as some respondents could hardly fully understand the questions due to complicated sentences. Therefore, the measuring tools were changed to acquire better precise data and correct information for the data analyses, the complicated questions were changed into simple sentences.

This phase would be necessary for justifying the possibility of incorrect data collection and for selecting the most accurate technique for the main research. In this state, the survey methods that have been suggested are appropriate for the research (Lowe, 2019). The information for the survey will also be gathered from the pilot study. It is possible to achieve accurate results in the testing of the hypotheses by testing the data analysis method (Lowe, 2019).

By using pilot study, the researcher might find any ambiguities, uncertainties in the participant data, or problems with the task design (Arain et al. 2010). Researchers also get preliminary data by using data from pilot studies to predict the potential results of their proposed experiment.

The following terms require pilot studies to be conducted:

Verify first that participants are familiar with the terminology used in the survey. Second, make sure that no questions with strong emotional overtones have been posed because these can make respondents defensive and render their answers ineffective. In order to avoid influencing the respondent's response, avoid asking any

leading questions either. Finally, check that it will take an appropriate amount of time to finish the questionnaire (Bergin, 2018). It indicates that completing the questionnaire should not take too long.

According to the responses from the pilot study, this survey appeared appropriately designed, well organized, and easy to understand as well as easy to answer. **Figure 3.3** shows the tools employed for carrying out the pilot study.

A large black rectangular area covers the top half of the page, indicating redacted content. A white rectangular box with a red border is centered within this area, containing the following text:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Bergin, 2018. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 3.3: Pilot study tools

Source: (Bergin, 2018).

3.6.4 Main survey

This study aims to investigate the degree to which marketing strategies impact convenience store profitability through business owners' and managers' perceptions. Based on existing literature, a questionnaire has been developed to determine managers' opinions about how marketing strategies affect the profitability of convenience stores.

The survey questions and scales of measurement are well presented in order for respondents to understand them and provide correct information. The quantitative tools were divided into nine categories: marketing mix strategies, product differentiation, promotion variation, pricing variation, people, place, physical evidence, process and profitability.

All construct measurements were taken from previous studies' statements. The survey used mixed measurement scales in general. Primary data was collected and asked for demographic details including gender, age, and education level (Nayeem, 2012). To obtain a reasonable understanding of how the responses were distributed, a seven-

point Likert scale was employed that went from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" (Bagozzi, 1994). As a result, this scale was used to measure all of the instruments.

3.7 Summary

In this chapter, both the conceptual framework and the research design which were employed to evaluate the hypotheses are discussed. Numerical data was collected using quantitative approaches, and the hypothesis was statistically tested. The marketing strategy measurement scales were made based on research that had already been done. They were used to figure out how each marketing strategy construct affected the profits of convenience stores.

In conclusion, this chapter determined the questionnaires, analysis methodology, and research strategy. The quality of the questionnaires was improved through conducting a pilot test prior to the distribution of questionnaires. The next chapter will go over the detailed results and discussion. The next chapter would start with analyses the data through (SPSS) statistical package for social science system. 280 valid survey participants provided the information for the study. Next method was analysis the demography and other relevant issues from respondents. This research analysis continue with Reliability test, data preparation, assessment of normality, Levene's test, regression analysis, correlation analysis. The investigation continue with the measurement of validity Hypotheses testing and final is conclusion. Next chapter will discuss about result and discussion.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Chapter overview

The analysis and findings section presents the important data that was collected during the process of research. This chapter's primary objective was to use the data collected to respond to the research questions that were proposed in chapter one. This chapter also explains the research findings and engages in a discussion about them. The data acquired, which included respondents' opinions on how marketing methods affect the profitability of convenience stores, among other significant data. All collected data was statistically analysed by using SPSS. The tables, charts, and graphs from SPSS were used to present and illustrate the detailed findings and analyses that were conducted. Sections 4.1 and 4.2 are the introduction and overview of the study, followed by section 4.3, which is the demographic data analysis. The reliability test is in section 4.4, and next is the data preparation in section 4.5. The analysis continues with the assessment of normality in section 4.6 and Levene's test in section 4.7. Next in section 4.8 is correlation analysis and in section 4.9 is regression analysis. The analysis continues with the measurement of validity in section 4.10. Hypotheses testing is in section 4.11 and a summary of the chapter is in section 4.12.

4.2 Overview of study

This research project investigated the concept of the impact of marketing strategies on the profitability of convenience stores and its dimensions. The study also identified the marketing mix 7Ps strategies, which include the seven factors (product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, process and physical evidence) most likely to have a substantial impact on profitability. Therefore, this chapter presented the empirical findings and provided an explanation of the results based on the research questions posed in the chapter one and seven hypotheses that were tested.

The next stage involved processing and evaluating the raw data, followed by an analysis of the findings. This was done after the quantitative component of primary research was finished and all the data required to begin addressing the research question and achieve the research objectives had been obtained. This chapter covers

in detail the methods used by the author to convert the raw data collected from the quantitative (Online Questionnaire) data into valuable information that the reader and, theoretically, researchers and practitioners can understand (Saunders, et al., 2009). A sequential approach consisting of quantitative studies was explored and following the seven hypotheses as below:

- H1:** The product differentiation will positively impact the profitability.
- H2:** The Promotion variation will positively impact the profitability.
- H3:** The Price variation will positively impact the profitability.
- H4:** The Place will positively impact the profitability.
- H5:** The People will positively impact the profitability.
- H6:** The Process will positively impact the profitability.
- H7:** The Physical evidence will positively impact the profitability.

This research started the analysis with demographic data analysis, which is discussed in the next section.

4.3 Demographic data analysis

This analysis is necessary in this survey to understand the demographic data of the respondents. This is because this data can be used to better understand and study the attitudes and behaviours of the target audience regarding marketing strategies and profitability. In addition to this, we were able to draw conclusions based on the supporting data. Aside from that, age, level of education, and occupations would be looked at in relation to sample populations and genders. Because of this, we were able to obtain a comparison and result that was more all-encompassing. The data for this study was gathered through online surveys performed in the United Kingdom. There was a section at the beginning of the survey that requested respondents to supply demographic information. Table 4.1 presents the statistical findings from the demographic section.

Source: The researcher

	Sample size (N)	N	%
Gender	Female	81	28.9%
	Male	199	71.1%
	Total	280	100%
Age	20 less than 30	48	17.1%
	30 less than 40	66	23.6%
	40 less than 50.	116	41.4%

	50 or above	50	17.9%
	Total	280	100%
Education Level	High school	75	26.8%
	Undergraduate	182	65.0%
	postgraduate and above	23	8.2%
	Total	280	100%
Occupations	Top executive or manager	113	40.4%
	Owner of a company	144	51.4%
	Office/clerical staffs	9	3.2%
	Worker	11	3.9%
	Others	3	1.1%
	Total	280	100%

Table 4.1: Demographic data analysis (N=280)

4.3.1 Gender

The participants were required to specify their gender in order to ensure that both gender representations were included in the study, and the following responses were obtained. As shown in Figure 4.1, there are 81 female (28.9 percent) respondents, while the majority of respondents are 199 male (71.1 percent). According to the findings of this study, men dominate management levels in the convenience store industry. The proportion of gender participation was acceptable for this study because the author wanted to gather information from convenience store owners or managers regardless of gender. This indicates that gender was not a factor in convenience store ownership or employment. Therefore, this study was not influenced by gender imbalances.

In the convenience store industry, there were gender imbalances. According to Gaele and Gill (2022), only 10% of management teams in the retail sector are female, while 90% are male. This is because, perhaps unsurprisingly, childcare and the challenges that come with it. A great many of female employees work part-time due to childcare issues, which limits their promotion prospects because they can only work a limited

number of hours and a manager can't really train someone to management level in that time frame (Gaelle and Gill, 2022). Furthermore, according to Maria (2022), the convenience store industry is largely led by men, and trade associations are still heavily dominated by men. For example, The Association of Convenience Stores has 16 male members on its board versus four female members, whereas Dairy UK's twelve-member board had only one woman (Maria 2022).

Figure 4.1: Respondents' Gender

4.3.2 Age

As shown by Table 4.1, the most of responders are people aged 40 to 50 which accounted 41.4 % (116 respondents). 23.6 % of the respondents were adult who aged 30 less than 40 (66 respondents). Minority of the respondents were age between 20 less than 30, which accounted for 17.1% (48 respondents) respectively. The procedure that was used to collect the data may provide an explanation for the uneven distribution of the respondents' ages. Both random sampling at predetermined locations and random sampling conducted online were used. The distribution were through the company's email who operate convenience stores business in the United Kingdom.

4.3.3 Education Level

Figure 4.2: Respondents' Education Level

As demonstrated in the Figure 4.2, the percent of the participants (65.0%) are graduated at the university (182 participants) from undergraduate, high school level were 26.8% (75 participants). While 8.2% (23 participants) were educated at postgraduate and above.

4.3.4 Occupations

Figure 4.3: Respondents' Occupations

In **Figure 4.3**, it shown that 51.4% of them (144 respondents) were owner of a company and 40.4% of them (113 respondents) top executive or manager. Because of the time constraints, the pool that was collected was satisfactory.

4.3.5 Marketing strategies in the convenience store

In this study, all respondents were given questions “Do you use marketing strategy in your business?” to assess the application of marketing strategy at convenience stores. **Table 4.2** demonstrates that 280 (100.0%) respondents stated that they use marketing strategy in their business.

Sample size (N)	N	%
Do you use marketing strategy in your business?		
Yes	280	100
No	0	0
Total	280	100

Table 4.2: Marketing strategies in the convenience stores

4.4 Reliability test

In this analysis, the reliability test was used. The reliability test was an important analytical method for estimating the dependability and quality of multiple-item components (Denis 2018). When the Alpha value was greater than 0.7, it was accepted as normal and preferable when the value was greater than 0.8. Cronbach's α (alpha) is an internal consistency coefficient in statistical data (Denis 2018). These are widely used to determine a psychometric test's reliability for a group of respondents.

Reliability Statistics of Constructs		
Variable	Number of variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Marketing Mix Strategy	5	.818
Product differentiation	5	.939
Promotion variation	5	.969
Price variation	5	.955
Place	3	.819
People	5	.926
Process	5	.852

Physical evidence	3	.921
Profitability	4	.872
Total variable	40	

Table 4.3: Reliability Statistics of Constructs

As seen in the Table 4.3, the reliability test was performed on each and every one of the items. The reliability test is necessary for this investigation because, based on the results, we will be able to determine the accuracy and precision of the multiple-item component's reliability and quality (Denis 2018). Thus, 40 variables were applied in this analysis and it showed all variable are highly reliable since Cronbach's alpha coefficient was >0.8 . After reliability test, this research analysis proceed with data preparation section.

4.5 Data preparation

4.5.1 Editing and data coding

For editing data and coding in this study, the data have to be measured and codify by SPSS software (Denis 2018). The first step is to download the data from the online surveys. It is necessary to codify and edit the information once it has been gathered. The codes that were used in the data analysis are shown in Tables 4.4 and 4.5.

Code	Name of the construct
MKM	Marketing Mix Strategy
PROD	Product differentiation
PROM	Promotion variation
PRIC	Price variation
PLAC	Place
PP	People
PROC	Process
PHY	Physical evidence
PROF	Profitability

Table 4.4: Codes for statistical analysis

Code	Meanings
MKM_TOTAL	Compute variable of Marketing Mix Strategy
PROD_TOTAL	Compute variable of Product differentiation

PROM_TOTAL	Compute variable of Promotion variation
PRIC_TOTAL	Compute variable of Price variation
PLAC_TOTAL	Compute variable of Place
PP_TOTAL	Compute variable of People
PROC_TOTAL	Compute variable of Process
PHY_TOTAL	Compute variable of Physical evidence
PROF_TOTAL	Compute variable of Profitability

Table 4.5: Codes for statistical analysis compute variable
Source: The researcher

4.5.2 Screening of data

Data screening is important in this research, to obtain an accurate analysis the data should be accurate (Denis 2018). Data cleaning and screening are performed to ensure that the data is free of errors and ready for statistical analysis (Denis 2018). Furthermore, it is important to conduct an early analysis of the information to ensure that the data to be shown is reliable, correct, and valid (Malhorta, 1999). According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), screening data before analysis can help in the finding of missing data or outliers in an analysis, as well as the adjustment of acquired data to the hypothesis prior to the multivariate procedure and the assessment of how to manage the problem. Therefore, in this research the data was analysed by using SPSS.

4.5.3 Analysis of missing data

Missing data, described by Hair et al. (2006) as missing values in data that are predicted to occur throughout much research, is one of the most severe problems for analysis of data. The missing data analysis produced “.00” values for all constructs as shown in (Table 4.6), indicating that there were no missing data to investigate further. Respondents found the questionnaire to be straightforward, clear, and well-written. Participants were required to complete all sections of the online survey in order to move on to the next section, which was designed to ensure that no information was left out. As a result of maintaining data confidentiality and avoiding contentious questions, this study was able to collect all of the information it needed.

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Missing	
				Count	Percent
PROD.1	280	4.44	1.850	0	.0
PROD.2	280	4.35	1.549	0	.0
PROD.3	280	3.76	1.593	0	.0
PROD.4	280	4.35	1.886	0	.0
PROD.5	280	3.85	1.730	0	.0
PROM.1	280	4.27	1.833	0	.0
PROM.2	280	5.02	1.823	0	.0
PROM.3	280	4.84	1.513	0	.0
PROM.4	280	4.43	1.553	0	.0
PROM.5	280	4.76	1.739	0	.0
PRIC.1	280	4.77	1.875	0	.0
PRIC.2	280	3.78	2.209	0	.0
PRIC.3	280	4.51	1.498	0	.0
PRIC.4	280	4.02	1.419	0	.0
PRIC.5	280	4.01	1.631	0	.0
PLAC.1	280	3.60	1.446	0	.0
PLAC.2	280	4.35	1.791	0	.0
PLAC.3	280	4.43	1.382	0	.0
PP.1	280	5.18	1.343	0	.0
PP.2	280	5.17	1.401	0	.0
PP.3	280	4.84	1.400	0	.0
PP.4	280	3.53	2.142	0	.0
PP.5	280	5.09	1.377	0	.0
PROC.1	280	4.93	1.843	0	.0
PROC.2	280	5.84	1.343	0	.0
PROC.3	280	5.50	1.381	0	.0
PROC.4	280	4.40	1.771	0	.0
PROC.5	280	3.37	2.068	0	.0
PHY.1	280	3.20	1.784	0	.0
PHY.2	280	3.77	1.536	0	.0
PHY.3	280	3.69	1.548	0	.0
PROF.1	280	3.11	1.901	0	.0
PROF.2	280	2.70	1.894	0	.0
PROF.3	280	4.95	1.674	0	.0
PROF.4	280	5.65	1.005	0	.0
PROF.5	280	6.01	1.061	0	.0
PROF.6	280	6.13	1.158	0	.0
PROF.7	280	5.02	1.631	0	.0
D1	280	1.71	.454	0	.0
D2	280	2.60	.971	0	.0
D3	280	1.81	.563	0	.0
D4	280	1.74	.790	0	.0

Table 4.6: Missing data examination at item-level

Source: The researcher

4.6 Assessment of normality

4.6.1 Testing the normality assumption

The normality assumption test is the initial presumption in a multivariate analysis, and it is essential for assessing hypotheses (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). In this investigation, a normality test was performed to check that the data did not contradict the initial normality assumption. The normal probability plot is used to examine the extent to which the data is normally distributed (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The findings of the Q-Q plots (Figure 4.4) reveal that each of the factors was concentrated all around the diagonal up straight line, indicating that the data has a normal distribution.

Figure 4.4: Normal probability Q-Q plots

Source: The researcher

4.7 Correlation analysis

The correlation of marketing mix 7Ps constructs was verified using Pearson's correlation analysis. Correlation analysis is a method for analysing the level and direction of correlations between interval/ratio variables and/or ordinal variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient is a way to figure out how closely two things are linked (Bryman 2011).

According to Saunders et al. (2003), a strong positive relationship exists between the variables when the correlation coefficient is very near to +1. There is a considerable negative association when it is extremely near to -1. There is little or no association if it is near to 0. Refer to (**APPENDIX 4.2**), this test determined that all variables are closer to +1, This suggests that every of the independent variables are strongly related

to one another. Furthermore, with the $0.000 < 0.05$ of Sig. (2-tailed). It is possible to determine that the variables indicated above have strong correlation.

4.7.1 (Product Differentiation→Profitability)

In Table 4.7, all the variables from product differentiation were computed into a target variable and labelled as "PROD_TOTAL." The five variables from profitability were computed into the target variable named "PROF_TOTAL". By computing the group of variables, the correlations between product differentiation and profitability were able to be made. Based on the Person Correlation, it demonstrates the significant link between "product differentiation and profitability" since the coefficient is (0.798) close to 1 and the Sig. (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$.

Correlations		PROD_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PROD_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.798**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.798**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.7: Correlation analysis of product differentiation and profitability.
Source: The Researcher

4.7.2 (Promotion Variation→Profitability)

In **Table 4.8**, based on the Person Correlation, it proves the strong positive relationship between **Promotion Variation** to **Profitability** variables because the coefficient is (0.782) close to 1 with the $0.000 < 0.05$ of Sig. (2-tailed). It is possible to determine that the variables indicated above have strong correlation.

Correlations		
	PROM_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL

PROM_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.782**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.782**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.8: Correlation analysis of Promotion Variation and Profitability.
Source: The Researcher

4.7.3 (Price Variation → Profitability)

In **Table 4.9**, based on the Person Correlation, it proves the significantly positive relationship between **Price Variation** and **Profitability** variables because the coefficient is (0.917) close to 1 with the $0.000 < 0.05$ of Sig. (2-tailed). It is possible to determine that the factors indicated above have strong correlation.

Correlations			
		PRIC_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PRIC_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.917**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.917**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.9: Correlation analysis of Price Variation and Profitability.
Source: The Researcher

4.7.4 (Place → Profitability)

In **Table 4.10**, based on the Person Correlation, it proves the strong positive relationship between **Place** and **Profitability** variables because the coefficient is (0.876) close to 1 and p-value less than 0.05.

Correlations			
		PLAC_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PLAC_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.876**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.876**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.10: Correlation analysis of Place and Profitability.
Source: The Researcher

4.7.5 (People→ Profitability)

In **Table 4.11**, based on the Person Correlation, It demonstrates a significant positive link between People and Profitability variables since the coefficient is (0.712) close to 1 and p-value less than 0.05.

Correlations			
		PP_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PP_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.712**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.11: Correlation analysis of People and Profitability.
Source: The Researcher

4.7.6 (Process→ Profitability)

In **Table 4.12**, based on the Person Correlation, it proves the strong positive relationship between **Process** and **Profitability** variables since the coefficient is (0.703) close to 1 and p-value less than 0.05.

Correlations			
		PROC_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PROC_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.703**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.703**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.12: Correlation analysis of Process and Profitability. Source: The Researcher

4.7.7 (Physical Evidence→ Profitability)

In **Table 4.13**, based on the Person Correlation, It demonstrates a significant positive link between Physical Evidence and Profitability variables since the coefficient is (0.913) near to 1 and the p-value is less than 0.05.

Correlations			
		PHY_TOTAL	PROF_TOTAL
PHY_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.913**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	280	280
PROF_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.913**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.13: Correlation analysis of Physical Evidence and Profitability. Source: The Researcher

4.8 Analysis of Descriptive statistics

The goal of analysis-descriptive is to give a constructive way to summarise or describe data points in such a way that it is possible for patterns to emerge that satisfy each as well as every data characteristic. In the procedure of carrying out statistical data analysis, this step is among the most crucial ones.

As shown in **Table 4.14**, Process (PROC_TOTAL) had the highest mean (4.81) compare to People (PP_TOTAL) (4.76) and the lowest is Physical evidence (PHY_TOTAL) (3.55). In the case of convenience store study, it could be explain that most respondents agree that the element of marketing 7ps mix strategies for example People, Process, and Physical evidence impact on profitability.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
PROD_TOTAL	280	1	7	4.15	1.540
PROM_TOTAL	280	1	7	4.66	1.369
PRIC_TOTAL	280	1	6	4.15	1.315
PLAC_TOTAL	280	2	6	4.43	.905
PP_TOTAL	280	2	6	4.76	1.352
PROC_TOTAL	280	2	7	4.81	1.350
PHY_TOTAL	280	2	6	3.55	1.512
PROF_TOTAL	280	2	7	4.33	.957
Valid (listwise)	N 280				

Table 4.14: Descriptive statistics between Product differentiation, Promotion variation, Price variation, Place, People, Process and Physical evidence.

4.9 Analysis of Regression and ANOVA

A regression and an ANOVA analysis were performed to better comprehend the contribution of these variables marketing mix strategies to profitability (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The regression analysis statistical approach is used to find the connections that exist among the variables being analysed (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The objective of analysis of regression is to explain why the average value of the dependent variable varies as a result of changes in only one of the independent

variables, whereas the other independent variables stay constant (Bryman and Bell, 2011). On the other hand, an ANOVA is a statistical model that is used to estimate a consistent result based on one or more classification predictor variables. This can be done by using a combination of both models. A statistical method known as the variance analysis or ANOVA, can identify significant variations with the means of two or more categories (Freund et al., 2006). Determine if a regression model was acceptable for the variables and whether independent variables statistically substantially impact the dependent variable using the F-ratio in the ANOVA table (Freund et al., 2006). In following this section, we will discuss about the finding.

4.9.1 (Product Differentiation→Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.15 and 4.16**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.491$, $F = 268.636$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that "Product Differentiation" and "Profitability" were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 49.1% of the variability, Product Differentiation. Table 4.17 provides an explanation of the standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contributions and levels of predictive power of each variable. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.701 ^a	.491	.490	.683
a. Predictors: (Constant), PROD_TOTAL				

Table 4.15: Model summary results showing the relationship between Product Differentiation and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	125.477	1	125.477	268.636	<.001 ^b
	Residual	129.851	278	.467		
	Total	255.328	279			
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PROD_TOTAL						

Table 4.16: ANOVA results of Product Differentiation and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.524	.118		21.468	<.001
	PROD_TOTAL	.435	.027	.701	16.390	<.001
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						

Table 4.17: Coefficients results of Product Differentiation and Profitability.

4.9.2 (Promotion variation → Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.18 and 4.19**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.415$, $F = 197.137$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that "Promotion variation" and "Profitability" were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 41.5% of the variability, Promotion variation. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.20. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.644 ^a	.415	.413	.733

a. Predictors: (Constant), PROM_TOTAL

Table 4.18: Model summary results showing the relationship between Promotion variation and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	105.937	1	105.937	197.137	<.001 ^b
	Residual	149.391	278	.537		
	Total	255.328	279			

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL
b. Predictors: (Constant), PROM_TOTAL

Table 4.19: ANOVA results of Promotion variation and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.233	.156		14.337	<.001
	PROM_TOTAL	.450	.032	.644	14.041	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL

Table 4.20: Coefficients results of Promotion variation and Profitability.

4.9.3 (Price Variation→Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.21 and 4.22**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.665$, $F = 552.120$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that "Price Variation" and "Profitability" were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as

66.5% of the variability, Price. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.23. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.816 ^a	.665	.664	.555

a. Predictors: (Constant), PRIC_TOTAL

Table 4.21: Model summary results showing the relationship between Price Variation and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	169.821	1	169.821	552.120	<.001 ^b
	Residual	85.507	278	.308		
	Total	255.328	279			

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL
b. Predictors: (Constant), PRIC_TOTAL

Table 4.22: ANOVA results of Price Variation and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.867	.110		16.966	<.001
	PRIC_TOTAL	.593	.025	.816	23.497	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL

Table 4.23: Coefficients results of Price Variation and Profitability.

4.9.4 (Place→Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.24 and 4.25**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.349$, $F = 148.724$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that “Place” and “Profitability” were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 34.9% of the variability, Place. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.26. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.590 ^a	.349	.346	.774
a. Predictors: (Constant), PLAC_TOTAL				

Table 4.24: Model summary results showing the relationship between Place and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	88.988	1	88.988	148.724	<.001 ^b
	Residual	166.340	278	.598		
	Total	255.328	279			
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PLAC_TOTAL						

Table 4.25: ANOVA results of Place and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.565	.232		6.758	<.001

	PLAC_TOT AL	.624	.051	.590	12.195	<.001
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						

Table 4.26: Coefficients results of Place and Profitability.

4.9.5 (People→Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.27 and 4.28**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.419$, $F = 200.300$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that “People” and “Profitability” were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 41.9% of the variability, People. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.29. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.647 ^a	.419	.417	.731
a. Predictors: (Constant), PP_TOTAL				

Table 4:27 Model summary results showing the relationship between People and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	106.925	1	106.925	200.300	<.001 ^b
	Residual	148.403	278	.534		
	Total	255.328	279			
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PP_TOTAL						

Table 4.28: ANOVA results of People and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.152	.160		13.441	<.001
	PP_TOTAL	.458	.032	.647	14.153	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL

Table 4.29: Coefficients results of People and Profitability.

4.9.6 (Process → Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.30 and 4.31**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.413$, $F = 195.438$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that "Process" and "Profitability" were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 41.3% of the variability, Process. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.32. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.642 ^a	.413	.411	.734

a. Predictors: (Constant), PROC_TOTAL

Table 4.30: Model summary results showing the relationship between Process and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	105.401	1	105.401	195.438	<.001 ^b
	Residual	149.927	278	.539		
	Total	255.328	279			
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PROC_TOTAL						

Table 4.31: ANOVA results of Process and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.143	.163		13.179	<.001
	PROC_TOTAL	.455	.033	.642	13.980	<.001
a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL						

Table 4.32: Coefficients results of Process and Profitability.

4.9.7 (Physical evidence→Profitability)

In this study, Enter method was used. Refer to **Table 4.33 and 4.34**, the model was significant, $R^2 = 0.689$, $F = 175.858$, $p < 0.05$. The p-values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p-values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Shrestha, 2019). It was clarified that "Physical evidence" and "Profitability" were significantly positively correlated. The independent variables explain the R Square as 68.9% of the variability, Physical evidence. The standardised and unstandardized (B) regression coefficients, along with the respective contribution and predictive ability of each variable, are presented in Table 4.35. The data is considered statistically significant if the t-value is 2 or above.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.8300 ^a	.6891	.6881	.535

a. Predictors: (Constant), PHY_TOTAL

Table 4.33: Model summary results showing the relationship between Physical Evidence and Profitability.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	175.858	1	175.858	615.182	<.001 ^b
	Residual	79.470	278	.286		
	Total	255.328	279			

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL

b. Predictors: (Constant), PHY_TOTAL

Table 4.34: ANOVA results of Physical Evidence and Profitability.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.467	.082		30.204	<.001
	PHY_TOTAL	.525	.021	.830	24.803	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: PROF_TOTAL

Table 4.35: Coefficients results of Physical Evidence and Profitability.

4.10 Measurement of validity

The homogeneity of the constructs is referred to as convergence validity (Hair et al., 2006). The validity of the convergent items in relation to their internal consistency validity was determined by defining whether or not the element concentration of items was greater than 0.5 and statistical significance. This was done in order to define the convergent items validity (Hair et al., 2006). Convergent validity are being considered sufficient if the (AVE) average variance extracted is at least 0.5. The AVE can be seen to range anywhere from 0.576 to 0.911 in Table 4.36.

	PROD_ TOTAL	PROM_ T OTAL	PRIC_ T OTAL	PLAC_ TOTAL	PP_ T OTAL	PROC_ TOTAL	PHY_ T OTAL	PROF_ TOTAL
PROD_ TOTAL	1							
PROM_ TOTAL	.911**	1						
PRIC_ TOTAL	.829**	.847**	1					
PLAC_ TOTAL	.611**	.576**	.696**	1				
PP_ TOTAL	.807**	.747**	.819**	.673**	1			
PROC_ TOTAL	.738**	.671**	.782**	.635**	.942**	1		
PHY_ TOTAL	.790**	.696**	.868**	.668**	.730**	.748**	1	
PROF_ TOTAL	.701**	.644**	.816**	.590**	.647**	.642**	.830**	1

** . At the 0.01 level (2-tailed) showed that Correlation is significant

Table 4.36: Inter-construct correlation for basic model

4.11 Hypotheses testing

The results of the tests performed on the causal paths are presented in Table 4.37. The outcome of the hypotheses for a total of eight hypotheses tested include these results of p-value, standard error and. standardised path coefficients (β). In the context

of product differentiation (PROD) and profitability (PROF), the standardised regression path is statistically significant ($p = 0.847$, $t = 16.390$). The H1 protocol is fully supported as a result. Using the same standards, we can conclude that the hypotheses H2, H3, H4, H5, H6, H7, and H8 are all strongly accepted by the positive significant relationships between Promotion variation (PROM) , Price variation (PRIC), Place (PLAC), People (PP), Process (PROC), and Physical evidence (PHY) to Profitability (PROF).

The relationship between the constructs was discovered after hypothesis testing. Figure 4.5 depicts the connection among the marketing mix strategies as well as its dimensions and the main outcomes.

				Beta	Std.Error	t	p	Lable
H1	PROD	→	PROF	.701	.027	16.390	***	Supported
H2	PROM	→	PROF	.644	.032	14.041	***	Supported
H3	PRIC	→	PROF	.816	.025	23.497	***	Supported
H4	PLAC	→	PROF	.590	.051	12.195	***	Supported
H5	PP	→	PROF	.647	.032	14.153	***	Supported
H6	PROC	→	PROF	.642	.033	13.980	***	Supported
H7	PHY	→	PROF	.830	.021	24.803	***	Supported

Table 4.37: Results of hypothesis testing

P=Level of significance.

*** $p < 0.001$

Std.Error= Standard error;

Beta=Standardised regression coefficient;

Notes: Path=Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable:

t=t-value;

Figure 4.5: Validated conceptual framework. Source: The Researcher

Findings from this study point out that Product differentiation, Promotion variation, Price variation, People, Place, Physical evidence, and Process is linked to Profitability. This research findings showed that every dimension is important for convenience store companies to increase their profitability.

4.12 Summary

To further understand the characteristics of the sample, the collected data was analysed, as well as a descriptive study of the demography. No missing data were found when the data was inspected for it in this segment. The data accuracy was evaluated using normality tests. To investigate the relationships between (PROD), (PROM), (PRIC), (PLAC), (PP), (PROC), (PHY), and (PROF), the Correlation and Regression analyses were used. The data were tested for validity at this time, and the results showed that the data had adequate convergent validity and statistical significance. Finally, based on the correlation and regression analysis, the seven presented hypotheses are tested at this point. Overall, findings indicate that all hypotheses are accepted. The explanation of findings and contributions is discussed in the following chapter.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

5.1 Chapter overview

This chapter's objective is to discuss the findings and contributions. The findings in this study are related to the introduction chapter by the hypotheses posed, research questions and the reviewed of literature. Furthermore, it examines and discusses the significance of these research results in the light of what was previously known about the research topic under consideration. In Section 5.2 chapter begins with the discussion of the results, followed by the major findings in Section 5.2.1, and the next is the result of "Product differentiation" in Section 5.2.2. The discussion continues with the result of "Promotion variation", which is in section 5.5.3. The result of "price variation" is in section 5.2.4. Next, the result of "Place" is in section 5.2.5 and the result of "People" is in section 5.2.6. The discussion continues with the result of "Process" which is in section 5.2.7. Then, the result of "Physical evidence" is in section 5.2.8 and section 5.3 is a summary of the chapter.

5.2 Discussion of the Results

The empirical results were presented in this chapter, along with an explanation of the findings derived from the seven tested hypotheses. The discussion of results starts with the major finding from the data analysis and is followed by the seven results from each hypothesis. The empirical findings were verified and confirmed, and the results were compared with the findings in Chapter 2.

5.2.1 Major findings

This research's objective was to examine the impact of the marketing mix's 7Ps strategies and its impact on convenience store's profitability in the UK context. This study assessed marketing mix strategies based on their dimensions and their impact on profitability. The research aim is to specifically investigate the impact of mix strategies factors (which includes product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, people place, physical evidence, and process) on company's profitability.

The results show that the company's profitability appears to be significantly impacted by the marketing mix strategies. Research findings point out that product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, people, place, physical evidence,

and process are linked to profitability. Moreover, it shows that price and product differentiation are the most important aspects when business owners or managers apply marketing mix strategies. This research found that customers were highly satisfied with the several varieties of products to choose from in convenience stores (50.8%). It means the majority of business owners agree to offer several varieties of products in their store to satisfy a customer. In this research, 42.9% of respondents agree that their company achieved maximum profitability due to product strategy for the past 3 years. Moreover, the result of this study revealed that 41% of the respondents agree that "Provide products with different price ranges" and 38% agree that "The company uses pricing skills and systems to respond quickly to market changes." In addition, 35% agree that "The price of the products is reasonable." The finding also revealed that 47% of the respondents agreed that "Company achieved maximum profitability due to pricing strategy." This indicates that convenience stores in the United Kingdom compete primarily on price and product differentiation. The results of the correlation between each element of the marketing mix (the 7 Ps) and profitability are discussed in the next section.

5.2.2 Product differentiation

The results of this study demonstrated a substantial positive correlation between variables related to product differentiation and profitability performance, with a coefficient is (0.798) close to 1 and the Sig. (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$. In addition, it was shown that "Product differentiation" and "Profitability" have a strong linear correlation. The independent variables explain the R Square as 49.1% of the dependent variable of the variability, Product Differentiation.

Table 5.1 demonstrates that consumers have a very positive opinion of the product's quality (54.1 percent). This could be the case due to the fact that quality is what determines a product's ability to fulfil the needs of the consumer, whether those needs are expressed or expected. Consumer demands come first, followed by quality that exceeds consumer expectations, and finally by consumer loyalty (Kotler et al., 2008). In addition, it was also found that customers were highly satisfied with the several varieties of products to choose from in convenience stores (50.8%). It means majorities of business owners agree to offer several varieties of products in their store

to satisfy a customer. In this research 42.9% respondents agree that their company achieved maximum profitability due to product strategy for the past 3 years.

	Your company offers several varieties of products to choose. (PROD.1)	Your company offers high quality Products (PROD.2)	Your products meet customer's requirements. (PROD.3)	Your company gives room for product warranty (PROD.4)	Your product has good packaging and attractive. (PROD.5)	In the last 3 years your company achieved maximum profitability due to product strategy (PROF.1)
Strongly disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	1.2%	1.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Somewhat disagree	0.0%	4.6%	3.2%	24.6%	2.0%	2.0%
Neutral	3.8%	0.6%	25.0%	8.1%	8.2%	11.0%
Somewhat agree	20.4%	23.9%	26.8%	21.7%	25.7%	25.0%
Agree	50.8%	54.1%	26.2%	23.8%	35.4%	42.9%
Strongly agree	25.0%	16.8%	17.6%	19.8%	28.7%	17.1%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 5.1: Percentage of PROD.1, PROD.2, PROD.3, PROD.4, PROD.5 and PROF.1.

The findings agree with a review of literature that 'product differentiation strategies appear to enhance competitiveness and increase profitability' (Hosen 1993). In addition, the results also correlate with the literature reviews from (King'oo, 2015) and Waterson (1990), which proved that marketing mix strategies and product differentiation can impact profitability. Moreover, the findings also agree with a review of literature by Wang (2021), who studies performance evaluation of retail enterprises. Product differentiation appears to boost competitiveness and profitability. Furthermore, the results also correlate with a literature review from Waterson (1990), who studied product differentiation and profitability. Product differentiation significantly enhances a company's profitability. This study demonstrated that a strategic plan can contribute to enhanced financial performance, including increased profitability. This is possible because a reliable product–market match could really contribute to higher customer satisfaction, which is one of the outcomes of this hypothesis. These findings are in agreement with the findings presented here.

5.2.3 Promotion variation

This study discovered a strong positive correlation between promotion variation variables and profitability performance, with a coefficient close to 1 and a p-value less than 0.05.

In it, it was revealed that there was a strong linear link between “Promotion variation” and “Profitability”. The independent variables explain the R Square as 41.5% of the dependent variable of the variability, Promotion variation. **Table 5.2**, from the results of this study 46.10% of the respondents agree that “*Your company applies personal selling as one of the promotional strategy.*” Moreover, it was also found 45.3% agree that “*Promotions consider the public understanding*” and 41.20% agree that “*Your product is promoted on events (exhibitions)*”. The findings also showed that 49% of the respondents agree “*Your company achieved maximum profitability due to promotional strategy*”. Based on this study, it could be said that the company’s profitability was highly increased by the Promotion variation marketing strategy implementation.

	People know your products based on your promotional strategy (PROM.1)	Your company applies advertising as one of the promotional strategy (PROM.2)	Your company applies personal selling as one of the promotional strategy. (PROM.3)	Promotions consider the public understanding (PROM.4)	Your product is promoted on events (exhibitions) (PROM.5)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to promotional strategy (PROF.2)
Strongly disagree	1.0%	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Disagree	2.0%	3.0%	1.0%	0.0%	2.0%	1.0%
Somewhat disagree	2.0%	4.1%	1.0%	2.0%	2.0%	1.0%
Neutral	9.8%	1.0%	14.2%	5.7%	1.2%	3.0%
Somewhat agree	30.8%	33.9%	20.1%	21.7%	35.4%	13.0%
Agree	35.4%	39.0%	46.1%	45.3%	41.2%	49.0%
Strongly agree	19.0%	17.0%	17.6%	25.3%	18.2%	33.0%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.2: Percentage of PROM.1, PROM.2, PROM.3, PROM.4, PROM.5 and PROF.2.

The findings agree with review of literature that 'promotional variation strategy caused increase in market share and profitability' (Adefulu, 2015). The findings also correlate with a literature review from Aghara et al. (2018), which stated that specific marketing variety were employed since the approach was essential for creating and retaining brand and customer loyalty, which leads to profitability. The results also correlate with this statement. In addition, the findings corroborate with the literature review conducted by Ailawadi and Neslin (1998), which uncovered the fact the promotional products encourage buyers to purchase right away and have a beneficial influence on both market share and profitability. Moreover, Anthonia (2019) discovered that the results of the testing hypotheses demonstrated that sales promotion does have a positive effect on profit and that there is a need for organisations to be significantly proactive in their actions to continue to improve their revenue and profits and strategic edge. These findings are in agreement with the findings presented here.

5.2.4 Price variation

The results of this study demonstrated a substantial positive connection with price variation factors and profitability performance, with a coefficient of (0.917) near to 1 and a p-value below 0.05. Additionally, it was demonstrated that "price variation" and "profitability" had a considerable linear correlation. R Square indicates that the independent variables account for 66.5% of the dependent variable of the variability. Price variation. In **Table 4.21**, result of this study revealed 41% of the respondents agree that "*Provide products with different price range*" and 38% agree that "*The company uses pricing skills and systems to respond quickly to market changes.*" In addition, 35% agree that "*The price of the products is reasonable*". The finding also revealed that 47% of the respondents agree that "*Company achieved maximum profitability due to pricing strategy.*"

However, in Table 5.3 showed that the finding of 45% respondents disagree the term of "The pricing decision allows for credit terms" and 36% disagree that "*The pricing decisions allow for discounts*". It means many companies not giving credit terms for customer in order to increase profitability. Moreover, 21% respondents disagree that

gives their customers typically lowest pricing. It means business owner only offers lower price or discount on certain times and on certain product. This showed having inappropriate pricing strategies results relatively lesser profitability. Findings showed that business performance is highly dependent on pricing strategies and whatever price a company establishes for a service or product has a big impact on its profitability. Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the Price variation marketing strategy implementation.

	The price of the products is reasonable (PRIC.1)	This company offers the overall lowest price in the area (PRIC.2)	The pricing decisions allow for discounts (PRIC.3)	The pricing decision allows for credit terms (PRIC.4)	Provide products with different price range (PRIC.5)	Maintains the best everyday price for most product (PRIC.6)	The company uses pricing skills and systems to respond quickly to market changes (PRIC.7)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to pricing strategy (PROF.3)
Strongly disagree	1%	5%	4%	10%	0%	3%	0%	0%
Disagree	2%	21%	36%	45%	2%	10%	1%	1%
Somewhat disagree	2%	23%	21%	25%	2%	5%	8%	4%
Neutral	10%	10%	10%	11%	1%	8%	10%	3%
Somewhat agree	31%	19%	17%	4%	35%	19%	22%	12%
Agree	35%	18%	7%	3%	41%	30%	38%	47%
Strongly agree	19%	3%	4%	2%	18%	25%	21%	33%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.3: Percentage of PRIC.1, PRIC.2, PRIC.3, PRIC.4, PRIC.5, PRIC.6, PRIC.7 and PROF.3.

The results are consistent with the literature review, which specifies that pricing are critical element of the marketing strategy (Nagle and Müller 2017) .According to Nagle and Müller (2017), who studied the strategy and tactics of pricing, a business can maximise its profitability by determining an appropriate price for each of its products. The results agree with a review of the previous research. According to Savan (2018),

who investigated analysis of time series for small-to medium-sized businesses' strategic pricing, price variation is a part of marketing strategies used by businesses to accurately price those goods and services in accordance with the demand that is present in the market. The finding showed that it is useful in determining the optimal price for the product, which can vary depending on the positioning that an organisation targets to increase sales and profitability. The discoveries are similarly consistent with the findings of this study. Customers are pushed in the direction of making an immediate purchase, which contributes to an increase in the profits of businesses.

The results are also consistent with a review of the literature by Kohli and Suri (2011), who examined guidelines for pricing to increase profitability. They found that companies should set prices with an eye toward maximising profits; even relatively small changes in price can have a sizable effect on profits and sales. Setting prices is a mathematical and behavioural economics-based creative exercise. As a consequence of this, failing to engage in careful price planning results in a lost opportunity. The results are consistent with a review of the literature from Benoit et al. (2020), who studied intuitive pricing by independent store managers, all of these offer such as discounted prices, premium offers of any kind, gift certificates and samples are utilised by convenience store businesses as a means of boosting profits by incentivizing consumers to make an initial purchase. The conclusions of this review agree and are in line with those results in this study.

Furthermore, the results are consistent with De Toni et al. (2017), who investigated prices of products as well as other factors and their effects on business earnings. They found that price marketing strategy and premium price rate influence the profitability of the businesses that were surveyed, whereas low price levels have the opposite effect. The results are consistent with a review of the literature from Jindal et al. (2020), who studied marketing-mix response across retail formats, one of the most crucial business decisions is determining prices because doing so can have a significant impact on a company's profitability, return on investment, and level of market competitiveness.

Furthermore, the results are consistent with Goi et al. (2021), who investigated the factors that influence customer satisfaction in the convenience stores sector. They

found that price changes do have a significant effect on a company's profitability and that pricing strategies vary widely depending on the sector and the specific market condition. The results are consistent with a review of the literature from Bolton and Shankar (2018), who studied emerging retailer pricing trends and practices, A convenience store company may utilise product pricing to emphasise quality service and, as a consequence, generate profit. Importance pricing is generated from a variety of competing principles and organisational strategies. The results are also consistent with Cleary et al. (2018), who investigated store profitability and public policies and who hold that value-based pricing and retail pricing practises, which refer to the application of knowledge about costs and the competitors' prices, have been inseparably linked to the success of both the product and the service, as well as increasing sales and profitability.

In conclusion, these findings make it abundantly clear that different pricing strategies do have an effect on the amount of profit that businesses make. This study discovered it fluctuates greatly across industries and market conditions and has a considerable influence on a business's profitability.

5.2.5 Place

The results of this study shown that Place and profitability performance have a high significant relationships since the coefficient is (0.876), which is near to 1, p-value is less than 0.05. It demonstrated that "Place" and "Profitability" have a large linear connection. The independent factors account for R Square 34.9% of the variable dependent. Based on the data in Table 5.4, 58% of respondents agree that *"Your company is near to most resident/working areas"* and 49% of the respondents agree that *"Convenient public transport to get to this convenience store."* In addition, the findings identified that 53% of the respondents also agree that *"Have distribution channels easy to find"* and 40% agree that *"Fast checkout"*. The finding also revealed that 44% of the respondents agree that *"Your company achieved maximum profitability due to distribution strategy."* Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the Place in marketing strategy implementation.

	Fast checkout (PLAC.1)	Have distribution channels easy to find (PLAC.2)	Convenient public transport to get to this convenience store (PLAC.3)	Your company is near to most resident/working areas (PLAC.4)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to distribution strategy (PROF.4)
Strongly disagree	3%	2%	3%	1%	0%
Disagree	5%	3%	3%	3%	0%
Somewhat disagree	5%	5%	9%	7%	1%
Neutral	11%	19%	13%	14%	11%
Somewhat agree	24%	15%	18%	10%	25%
Agree	40%	53%	49%	58%	44%
Strongly agree	11%	3%	5%	8%	19%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.4: Percentage of PLAC.1, PLAC.2, PLAC.3, PLAC.4 and PROF.4.

The results are in line with a literature review, which claims that "it is vital to minimise the distribution costs while raising the profit of the organisation in order to attain a high profit and a good service level" (Huang and Liu, 2017). It is anticipated that the company will achieve profitability by incorporating placement and distribution activities into their business marketing strategies (Huang and Liu, 2017). The findings are also consistent with a literature review conducted by Hunelegn (2019) came to the conclusion that there was a substantial association between place strategies and company profitability based on the results of the correlation and regression.

Additionally, the findings are in line that Fraser and Hite's (1990) study of the literature, which investigated at how success in various overseas markets was impacted by global marketing. The type and degree of the relationships vary dramatically across global areas, they discovered, even while marketing mix components like locale and distribution seem to have an impact on success in one or more regions. Furthermore, implementation of place and distribution in marketing mix has been related consistently to the profitability of large corporations. Moreover, the results also

correlate with literature review from Londhe (2014), who studied marketing mix for next generation marketing, demonstrated that location, distribution methods, and profitability are all correlated positively.

Finally, The results support a review of the literature by Degeratu and Gruca (2015), who examined the effect of Marketing Strategy on Profitability and Market Share of Company Enterprises and found that “Place” in marketing mix elements leads to superior performance and profitability. Furthermore, they were able to demonstrate that the corporate ventures' marketing mix had a significant impact on their market share as well as their return on sales and profitability. Additionally, companies who employ a proactive approach outperform their rivals in terms of revenue and profit margins (Degeratu and Gruca, 2015). These results show that placement strategies affect an organization's profitability.

5.2.6 People

As this coefficient is (0.712), which is near to 1, and the p-value is less than 0.05, the outcomes of this investigation demonstrated a substantial positive association between people and their profit performance. It explained that "People" and "Profitability" have a strong linear connection. The independent factors account for R Square 41.9% of the variable dependent. In Table 5.5 of the research findings shows that 55% of respondents agree that *“Your organization have great team leader.”* The finding also revealed that 46% of the respondents agree that *“Your employees practice great customer service.”* In addition, the findings identified that 43% of the respondents also agree that *“Your employees knowledgeable about all product in store.”* and 41% agree that *“Your organization have well-trained staff”*. The finding also revealed that 44% of the respondents strongly agree that *“Your company achieved maximum profitability due to people strategy.”* Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the people in marketing strategy implementation.

	Your organization have well-trained staff. (PP.1)	Most of your staff have work experience in convenience store. (PP.2)	Your employees practice great customer service. (PP.3)	Your organization have great team leader. (PP.4)	Your employees knowledgeable about all product in store. (PP.5)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to people strategy? (PROF.5)
Strongly disagree	1%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Disagree	2%	7%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Somewhat disagree	2%	3%	0%	3%	2%	0%
Neutral	15%	21%	4%	11%	3%	13%
Somewhat agree	23%	16%	34%	12%	34%	18%
Agree	41%	34%	46%	55%	43%	25%
Strongly agree	16%	16%	16%	19%	19%	44%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.5: Percentage of PP.1, PP.2, PP.3, PP.4, PP.5 and PROF.5.

The results are consistent with the literature analysis by Judd and V.C. (1987), who investigated employees' perceptions of traditional advertising and created a strategy of differentiation in order to obtain a competitive edge and generate profit, which revealed that “employees should be recognised as a distinctive element of the marketing mix, people power and consequently as an integral part of marketing strategy”. The company may increase its profitability and achieve a competitive advantage by organising their workforce in the context of newly established consumer-related responsibilities. This helps the organisation stand out from its rivals and gives it a distinct advantage in the marketplace.

Moreover, the findings are consistent with a review that was carried out by Handayani et al. (2020). These researchers examined the part that a company's marketing mix implementation plays in its performance and discovered that the number of fiber-based firms, their profitability, their overall production, and their share of the market have all increased.

The results are consistent with a literature analysis done by Pooser et al. (2018), who investigated at how pleased consumers are with the services offered by U.S. car insurers and discovered a connection between profitability measures and consumer fulfilment ratings. The finding agree the idea of low pricing and high levels of quality are linked to better satisfaction among customers which lead to increase company's profitability.

Similarly, the findings correlate with the literature review from Ali et al. (2017) who studied how the effectiveness of tourist in Sri Lanka's eastern area is affected by marketing mix approaches, based on the finding, it was shown that people who offering great customer service to customers have the most significant impact on marketing performance and profitability. People are an indispensable part of any product, service, or experience offered by a company. Particularly in the industry of convenience stores, production and consumption of a service typically occur simultaneously, and various facets of the consumer experience are altered to cater to the specific requirements of the individuals who are using the service (Ali et al., 2017). Also, the findings correlate with the literature review from Lam and Mayer (2014), who studied a voice model in the context of customer service, the finding showed that employees who provide exceptional customer service have a substantial impact on sales and profitability.

In contrast, in their several research on shop image, Mitchell et al. (1998) discovered no connection both store characteristics and customer retention. In addition, according to Garton (1995) and Bloemer et al. (1998), the degree of effect that a consumer's encounter with the quality and service of a store has on whether or not they become a loyal repeat customer is relatively low.

In addition, the findings are consistent with a literature review that was carried out by Chandra (2016), who investigated how marketing strategy were perceived by workers of retail businesses and showed that this has a significant impact on the company's success and performance. The findings support Azeem and Sharma's review of the literature (2015) who studied at the components of the retail marketing mix as well as various retail types in India. The results demonstrate that employees are essential to

improving companies' sales and profitability. The perspective of the customer regarding the efficiency of the people providing the service is essential when conducting an analysis of the level of service provided (Azeem and Sharma, 2015). Furthermore, the findings are consistent with a literature review conducted by Hill and Alexander (2017), who studied the customer satisfaction and loyalty measurement handbook. Offering a replacement service to customers, such as changing business hours to better accommodate individual customers' needs and keeping commitments and agreements on time, is an important part of attracting customers and has the ability to give convenience store businesses an advantage in the marketplace and increase profitability (Hill and Alexander, 2017). According to the study's findings, it showed that the firm's participation in the implementation of strategies greatly enhanced the company's profitability.

5.2.7 Process

The study's findings demonstrate a high positive connection with process variables and profitability performance; both coefficient, which is close to one at (0.703), and the p-value, that is lower than 0.05, both reflect this. A substantial linear link for both the variables "process" and "profitability" was also discovered in the research. 41.3 % of the variation in the dependent factor is explained by the independent factors. , which is the promotion variable, according to the R Square calculation.

Research outcomes in **Table 5.6**, indicated that 55% respondents strongly agree that *"Your company achieved maximum profitability due to process strategy"*. The finding also revealed that 54% of the respondents agree that "Your organization educate and support customers on an ongoing basis and 50% of the respondents agree that "The store opens and close at convenient time". In addition, the findings identified that 43% of the respondents also agree that *"Your employees knowledgeable about all product in store."* and 49% agree that *"Are your customers get all product information they need"*. The finding also revealed that 48% of the respondents strongly agree that *"Are your customers being serviced excellently."* Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the process in marketing strategy implementation.

	Your organization educate and support customers on an ongoing basis. (PROC.1)	Are your customers being serviced excellently? (PROC.2)	Are your customers get all product information they need? (PROC.3)	The store offers speed of service. (PROC.4)	The store opens and close at convenient time. (PROC.5)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to process strategy? (PROF.6)
“Strongly disagree”	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
“Disagree”	2%	0%	2%	0%	0%	0%
“Somewhat disagree”	1%	2%	0%	1%	2%	0%
“Neutral”	16%	19%	18%	20%	11%	8%
“Somewhat agree”	54%	20%	20%	21%	18%	17%
“Agree”	17%	48%	49%	44%	50%	20%
“Strongly agree”	10%	12%	11%	13%	19%	55%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.6: Percentage of PROC.1, PROC.2, PROC.3, PROC.4, PROC.5 and PROF.6.

The results correlate with a literature review by Hanaysha et al. (2021), who studied the significance of marketing mix variables in retail purchasing habits. Their finding showed that process elements in the marketing mix significantly impact customer purchase decisions, which leads to profitability for companies. In addition, the findings correlate with a literature review from Kushwaha and Agrawal (2015), whose research of an Indian consumer's environment 7Ps in marketing management finds that aspects including quickness, quality of products, and ease of accessibility substantially impact customer satisfaction, which leads to higher sales and profitability for a company. However, at specific circumstances, inability to deliver promptly may force customers to leave convenience shops. (Kushwaha and Agrawal 2015).

The findings also agree with a review of literature from Bahador (2019), who studied the marketing mix and organizations' effectiveness, including all actual procedures. The findings show that all of the activities that take place at work can be categorised as processes, which is an essential component in the marketing strategies for convenience stores to increase profitability. Moreover, the findings correlate with the

literature review from Chantayarkul et al. (2020), who explored the enhancement of the development of local shops by using marketing strategy in Thailand. The quality of products and services has a substantial impact on consumer purchase decisions at those establishments. The investigation also established that providing a high level of services is critical for businesses to do in order to remain competitive and generate a profit (Chantayarkul et al. 2020).

Finally, the finding correlate with literature review from The research findings of Babu and Naveen (2018), who studied perceptions about the pros and cons of organised retail shops and unorganised retail stores, revealed that a well-designed and created store with a high emphasis on operational excellence by providing a considerable variety of merchandise and a significant level of operations has a significant impact on sales and profitability. Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the Process in marketing strategy implementation.

5.2.8 Physical evidence

The results of this study revealed a significant positive connection between the physical evidence factors and profitability performance, with a coefficient of (0.913) near to 1 and a p-value below 0.05. The link between "Physical evidence" and "Profitability" was also explained to have a substantial linear relationship. Physical evidence's R Square indicates that the independent factors account for 68.9% of its variability.

Research findings in **Table 5.7**, shown that most of respondents 56% agree that "*Your company achieved maximum profitability due to physical evidence strategy*". The finding also revealed that 49% of the respondents agree that "Your store are impressive with nice design and decoration" and 48% of the respondents agree that "Your store are clean and tidy environment". In addition, the findings identified that 44% of the respondents also agree that "*Your store are well organized.*" Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the physical evidence in marketing strategy implementation.

	Your store are well organized. (PHY.1)	Your store are clean and tidy environment. (PHY.2)	Your store are impressive with nice design and decoration. (PHY.3)	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to physical evidence strategy? (PROF.7)
Strongly disagree	0%	0%	0%	0%
Disagree	2%	2%	1%	0%
Somewhat disagree	6%	2%	1%	0%
Neutral	11%	10%	18%	7%
Somewhat agree	20%	29%	20%	17%
Agree	44%	48%	49%	56%
Strongly agree	17%	10%	11%	22%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5.7: Percentage of PHY.1, PHY.2, PHY.3 and PROF.7.

The findings are consistent with a review of literature conducted by Hill and Alexander (2017), who studied customer satisfaction and loyalty measurement, there is a positive impact on high-value perceptions on the physical evidence of business services stores on sales and profitability. The physical evidence of business services, including customer satisfaction, wide assortment, and convenience, is offered by the convenience stores (Hill and Alexander 2017). Moreover, the findings also are consistent with a review of literature conducted by Khairannur (2021), who studied marketing strategies in Medan, the research findings showed that physical evidence of the shop has a positive relationship with customer purchase decisions, which leads to profitability for the company. Moreover, the majority of customers typically visit two or more retail establishments on a consistent basis. This is partly due to the fact that they shop at a variety of locations, such as on the commute home from work or during other activities outside the home (Khairannur 2021).

However, the findings are not consistent with a review of literature conducted by Mitchell (1998), who investigated the effect of customer risk perceptions within groceries retail, based on several studies on store image and found no correlation between both store attributes and customer loyalty. On the other hand, the findings are consistent with a review of literature conducted by Bahador (2019), who investigated how the marketing strategy affects organisations' efficiencies, the "physical evidence" one of the marketing mix element seems to have a favourable influence on a business' profit and revenue. All of the tangibly present items that customers can see and touch constitute the elements of the physical evidence in the case of a convenience store (Bahador 2019).

In addition, the finding correlate with literature review from O'Sullivan and Ngugi (2022), who studied marketing mix, based on the research findings physical evidence and business success and profitability are positively correlated. Moreover, O'Sullivan and Ngugi (2022) stated that convenience stores are obligated to manage physical evidence because it has the potential to have a reflective influence on customers' perceptions and it communicates an external image of the service package, both of which can lead to the development of a desire to make a purchase and an increase in profitability. Furthermore, the finding correlate with literature review from Qomariah and Kurnia 2022, who examined the Effect of Marketing Strategy on Impulse Purchases at Supermarket, Jember, showed that the store's physical representation has a large influence on sales and profitability. For example, the appearance of the building, the grounds, the interior and exterior furnishings, the infrastructure, the equipment, and the uniforms of the employees, the communication materials, and any other visible prompts are all examples of physical evidence which lead to increase sales and profitability (Qomariah and Kurnia 2022).

Furthermore, the findings are consistent with a review of literature conducted by According to study by Hartman and Spiro (2005) who studied at consumer shop equity and conception, a company's profitability and sales are positively impacted by the physical attributes of its stores. Also, the finding correlate with literature review from Elgarhy and Mohamed (2022), who investigated the examining the effects of the services marketing mix (7ps) on loyalty, intent, and profitability in travel agencies in

Egypt, the research revealed that the components of physical evidence had a big influence on both sales and profitability.

Furthermore, the finding correlate with literature review from Jain et al. (2022), who studied each of the 7Ps of the Marketing Mix's Effectiveness, these aspects of a store's image have an impact on customer behaviour and the extent to which they retain a brand's loyalty, both of which are directly related to the retention of customers' trust, which, in addition to maintaining a positive image for one's convenience store, is an essential component for businesses that wish to continue to be profitable. Lastly, the finding correlate with literature review from Erlina and Hermawan (2021), who examined the marketing strategy of a Bandung coffee shop and its impact on loyal consumers, the most significant factor that affects customer loyalty and company profitability is physical evidence. Based on this study, it could be said that the company's profitability was highly increased by the physical evidence in marketing strategy implementation. These findings are in agreement with the findings presented here.

5.3 Summary

The empirical data and explanations of the outcomes based on the seven tested hypotheses were provided in this chapter. The major finding from the data analysis was discussed, and the seven results from each hypothesis were then presented. The empirical findings were verified and confirmed, and the results were compared to finding in literature reviews in Chapter 2. The findings were in line with a literature review on the connection between profitability and the seven Ps of marketing mix strategies. The results suggest that marketing mix strategies have a great influence on the profitability of the company. According to the study's findings, people, place, physical evidence and process all are linked to profitability along with product differentiation, promotion variation and pricing variation. Moreover, it shows that price and product differentiation are the most important aspects when business owners or managers apply marketing mix strategies. This indicates that convenience stores in the United Kingdom compete primarily on price and product differentiation.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

6.1 Chapter overview

This chapter provides a summary of research findings on the effects of marketing strategy on convenience shops' profitability in the United Kingdom. In addition to restating the original issue statement, this study conclusion also suggests several potential solutions. It also outlines how the study's findings could improve the industry. The chapter begins with the research findings and their implications in Section 6.2, then moves on to the theoretical implications in Section 6.2.1, and finally to the managerial implications in Section 6.2.2. Section 6.3 continues the discussion about the limitation of the study and future research. Section 6.3.1 details the limitation of the study. Section 6.3.2 discusses future research, and Section 6.4 provides a summary of the chapter.

6.2 Introduction

A marketing strategy is important for retailers because it helps them plan their business model and create and use effective marketing strategies. This study applies marketing mix strategies 7P to help convenience store retailers improve their business by providing a roadmap for their business objectives. This study was inspired by the fact that, though the convenience store is an innovative and vigorous retail format in the United Kingdom, no studies have ever explained its development under a marketing mix 7p theoretical framework. Therefore, this strategy is essential to help retailers choose the great product at the right time at the right price and for the right people in order to increase company profitability.

The purpose of this study was to investigate at the link involving marketing mix approaches and convenience store profitability in the United Kingdom. The marketing mix 7Ps strategy have been analysed in this study based on their various dimensions as well as the impact those dimensions have on profitability. To be more specific, the research investigates how much product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, physical evidence process people and place all elements contribute to companies profitability. The research came to the conclusion that the marketing mix 7 Ps strategies tend to exhibit a favourable influence on company profitability. The

conceptual framework for this research suggests that the seven factors that affect profitability are product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, process, and physical evidence, which were supported by a previous study.

This result revealed that product differentiation and price variation are the greatest favourable elements in marketing mix strategies. This research also suggests that product differentiation and promotion variation build brand awareness, which leads to purchase intention, and findings show that the main influence of marketing mix strategies variables on profitability is price variation. As a result, the prices of products in the grocery store can fluctuate from day to day, depending on demand. Despite the fact that most convenience stores in the United Kingdom have constant pricing policies, this is not always the case. Because customers may be confident in the price being offered, this results in customer satisfaction.

According to the survey results, a total of 77 percent of respondents stated that they provide regular discounts to their customers. Another 43 percent of those polled said they occasionally offer discounts to repeat and referral customers. When it comes to setting prices, logic simply comes down to a comparison of the effects of the various choices that can be made, such as the effect that offering a discount of ten percent will have on the profits of retail companies. Not only does an increase or decrease in revenue involve the revenue generated by the product in question, but also the revenue generated by the business as a whole. If the proposed change in price results in a significant increase in overall revenues rather than an increase in total costs, then the change will have the effect of resulting in an increase in the profit margin.

This chapter presents a research findings summary and an analysis of their contributions and limitations. In Section 5.2, the ramifications of the research findings are broken down in greater detail. The limitations of the ongoing research are analysed in Section 5.3, along with possible avenues for further investigation. Finally, Section 5.4 emphasises the importance of the conclusion.

6.3. Research findings and their implications

The aim of this research was to significantly contribute to the field of knowledge regarding marketing mix strategy. It was carried out in seven Ps (promotion variation,

price variation, place, people, process, and physical evidence). The fundamental contribution of this study is based on a research gap discovered in the review of related literature, which suggests that the influence of marketing mix strategies on convenience store's profitability in the UK should be further examined. It also makes an important contribution by suggesting a conceptual framework for studying the marketing mix strategy from all of its different angles and effects in order to figure out how this affects the profits of convenience stores, which is important. The next section discusses the implications of the study results, starting with theoretical implications and moving on to managerial implications.

6.3.1 Theoretical Implications

Ridder et al. (2009) define theoretical contribution as a process based on new theories' development and knowledge improvement by using logic and empirical evidence. It entails generating new knowledge based on existing knowledge through extensive and original research. Through a narrative literature review, the study was concentrated on theoretical contributions related to research questions and their answers. The previous study suggests that marketing mix strategies and profitability are related, but it did not investigate the nature of this relationship. Although this is true, the present study provided a valid and reliable framework that reveals the connections in the marketing mix strategy conceptual framework, the variables that affect profitability, and the implications of these relationships.

The current study offers a conceptual contribution by improving concepts and theories of the new knowledge. A new conceptual framework is developed by this study using models from earlier research. The conceptual framework has also been expanded upon by the construction and identification of new frameworks. In addition, the current research study has contributed to the creation of a new theoretical connection for the marketing mix 7Ps research with new multi-hypotheses that are being presented and tested.

This study contributes to knowledge by evaluating a theoretical relationship among seven dimensions as well as exploring the impact of a marketing mix seven Ps factor on profitability that has not previously been evaluated in the UK context. Furthermore,

this research determines the degree to which a variable strongly correlates with profitability constructs.

Additionally, for methodology contributions, by testing a proposed methodology in a new context, this research provides new knowledge. The methodology has been adopted in other industries, and the effectiveness of this methodology in the convenience store industry is proven by this study. Besides that, this research advances knowledge through validating instruments in a different environment. In addition, this study uses previous survey questions and questionnaires. These quantitative methods were utilised in this investigation.

Moreover, by validating a theory, this study contributes advance knowledge in the retail industry. The hypothesis has been tested in other nations, but not in relation to the UK context. Also, this research was tested in the UK and proved positive and approved the theory's effectiveness, which is a new knowledge contribution. Furthermore, this research contributes to the expansion of literature about marketing mix 7Ps theory strategies, their dimensions, and their impact on profitability. Besides, this study has applied the marketing mix 7Ps theory and has revealed how marketing strategy impacts the profitability of convenience stores.

The reason for conducting this research was to fill gaps in the existing knowledge on how marketing strategies impact convenience store profitability. It also responds to a previous study that looked at marketing research from the perspective of consumers.

This research contributes to the expanding knowledge base on marketing mix strategies, including their dimensions and effects on profitability. Based on models from earlier research, a fresh conceptual framework was created and tested in the UK's convenience store industry. In particular, the development of a multi-hypothesis for marketing mix strategies is a significant contribution made by the current investigation. The most difficult task in this regard is the transformation of hypotheses into relationships that can be translated into findings that are correlated with the current research.

This research examined seven essential marketing mix strategy dimensions were studied in this research: product differentiation, promotion variety, pricing variation,

place, people, process, and physical evidence. This study concentrated on marketing mix strategies and their dimensional factors, which captured a variety of data, including knowledge about general business performance and profitability, the value of recognition and recall feelings and opinions, ideas, and selling trends, as well as general knowledge about business performance and profitability. It has been shown in previous research that businesses will perform better and earn more profit if they implement marketing mix strategies (Cleary et al., 2018); Black et al., 2017; Laffy and Walters, 2016). The results of this research support this assertion.

The results of this research also revealed that each dimension of marketing mix strategies has a statistically significant relationship with the outcomes predicted by the conceptual model. Thus, if marketing mix strategies fail on the dimensions of price variation, people will have a negative perception of place, people, and physical evidence; there will be a lack of product differentiation; negative associations will be formed with the promotion variation and the brand; and there will be a negative impact on the profitability of businesses.

6.3.2. Managerial implications

The main objective of this research is to explore at the marketing mix 7Ps strategies and how they affect company's profitability. This research offers managerial insights for managers and business owners who are interested in marketing mix strategies and how to apply them successfully based on the theoretical contributions presented in the previous sections. This research also contains valuable insights into the convenience store industry, it aids in understanding and improving the company's business performance; and it aids in increasing the company's profits.

This research provides a general picture of the entire situation in which marketing mix strategies influence profitability. This includes product differentiation, promotion variation, price variation, place, people, and process, as well as physical evidence. The research's findings have important managerial implications since it present a complete picture that includes brand awareness and good impressions of product differentiation, promotion variation, pricing variation, place, people, process, and physical evidence. It indicates a thorough comprehension of the variables that

influence the creation of successful marketing mix approaches that provide beneficial effects.

The results showed how marketing mix approaches significantly affect a company's profitability. Meanwhile, customers in the UK tend to be highly prone to developing brand loyalty for a certain brand by associating that brand with quality, services, convenience, and prices. The results of this study show that while brand recognition is important to consumers, it is not the main driving force behind purchases. Customers are more inclined to judge a brand on the basis of the value of the goods and services it offers. The above indicates that consumers are more likely to think about the brand's quality in general before making a purchase.

Speaking of quality, the findings revealed that the presence of a product that is easily identifiable and of high quality makes people feel more confident about purchasing the product. Furthermore, a high product's quality is also closely linked to consumer willingness to purchase it. According to the findings of this study, 50.8 percent of businesses agree to provide customers with a variety of products to choose from. That is to say, managers and business owners agreed that consumers have a positive attitude toward a variety of products, particularly when the products are associated with a well-known and reliable brand. Customers are more likely to purchase products that make them feel comfortable.

Another conclusion that can be drawn through the findings of this research is that managers and business owners need to be informed about the importance of marketing strategy. Businesses should make efforts to evaluate the needs of their customers and train all staff members in the responsibilities that have been assigned to them, particularly in the area of customer service. Additionally, they have to try to ascertain what their clients' demands are. Also, the majority of convenience stores lack the resources (including time, finances, skills, and industry expertise) necessary to perform the research and development of new business ideas that could be advantageous to their customers. Moreover, Institutions of higher learning (HEIs) have the ability to provide convenience stores with information relating to specialised knowledge, technological advancements, and other resources that may be of use to convenience stores. Working together with research departments at colleges and

universities would have allowed a convenience store to reach the same level of new business development that it could not have done on its own.

Moreover, convenience stores retailers in particular need to take part in marketing research to better understand their customers. They should carry out research on the market to determine the level of expertise possessed by their customers in order to better meet the requirements of specific niches in which they operate. High-end customers expect products of higher quality and a higher level of luxury, whereas regular customers are more concerned with the fundamental necessities of life and are less concerned with quality. Customers of high-end luxury goods are attracted to the allure of quality, and they are willing and able to pay significant sums of money to have the peace of mind that the quality of products, goods, or services they purchase lives up to the high expectations they have set for them and is well worth the substantial amount of money they have spent. In addition to this, it is essential for business owners or managers to conduct research into the ways in which their customers evaluate price and quality. They will find that the process of business segmentation and selection of target markets is much simpler for them as a result, which will enable them to focus on and develop their particular niche within society. It would appear that the management of convenience stores in the United Kingdom are aware that the customer is the single most important component in the success of their organisations. Even though many companies are aware of how to foster customer loyalty, it is possible that they do not fully understand what constitutes the foundation of an effective customer care initiative. To improve quality standards in the convenience store industry, the following ideas could be taken into account:

A comprehensive "paradigm shift" in the way that management thinks about the delivery of service quality by providing employees with ongoing learning and skills in aspects of customer service, customer satisfaction, and quality service.

A more consistent and reliable product offering is required to ensure that a consistent and reliable general opinion is created in the thoughts of customers. When delivering services and products to customers, it's important to pay attention to details, like making sure that expiration dates are checked.

Convenience store owners and managers must devote more time to developing "relationships" with their customers in order to be successful. This will make it easier to receive regular feedback from customers on their level of satisfaction with the product. Through offering personalised attention to clients, it helps to develop customer loyalty. Because of this, convenience store owners and managers should pay closer attention to the specific requirements of their customers.

To be competitive, convenience stores should emphasise their pricing decisions on established financial accounts rather than just their intuitions. Moreover, the result of this study revealed that 41% of the respondents agree that "Provide products with different price range" and 38% agree that "The company uses pricing skills and systems to respond quickly to market changes." The finding also revealed that 47% of the respondents agreed that "Company achieved maximum profitability due to pricing strategy." The findings showed that owners and managers of convenience stores in the United Kingdom had adopted the marketing strategy concept to an above-average degree. This suggests that there is an opportunity for these business owners or managers to receive additional training on how to implement marketing strategies that increase profitability. Therefore, in order to maximise profitability while applying the marketing strategy mix, convenience store owners and managers should employ systematic skills to react rapidly to market changes. For example, business owners or managers need to investigate how much the product costs and what the current market price is in the market before making a price decision on their product. This method will offer a reasonable price to the consumer and not too high or too low.

Moreover, the study's conclusions indicate that these convenience stores need to use at least three Ps of marketing strategy—product, pricing, and place to increase their profitability. The owners/managers of convenience stores, on the other hand, stated that they do not engage in extensive marketing practises, which is true.

Additionally, the owners/managers of convenience stores stated that they make an effort to distinguish themselves from other businesses that offer similar products. Convenience shops compete mostly on how distinctive their items are, so they must offer a large selection of goods for customers to pick from. According to this research finding, exhibit behaviours that can indicative of a high degree of marketing orientation.

In order to increase sales, they offer loyal consumers discounts rather than adopting a long-term strategy centred on their needs and desires. Therefore, convenience stores need to employ the principles of marketing mix 7Ps strategy to increase their profitability.

Moreover, the research findings point out that convenience store managers or owners should think carefully and do sufficient research before using marketing mix strategies in their business. For convenience store managers or owners be able to quickly respond to the changes in the customer and market environment, they should be aware of target consumers' preferences and purchase behavior.

Finally, during the 2019 coronavirus (COVID-19) season, the convenience store retail industry has been facing new challenges and opportunities. The pandemic caused numerous changes in the convenience store companies, including shifts in consumer behaviour and perception. Even though the pandemic is only temporary, these changes may have both short-term and long-term effects on reforms in the convenience store retail business. Additionally, according to Wang, Y., et al. (2020), who studied how COVID-19 affected consumer store groceries behaviour throughout this pandemic, the survey's results revealed that consumers now have higher standards for in-store safety, have slowed down their shopping frequency, have altered their typical shopping schedules and destinations, and want to increase their spending per trip. Below is the suggestion of Pandemic marketing plan and Pandemic safety conduct for business owner and managers of convenience store need to take consideration in order to improve sales and profitability both in the short term and in the long term.

Pandemic marketing plan:

To encourage new customers to attempt online grocery shopping in the short term goal, convenience store companies provide promotional discounts or rewards. Provide delivery people who have been trained by professionals and are protected and tested in large groups. Long-term goals include expansion into smaller cities so that more customers have access to the service. Food items should have health certificates, particularly imported items, to ensure safety procedures. Provide freshness and fast

delivery to ensure customer satisfaction. Create an independent logistics system, for example, near busy crossroads for prompt delivery. It offers a flexible return option for customers who are dissatisfied with their purchases.

Pandemic preparedness of safety conduct:

In the short term, managers routinely test frontline staff members like cashiers and store assistants and address their issues about health implications. Managers also need to analyse and report information on food safety for products coming from high-risk countries. All staff members ought to eventually obtain the necessary training during the pandemic. Maintain an increase in the quality and sources of raw food ingredients (poultry products, dairy products, vegetables and fruits), and keep that information easily accessible online. Through websites, retail applications, and social media, keep the lines of communication open with business customers. Ensure that food packaging is eco-friendly, has precise and concise details about its contents, as well as being safe to use.

To summarise, the employment of marketing mix strategies in convenience stores is an effective marketing tool. Businesses should utilise the right marketing mix methods to attract potential customers' attention and excite their interest. This finding also demonstrates that price variation has the greatest impact on profitability when considering marketing mix strategies. Following the investigation, evidence to substantiate this claim was discovered. In the grand scheme of things, the achieved results of the various variables were positive. The correlations between each of the constructs were positive, and the findings indicated that each of the components plays an essential part in the convenience stores' marketing mix strategies and creates profitability for them.

6.4 Limitations of the study and future research.

Like other research projects, this study also has some limitations. The limits of the measurement concerns, research methodology, and research setting of the 7P marketing mix and their effects on convenience store profitability are further discussed in the following section.

6.4.1 Limitations of the study.

The researcher's objective was to broaden understanding of marketing mix theory, including its implications and dimensions. Even though the effort was valuable, it wasn't without limitations.

The analysis of the United Kingdom's convenience store industry shows that, compared with traditional theories of marketing strategies, marketing mix 7P provides an alternative framework to explain. The aim of this research is to investigate how various marketing mix 7Ps concepts relate to the profitability of convenience stores in the UK. This research attempts

1. To critically review the literature of marketing strategies and profitability for stores.
2. To examine existing practices of marketing strategies on profitability.
3. To examine challenges to implement the marketing strategies.
4. To examine the benefits of implementing the marketing strategies.
5. To analyse the relationship between constructs of marketing mix 7ps strategies that impact the profitability of convenience stores in the United Kingdom.

However, when applied to the analysis of convenience stores, one should consider the following factors:

Marketing mix 7ps emphasises the importance of intangible resources, which are often the sources of competitive advantage in the retail industry. However, this theory cannot identify the other important retail factors, e.g., location and store ambience. Problems may also occur in the classification of resources. For example, location is an important factor in retail strategy. However, it is not clear what category "location" belongs to.

Due to marketing mix 7ps's assertion of competition outcomes, the theory is only suitable for an industry that has developed over a long time period. A new industry may be unstable in terms of its development, and thus, marketing mix 7ps will not be able to model its pattern of development and its influence on the whole economy.

Every country has a different economic environment, cultural environment, and government policies. Thus, when applying this theory to the analysis of competition in other markets, one should consider the differences in the economy in different cultural settings.

The research's target respondents should come from various cities in the United Kingdom. However, due to time constraints, the majority of respondents are from London and a few other cities within the United Kingdom. Furthermore, because the current study's sample was not selected using probability sampling, the results have been considered cautiously. Also, the questionnaire about the qualities of marketing mix strategies may have resulted in some perceptual discrepancies among respondents. Because the perception of marketing mix strategy variables is highly subjective, making decisions on those terms is difficult. Additionally, the results of this study may be different in another nation or sector because it was done in a specific environment. In order to evaluate the research's generalizability, it is recommended that a follow-up study be carried out to replicate this research in other countries. Furthermore, in order to have a better understanding of the important aspects of the convenience store sector, future studies might widen its scope and be carried out in other regions of the nation.

Additionally, since the information was acquired through a quantitative approach with predetermined questions, different future research hypotheses can be used in subsequent studies to validate the results. For example, to achieve better findings, combine approaches such as quantitative and qualitative research.

Finally, this research was conducted with only seven independent variables explored. Therefore, future research can take into account other factors that could impact profitability in the UK convenience store sector, such as corporate social responsibility and social media marketing.

6.4.2. Future research

This section describes the study's limitations and then provides a wide range of suggestions for future research projects that will add to the existing knowledge in the literature review.

This study's objective was to present the most current data on how marketing strategy impact convenience store profitability in the UK market. In order to fully understand the issue, further study on the same topic should be conducted in different countries. A future study could produce different results using the same research scales and constructs.

In terms of the applicability of marketing mix 7P to retail competition, there are five directions for future research:

- To develop a model that can supplement Marketing Mix 7P and provide practitioners with clear strategic options for future development.
- To revise the market position matrix of marketing mix 7P or to develop an alternative model more suitable for practical use.
- To find out how retailers spot a valuable resource and further develop it into a competitive advantage.
- To modify the framework to reflect the cultural factors which influence competition.

There are also a number of potential future research options for the study of the UK convenience store business. The first possibility is to develop a dynamic model to determine the possible capacity of this industry. This research pointed out that forecasts in the past failed to provide the accurate capacity of this industry due to the changing environment. Thus, a capacity prediction model, which contains the simulation of possible environmental scenarios, will help retailers to plan for future investment and help the government to formulate policies concerning retail development in the United Kingdom.

The second possible research direction is the influence of culture on retail development. The preference of consumer shopping locations varies in different markets. Consumers' shopping preferences influence the development of supermarkets and convenience stores in the UK. Thus, a potential issue is research on the influence of cultural background on the store outlet development.

Furthermore, though the analysis showed that competition in the convenience store industry contributes to economic growth in the United Kingdom, this research did not model the relationship between the factors in convenience store competition and the outcomes. Therefore, a model is needed to identify the resources of comparative advantage in the convenience store competition that contribute to economic growth.

Finally, although international retailers played an important part in the modernization of the United Kingdom's convenience store sector, the discussion in this research did not cover this issue in-depth and mentioned the role of international retailers. Thus, another possible research direction is to test whether a difference exists between convenience store retailers with international retailers' assistance and those without. For example, whether retailers with international know-how operate more efficiently than purely local retailers and whether "the country-of-origin" effect exists in the retail industry.

The application of the Marketing Mix 7P to the convenience stores in the United Kingdom sector is being empirically tested for the first time with this study. More empirical research should be done in various settings, such as marketplaces or alternative forms like the hypermarket and the supermarket in other countries, to further elaborate the theoretical framework and to strengthen the applicability of the Marketing Mix 7P's to the convenience store retail industry.

6.5 Summary

This chapter presents the results of a study examining the impact of a marketing mix 7Ps strategy on convenience stores' profitability in the United Kingdom. This research finding also restates the problem description and identifies solutions based on it. It also highlights how the study's findings could help the industry. Also, explore in greater

depth the research findings and their implications: theoretical implications, managerial implications, future research and the limitations of the study.

This study provides a variety of insights for convenience store managers and owners based on the results of the empirical investigation. To begin with, it offers two important pieces of knowledge and insight: 1) A total picture of the present state of convenience stores in the United Kingdom; 2) What has been the overall pattern of customer purchasing behaviour in convenience stores in the UK? Secondly, this research provides the following information from the viewpoint of the consumer: 1) It demonstrates broad consumer behaviour trends such as beliefs, perceptions, personal opinions, purchasing trends, and customer expectations; and 2) It provides an in-depth understanding of what consumers seek in convenience stores. Furthermore, the study offers a broad perspective on the marketing strategy's implementation situations in the United Kingdom, illustrating which variables in marketing mix 7Ps strategies would have a significant impact on profitability.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

Questionnaire

MARKETING MIX STRATEGY								
Below are statements about Marketing Mix Strategy . Please indicate your general impressions of this topic.								
No.	Items	1) Strongly disagree	2) Disagree	3) Somewhat disagree	4) Neutral	5) Somewhat agree	6) Agree	7) Strongly agree
1	Do you use marketing strategy in your business?							
PART 1: PRODUCT								
2	Your company offers several varieties of products to choose.							
3	Your company offers high quality Products.							
4	Your products meet customer's requirements.							
5	Your company gives room for product warranty.							
6	Your product has good packaging and attractive.							
PART 2: PROMOTION								
7	People know your products based on your promotional strategy.							
8	Your company applies advertising as one of the promotional strategy.							

9	Your company applies personal selling as one of the promotional strategy.							
10	Promotions consider the public understanding.							
11	Your product is promoted on events (exhibitions).							

PART 3: PRICE

12	The price of the products is reasonable.							
13	This company offers the overall lowest price in the area.							
14	The pricing decisions allow for discounts.							
15	The pricing decision allows for credit terms.							
16	Provide products with different price range.							
17	Maintains the best everyday price for most products.							
18	The company uses pricing skills and systems to respond quickly to market changes.							

PART 4: PLACE/DISTRIBUTION

19	Fast checkout.							
20	Have distribution channels easy to find.							
21	Convenient public transport to get to this convenience store.							
22	Your company is near to most resident/working areas.							

PART 5: PEOPLE

23	Your organization have well-trained staff.							
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24	Most of your staff have work experience in convenience store.							
25	Your employees practice great customer service.							
26	Your organization have great team leader.							
27	Your employees knowledgeable about all product in store.							

PART 6: PROCESS

28	Your organization educate and support customers on an ongoing basis.							
29	Are your customers being serviced excellently?							
30	Are your customers get all product information they need?							
31	The store offers speedy delivery of service.							
32	The store opens and close at convenient time.							

PART 7: PHYSICAL EVIDENCE

33	Your store are well organized.							
34	Your store are clean and tidy environment.							
35	Your store are impressive with nice design and decoration.							

PART 8: PROFITABILITY INDICATORS

36	Your company achieved maximum profitability in the last three years due to product strategy.							
37	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to promotional strategy.							

38	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to pricing strategy.							
39	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to distribution strategy.							
40	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to people strategy.							
41	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to process strategy.							
42	Your company achieved maximum profitability due to physical evidence strategy.							

A FEW THINGS ABOUT YOURSELF

In order to get fully understanding about your opinion on the marketing strategies on profitability of convenience store, please answer the following questions.

1. Gender Male Female

2. Age:

3. Please provide the name of the most recent degree you received.

High school Undergraduate postgraduate and above

4. Please choose the option from the list below that best describes your current job situation. Only one box needs to be checked.

Currently, I am employed

- Owner of a company
- Top executive or manager
- Office/clerical staffs
- Worker
- Other

I would like to express my gratitude once more for your gracious cooperation and the contribution of your valuable time. The order in which the questions were asked was determined by Krueger's recommendations (1994).

APPENDIX 2

Definitions of the constructs

Constructs	Definition	Ref
Extended Marketing Mix Strategy	There are seven marketing elements in the extended marketing mix (7P's), all of which aim to achieve the marketing strategy's objectives. "The following are the 7 components: product, price, location, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence". Marketing is a constantly evolving discipline, and as such, companies can find themselves falling far behind the competition if they remain stagnant for too long.	Mas et al., 2018
Product Differentiation	"Product differentiation refers to physical goods or services for which a consumer is willing to pay a premium. Consumers purchase both tangible goods like furniture, clothing, and groceries and intangible products like services. The most important component of any marketing mix is the product. A product's life cycle is divided into three stages: growth, maturity, and sales decline". When sales start to go down, marketing companies have to come up with new ways to make people want to buy their products.	Larimo et al., 2018
Promotion Variation	"Promotion is comprised of various combinations of its constituents that are being used to achieve the company's marketing objectives". Promoting products and services is one of the most effective components of the marketing mix. Publicity, public relations, exhibitions, and demonstrations, among other things, are used in sales promotion. The level of marketing expenditure on promotion is determined by the marketing manager. Generally speaking, promotional activities are intended to complement personal selling, advertising, and public relations efforts. Promotion assists the trader and sales force in effectively representing the product to the public and convincing them to purchase it". "The positioning of the product in the target market is determined by the promotion variation. It should be seen as an expense,	Larimo et al., 2018

	and because of that, the price of a product should increase”.	
Price Variation	“Price variation can be defined as the amount of money that the consumer must exchange in order to obtain the offering”. Prices of products are influenced by a range of factors, and as a result, they fluctuate on a continuous basis. Pricing should be versatile in order to meet these different variants. While it is true that the product's pricing will generally change if all of the variables change, this is not always the case. The most important things to consider when setting prices are the cost of the product, the marketing strategy, the costs of distribution and advertising, and any other price changes in the market.	Dadzie et al., 2017
Place	The Place could be defined as the firm's warehousing facilities, distribution channels, inventory control and type of moving, and organisation, therefore it is a method of transporting goods and services from the provider and manufacturer to the consumer. Because distribution has such a large impact on company profitability, businesses must have a solid logistics management and supply chain strategy in place.	Dadzie et al., 2017
People	"People refers to any individual who is directly or indirectly involved in the operation of a business, as defined in the marketing mix. This group includes people who work in marketing, team management, the sale of a product or service, recruiting, customer service, and training”.	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019
Process	The process is defined as the standard operation that is followed while providing the service. Subject on the circumstances and the situation, staffs at a convenience store may be needed to smile, greet, and be friendly to customers.	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019
Physical Evidence	Physical evidence is a tangible component of a service that allows consumers to evaluate it. It is the physical component that is more or less complementary to the service. “Physical evidence includes the environment or location in which the service is provided, as well as	Saidani and Sudiarditha, 2019

	any tangible components that aid in the performance or communication of the service". In a convenience store, for example, the physical evidence will include things like the staff's uniform, the cleanliness of the store, the spraying of pleasant room freshener, and so on.	
Profitability	Profitability refers to a business's ability to generate a profit. A profit is the amount of money left over after a business's income has been paid for all expenses that are directly related to revenue generation, such as other expenses related to the operation and the manufacturing of a product.	Bishnoi and Devi, 2017

Table 1.1 Definitions of constructs

Source: The Researcher

APPENDIX 3

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study:

THE IMPACTS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES ON THE PROFITABILITY OF CONVENIENCE STORE IN THE UNITED KINGDOM

You've been selected to participate in a study about which you've been informed. Before you decide whether or not to participate in the research, you need to know why it's being done and what it entails. If you have the time, please read the following information carefully and share your thoughts on it with others. Please let me know if anything is unclear or if you require additional details. Please give yourself plenty of time to make up your mind about participating or not.

Introduction

Norziana Ismail is the author of this study, and she is currently pursuing a DBA at the University of the West of Scotland in the United Kingdom. The purpose of this research is to investigate the effects of marketing strategies on the profitability of a convenience store in London.

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to complete a survey about your opinions on marketing strategies used by convenience stores. This questionnaire is being used as part of a research project, and we would like to express our gratitude for taking the time to fill it out. The successful completion of this project is dependent on your cooperation. Whether or not this investigation is successful will be entirely dependent on the information provided by you. Taking part in the survey that has been enclosed is entirely optional.

It is important to note that your participation and any data collected will be kept anonymous, and that the responses will only be presented in aggregate form with no individual names disclosed. Filling out the questionnaire will take you only a few minutes of your time.

What is the purpose of this research?

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on profitability in order to measure the relationship marketing strategy effectiveness of convenience store in London. It is useful to investigate the concept further in order to complement existing studies given the significance of the marketing strategy and build upon the evidence discussed.

Do you have to take part?

You have the right to withdraw from the research without consequence if you choose not to participate (participation is voluntary). You also have the right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the research if you choose not to participate.

What will you do in the project?

A questionnaire will be given to you to complete as part of the research. It will take you only a few minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Why have you been invited to take part?

The study aims to include who are being in charge of the convenience store business such as shop owner or store manager. You have been invited to take part because it related with the research topic in retail industry of convenience store.

What information is being collected in the project?

The project is only collecting information that is relevant to the research topic.

Who will have access to the information?

Full consent from participants will allow data to be used within my postgraduate thesis. Only researcher and UWS member Staff's such as lead supervisor will have access to the information collected.

Where will the information be stored and how long will it be kept for?

The data will be stored on a password-protected laptop, and subjects can remain anonymous.

UWS will keep data storage and retention information. Personal information should only be kept for as long as it is absolutely necessary. By storing anonymous research data in a suitable data repository, it is possible to keep it indefinitely.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

Ethics approval for this study was granted by the University of the West of Scotland's Ethics Committee. If you have any questions or concerns during or after the research, or if you would like to speak with an independent person to whom any questions or concerns can be directed or from whom further information can be sought, please contact the following address:

Personal details withheld.

APPENDIX 4

Consent Form

Title of the study:

THE IMPACTS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES ON PROFITABILITY OF CONVENIENCE STORE IN LONDON

- I certify that I have read and comprehended the participant information sheet for the above project, and that the researcher has satisfactorily answered any questions I may have.
- I certify that I have read and understand the Privacy Notice for Participants in Research Projects and that I understand how my personal information will be used and what will happen to it after it has been collected (i.e., how it will be stored and for how long).
- I understand that my participation is entirely voluntary, and that I am free to leave the project at any time, up to the point of completion, without explanation or repercussions.
- I understand that I have the right to request that some of my personal information be removed from the study, and that researchers will comply whenever possible.
- I understand that once anonymised data (data that does not identify me personally) has been included in the study, it cannot be withdrawn.
- I understand that any information recorded in the research will be kept confidential and that no information identifying me will be made public.
- I give my permission to participate in the project.

Name:

Signature of Participant:

Date:

APPENDIX 5

Correlation analysis of all variables.

Correlations

		PRO D_T OTA L	PRO M_TO TAL	PRIC TOTA L	PLAC _TOT AL	PP_ TOT AL	PROC _TOT AL	PHY_ TOTA L	PROF _TOT AL
PRO D_T OTA L	Pearson Correlati on	1	.911**	.829**	.611**	.807**	.738**	.790**	.701**
	Sig. (2- tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.00 0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PRO M_T OTA L	Pearson Correlati on	.911**	1	.847**	.576**	.747**	.671**	.696**	.644**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.00 0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PRIC _TOT AL	Pearson Correlati on	.829**	.847**	1	.696**	.819**	.782**	.868**	.816**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.00 0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PLA C_T OTA L	Pearson Correlati on	.611**	.576**	.696**	1	.673**	.635**	.668**	.590**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.00 0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PP_T OTA L	Pearson Correlati on	.807**	.747**	.819**	.673**	1	.942**	.730**	.647**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PRO C_T OTA L	Pearson Correlati on	.738**	.671**	.782**	.635**	.942**	1	.748**	.642**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.00 0		0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PHY_ TOT AL	Pearson Correlati on	.790**	.696**	.868**	.668**	.730**	.748**	1	.830**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
PRO F_TOTAL	Pearson Correlation	.701**	.644**	.816**	.590**	.647**	.642**	.830**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).									